

**PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF
BIOCOMPATIBLE POLYMER-MAGNETIC
NANOCOMPOSITES**

A Thesis

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements for Award of the Degree of

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY

in

NANO SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

by

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MUKKA, KANNADA, INDIA

March 2021

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I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this thesis are original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This thesis is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

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Certificate

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “**Preparation and Characterization of Biocompatible Polymer-Magnetic Nanocomposites**” submitted by **Mrs. Bhavya M. S.** to SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY for the award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy is a Bonafide record of the research work carried out by her under my supervision and guidance. The content of the thesis, in full or parts have not been submitted to any other institute or university for the award of any degree or diploma.

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Acknowledgements

This thesis of mine was possible only due to the incessant prayers, guidance, support, cooperation, assistance, encouragement and good wishes of a number of people to whom I owe a great debt of gratitude. I feel the presence of unseen hands of GOD in providing me with people, material, enlightenment and opportunities to complete the research work without any hassle. I bow my head to him for the innumerable blessings showered on me and my family.

With a grateful heart I am immensely pleased to place on record of gratitude to my research guide, Dr. Prasad P., Professor, Centre for Nano Science and Technology, Srinivas University College of Engineering and Technology, Mangaluru, for giving me an opportunity to complete doctoral studies in his research group, for his invaluable, meticulous and untiring guidance and positive criticism of this research work.

I am very much thankful to Shri. CA. A. Raghavendra Rao, Honourable Chancellor, Srinivas University, Dr. A. Shrinivasa Rao, Honourable Pro-Chancellor, Srinivas University, for providing the infrastructure facility to carry out my research work comfortably. I thank Dr. P. Shreeramana Aithal, Honourable Vice-Chancellor, Srinivas University, Dr. Anil Kumar, Honourable Registrar, Srinivas University, Dr. Srinivasa Mayya D., Honourable Registrar Evaluation, Srinivas University, and Prinicpal, Srinivas Institute of Technology for their support and motivation.

A great deal of credit goes to my husband Mr. Shekar Dammur, my children Master Skanda and Baby Brunda, my beloved parents, Sri. Sadananda Mundodi and Smt. Ravikala, my brother, Mr. Bhavan M. S. and beloved Mr. Lokanath Amachoor and Mr. Thejaprasadh Amachoor who are behind all my success and without their support I would not have reached this stage.

I am also greatly indebted to Dr. Savitha M. B., Associate Professor, Department of Chemistry and Research Centre, Sahyadri College of Engineering and Management, Adyar, Mangaluru for her support throughout my research work. I also place in record my appreciation for the encouragement from Mr. Shareefraju J. Ukkund, and Mr. Naveen Kumar J. R., my fellow researchers who were with me from the beginning and have been a great support and have helped me timely in all my hardships.

I thank the authorities of IISc Bangalore, University of Mysore, Mangalore University, SJEC Mysore, NITK, Surathkal for permitting me to carry out literature survey and analysis of research samples throughout my research work.

Mrs. Bhavya M. S.

Symbols and Abbreviations

f	:	Ultrasonic wave frequency
λ	:	Wavelength
n	:	Refractive index
ρ	:	Density
β_{ad}	:	Adiabatic compressibility
v	:	Ultrasonic velocity
T _g	:	Glass transition temperature
η_r	:	Relative viscosity
η_{sp}	:	Specific viscosity
Mag	:	Maghemite
ATR	:	Attenuated Total Reflectance
DSC	:	Differential Scanning Calorimetry
SEM	:	Scanning Electron Microscopy
FTIR	:	Fourier Transform Infra Red Spectroscopy
NMR	:	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy
TGA	:	Thermo-Gravimetric Analysis
UTM	:	Universal Testing Machine
ASTM	:	American Society for Testing and Materials
USLV	:	Ubbelohde Suspended Level Viscometer
FESEM	:	Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope
SE	:	Secondary electrons
BSE	:	Back scattered electrons
DTA	:	Differential thermal analysis
CL	:	Cathodoluminescence
MRI	:	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
GG	:	Guar gum
HPMC	:	Hydroxypropylmethylcellulose
PVA	:	Poly (vinyl alcohol)
XG	:	Xanthan gum
PAA	:	Poly (acrylamide-co-acrylic acid)
PVP	:	Poly (vinyl pyrrolidone)
CMNC	:	Ceramic Matrix Nano Composites

MMNC	:	Metal Matrix Nano Composites
PMNC	:	Polymer Matrix Nano Composites
IPN	:	Inter Penetrating Network
MNPs	:	Metal Nano Particles
PNIPAM	:	Poly-(N-isopropyl acrylamide)
PDMAEMA	:	Poly ((2-dimethylamino) ethyl methacrylate)
PLLA	:	Poly lactide acid
PLGA	:	Poly(1-lactide acid-co-glycolide)
PNC	:	Polymer Nano Composite
LCST	:	Lower critical solution temperature
DMS	:	Dimethyl sulfate
MC	:	Methylcellulose
PVA	:	Poly(vinyl alcohol)

Synopsis

The present thesis reports, the results of investigations carried out on title **“Preparation and Characterization of Biocompatible Polymer-Magnetic Nanocomposites”**. This thesis also reports the results of solution state studies by refractive index, ultrasonic velocity, density, and viscosity methods, chemical group analysis of polymer blends in solid state by FTIR, morphology by SEM, DSC-Tg measurements, thermal degradation property by TGA, mechanical properties (tensile strength), physicochemical evaluation and drug release kinetic study.

Water soluble polymers have been studied by several researchers due to their blood compatibility, non-toxic, non-immunogenic, non-mutagenic and non-carcinogenic nature. Synthetic and natural polymers are used for numerous applications in the biomedical field. However the properties of pure synthetic polymers and those of pure biological polymers alone are often inadequate to produce materials with good combination of chemical, mechanical, thermal and biological performance characteristics. Hence a set of new polymeric materials (biocompatible polymer blends) have been prepared by blending the natural, semi-synthetic and synthetic water soluble polymers like hydroxypropylmethylcellulose (HPMC), Xanthan gum (XG), Guar gum (GG), Methylcellulose (MC) and Poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA). Further biocompatible maghemite nanoparticles were used to prepare polymer blend – nanocomposites and studied for the compatibilising effect of maghemite on polymer blends.

The properties of polymer blends depend on their miscibility at molecular level. Solution techniques are providing as much information as solid state techniques to probe miscibility of polymer blends. Hence the miscibility of the polymer blends are studied in solution state and then it is confirmed in solid state. In solution state the miscible windows of polymer blends are identified by using simple and rapid techniques such as ultrasonic velocity, refractive index, and density. Further, the miscibility in solution state is confirmed by viscometry at 30°C and 40°C. The miscibility of polymer blends in solid state is studied by analyzing the chemical properties (functional group analysis) by FTIR, morphology by SEM and glass transition temperature (Tg) measurements by DSC methods. The miscible polymer blends are analyzed for their thermal degradation properties (TGA), mechanical properties, and drug release kinetics. All the maghemite nanocomposites were studied in solution state by density, ultrasonic velocity, and

viscosity methods and the compatible blends were characterized by FTIR, SEM, DSC, TGA, tensile strength and drug release kinetics.

In the present study Abbe's refractometer, specific gravity bottle, ultrasonic interferometer (M/S Mittal enterprises, New Delhi), Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer (USLV), NICOLET AVATAR 530 spectrophotometer, ZEISS Sigma FESEM 300 analyzer, TA Q200 Differential Scanning Calorimeter, Thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA Q50 V20.2 Build 27), LLYODS UK model analyzer (LR 100K) and Double beam spectrophotometer 2202 (SYSTRONICS) are used for refractometric, density, ultrasonic, viscometry, FTIR, SEM, DSC, thermal degradation property, tensile strength measurement and drug release kinetic studies, respectively. The entire work is represented in seven chapters.

Chapter 1 is divided in to two sections. In the first section (*Section A*) a general introduction is given to biocompatibility, biocompatible polymers, polymer blends, miscibility of polymer blends, experimental methods to determine miscibility, applications of polymer blends, magnetic nanoparticles, iron oxide nanoparticles, superparamagnetism in magnetic nanoparticles, maghemite, properties and applications of iron oxide nanoparticles and maghemite, polymer-magnetic nanocomposites, and controlled drug delivery systems. This section concludes with detailed literature in the field of water soluble biocompatible polymer blends, polymer-iron oxide nanocomposites, and the objective and scope of the present work. *Section B* gives the detailed introduction to the materials used in the preparation of biocompatible polymer blends/composites, their chemistry and properties, and different methods & methodologies adopted for the characterization of the prepared polymer blends in solution and solid states (thin films).

Chapter 2 deals with the preparation and miscibility studies of guar gum (GG)/methylcellulose (MC) blend in the solution and solid states. 0.02 wt% maghemite nanoparticles were found suitable for the preparation of polymer/blend – composites. The refractive index, ultrasonic velocity, density, and viscosity were measured for pure GG, MC, and their blends (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10). Adiabatic compressibility was calculated using ultrasonic velocity and density data. The plot of these against blend/blend-nanocomposite composition showed both linear and non linear regions, indicating semi-miscibility/compatibility.

. Chapter 3 presents the miscibility studies of guar gum (GG)/hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) blends in solution and solid states. The refractive index, ultrasonic velocity, density, adiabatic compressibility, and viscosity were measured for

pure GG, HPMC and their blends (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10). Adiabatic compressibility was calculated using ultrasonic velocity and density data. The plot of these against blend composition showed linear and non-linear regions, indicating semi-miscibility. Reduced viscosity plots against concentration showed higher slope variation for compositions with 50% or more GG in the blend. The solid state miscibility study was done for thin films of pure GG, HPMC and their blends prepared by solution casting method. A SEM study reveals that in the GG/HPMC blend HPMC granules were well distributed in the GG matrix, confirming a good interaction between the polymers. FTIR measurement and DSC-Tg analysis confirmed the intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions in GG/HPMC blends. Thermal and mechanical properties were reported with TGA and tensile strength measurements. 0.02 wt% maghemite nanoparticles showed compatibilising effect on GG/HPMC blends in solution and solid state, studied by density, ultrasonic velocity, adiabatic compressibility, viscosity, SEM, FTIR, DSC-Tg, TGA, and tensile strength measurement methods.

Chapter 4 reports the miscibility studies of Xanthan gum (XG)/methylcellulose (MC) blends in solution and solid states. Refractive index, ultrasonic velocity, density and adiabatic compressibility studies reveals the miscible nature of XG/MC blends in solution. It is observed from the plots of refractive index, ultrasonic velocity, density and adiabatic compressibility against % composition that 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 XG/MC blend compositions showed linearity at both 30°C and 40°C. Hence it confirms that XG/MC blend is miscible in aqueous solution when XG content is more than 50% in the blend. The viscosity plots showed linearity and higher slope variation for 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 XG/MC blend compositions attributes to the increase in hydrodynamic volume. The homogeneity and hydrogen bonding interactions in solid state is confirmed by SEM, FTIR and DSC-Tg measurement methods. Temperature characteristics and mechanical properties were studied by TGA and tensile strength measurements. The influence of maghemite nanoparticles (0.02 wt% and 0.03 wt%) on the blending of XG/MC blends were studied by density, ultrasonic velocity, and viscosity measurements. It is observed that the presence of 0.02 wt% maghemite improved the miscibility nature in solution state indicated by the linearity of the plots. Whereas, maghemite nanoparticles with 0.03 wt% does not improve the miscibility characteristics. The solid state studies were performed with SEM, FTIR, DSC-Tg, TGA, and tensile strength measurements

Chapter 5 presents miscibility studies of xanthan gum (XG)/Poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) blends in solution and solid states. The refractive index, ultrasonic velocity and density were measured for pure XG, PVA and their blends (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30,

and 90/10). Adiabatic compressibility was calculated using ultrasonic velocity and density data. The plot of these against blend composition showed linear regions, indicating miscibility at both 30°C and 40°C. Viscosity measurements confirmed the miscibility of XG/PVA blends. The temperature did not have any significant effect on the miscibility of XG/PVA blends. The solid state miscibility study was done for thin films of XG/PVA blends prepared by solution casting method. The SEM, FTIR, and DSC-Tg measurements proved the presence of hydrogen bonding between XG and PVA in their blends. Temperature and mechanical characteristics were reported with TGA and tensile strength measurement studies. The influence of 0.02 wt% and 0.03 wt% maghemite nanoparticles on XG/PVA blends in solution state were also studied by density, ultrasonic velocity, adiabatic compressibility, and viscosity measurements and confirmed the compatibility. Further the blend – maghemite nanocomposites were characterized by SEM, FTIR, DSC-Tg, TGA and tensile strength measurement techniques.

Chapter 6 reports the transdermal drug release applications of GG/MC, GG/HPMC, XG/MC, and XG/PVA blends and their maghemite nanocomposites. The metoprolol model drug infused thin films (patches) of all the pure polymers and their maghemite nanocomposites, and miscible blend compositions, and compatible blend – maghemite nanocomposites were evaluated for their physicochemical properties such as thickness, weight, folding endurance, percentage moisture absorption and percentage moisture loss. These parameters are important for the applications of the patches for transdermal drug release systems. The drug release kinetics studies revealed that all the patches showed diffusion of the drug and were slow, sustained release of the drug, metoprolol succinate, and follows Fickian kinetics. Hence these biomaterials can be useful for slow, sustained release formulations for transdermal systems.

Chapter 7 gives the detailed conclusions of the present study and the scope for the future works.

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Chapter- 1

Introduction Materials and Methods

“I also believe that a person who does not have respect for time, and does not have a sense of timing, can achieve little.”

- Vikram Sarabhai

Chapter 1

Section A

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Biocompatibility

Biocompatible materials are those which function in a specific biological environment. These include all living things like human beings, animals, and plants. A biomaterial can interact with biological system to treat and evaluate. It can also be used as a supplement, or to replace any parts of the body [1]. The studies on the applications of biocompatible materials for permanent use as prosthetic devices have increased recently [2]. Prosthetic devices are artificial replacement of body parts. Biocompatible materials are rapidly replacing non-biocompatible materials such as metals, alloys, and ceramics in prosthetic devices [3].

Biocompatible materials show the property called biocompatibility. Biocompatibility is the ability of the material to function as a part of living things without disturbing it or getting destroyed. Many chemical, physical, and biological characteristics of materials like its molecular weight, solubility, and miscibility can influence their biocompatibility [4]. Many polymers are proved to be biocompatible. Since the human body is a complicated system a single polymer may not suit for all the applications. Hence newer biocompatible polymers are synthesised. The study of the multifunctionality of the biocompatible polymer and different combinational studies are necessary for the design of a device to be used as a prosthetic device.

Biocompatible polymers can also mimic the properties of tissues, and hence finds applications as bone plates, bone screws, and in tissue engineering [5]. Another potential application is as controlled drug delivery vehicle. For this specific application their structure and degradation parameters are need to be engineered [6].

1.2 Biocompatible Polymers

Based on the origin, biocompatible polymers can be classified as natural, synthetic, and semi-synthetic.

1.2.1 Natural biocompatible polymeric materials

Starch, silk, collagen, alginates, chitin (which is a group of polysaccharides), fibrin (which is a group of proteins), and natural gum (polymers obtained from plants, and microorganism) are biocompatible [7]. Other recognised biocompatible material of natural origin includes polyhydroxy alkanooate (a class of biocompatible polyester), sundew adhesives, and ivy nanoparticles. Sundew adhesives are natural polysaccharide-based hydrogels. Arabinogalactan proteins are found on cell surface of most plant species and supports cellular processes such as growth, pattern forming, reproduction, etc. Certain spherically shaped arabinogalactan proteins are called ivy nanoparticles [8, 9].

1.2.2 Synthetic and semi-synthetic biocompatible polymers

Natural biocompatible polymers finds applications such as to support the cell functions and as adhesives. The mechanical properties of natural polymers are comparatively poor and they degrade faster limiting their applications. Natural polymers are also vulnerable to microbes and virus attack [10, 11]. Semi-synthetic polymers are the modified form of natural polymers. Semi-synthetic polymers and synthetic polymers are having better chemical and mechanical properties than that of natural polymers. But most of the semi-synthetic and synthetic polymers are not biocompatible [12].

Recently, many semi-synthetic and synthetic polymers developed are biocompatible. The major issues with non-biocompatible polymers as prosthetic devices are inflammation and followed by scar formation. The non-biocompatible polymers are the foreign object to human body, and the immune system responds to these irritants causing inflammation. These issues can be avoided by the use of biocompatible synthetic/semi-synthetic polymers [13]. The synthetic biocompatible polymer used in this research work is poly (vinyl alcohol) and the semi-synthetic biocompatible polymers include methylcellulose, and hydroxypropyl methylcellulose.

1.3 Polymer Blends and Miscibility

This section is sub-divided in to polyblends (or polymer blends), miscibility of polyblends, experimental methods to determine miscibility, and applications of polyblends.

1.3.1 Polymer blends

Polyblends are prepared by mixing two or more than two polymers using physical methods. The individual polymers used may not be having same chemical and/or physical properties. The polymer mixtures of two polymers are known as binary polymer blends, and mixture of three polymers are known as ternary polymer blends. The polymers in these mixtures do not develop covalent bonds between them. The attractive forces which make them to mix to each other are secondary forces (dipole-dipole, and H – bonding). Dipole-dipole interactions exist if the polymers are polar in nature; the partial positively charges formed in first polymer are attracted towards the partial negative charge formed in the second polymer and vice-versa. The hydrogen bonding interaction is possible with partial positively charged hydrogen of one of the polymers with partial negatively charged elements such as oxygen, nitrogen, etc. of the other polymer.

Due to the complicate structure of long chain polymer molecules (coiled/uncoiled structures and zigzag arrangements) it is always not easy for a researcher to predict the homogeneous mixing of polymers through secondary forces. The secondary forces of interaction among polymer mixtures are also dependent on their concentration, pH of the medium, temperature, etc.

Than developing new material, polymer blending is a simple and effective approach for a particular application. Basic cost reduction, enhancement of properties, and improved processibility are the added advantages of preparing polymer blends [14]. The processibility is the ability of the material to be processed (to a desired shape or as a device) for their applications. The mixtures of polymer may exhibit newer property or a combination of their individual properties depending on their miscibility.

1.3.2 Miscibility of polymer blends

The properties of polyblends are superior to any one of the individual polymers used in it, if they are miscible [15]. The term ‘miscibility’ refers homogeneity in mixing of the molecules. Depending upon the homogeneity of obtained product the blends may be classified as miscible, semi-miscible, and immiscible polymer blends.

In miscible polymer blends the polymer mixture is homogeneous at all concentrations. Semi-miscibility of polymer blends indicates that the polymer mixture is homogeneous at a particular composition and immiscible when that concentration is varied. Immiscible polymer blends are those which is non-homogeneous at all concentrations.

If the polymer blend is immiscible also, such multi-phase polymer blends have got applications. Introduction of specific interactions (acid-base, hydrogen bonding, dipole interactions, etc.) are the best methods of enhancing miscibility of polymers. All these contribute to the negative enthalpy of mixing (exothermic mixing) [16, 17]. The two types of miscible polymer blends are:

- (i) miscible polymer blends having weak or little interactions and
- (ii) miscible polymer blends having strong specific interactions [18].

Not only the presence of secondary attractive forces makes the polymer miscible, polymers with similar solubility parameters are also found to be miscible [19]. Most of the polymer blends are heterogeneous or immiscible blends. These immiscible blends may be made homogeneous by adding suitable compatibilising agents. The compatibilising agents introduce secondary attractive forces among the polymers.

1.3.3 Experimental methods to determine the miscibility

In solid-state (in the form of thin films) Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), etc. are some of the experimental methods used to investigate the miscible nature of polymers [20-23].

When polymers are dissolved in a suitable solvent, the long-chain coiled structure opens up allows the possible interaction between the other polymers. These interactions will affect their viscosity, density, refractive index, responds to ultrasonic waves, etc. As the polymers are highly viscous at higher concentrations dilute solution viscometry is one of the effective methods to assess the polymer-polymer, polymer-solvent interactions. Hence a large number of investigations carried out with a ternary system of polymer1, polymer 2, and a solvent [24-26]. Additional advantages of dilute solution viscometry is that the equipment required is not sophisticated (viscometer made of glass, or simple rotation viscometer), and the crystallinity or morphological state will not affect the study. Thus dilute solution viscometry is more convenient and handy method of characterizing polymer mixtures. Many other techniques such as refractive index, ultrasonic velocity, and density of the polymer blends in solution were also reported [27-32].

1.3.4 Applications of polymer blends

The polymer blends/blend-composites finds applications in nano-industry, electronic devices and batteries, membrane and plastic industry, sensors, catalyst, and medical applications. Considering the raw material cost for the production of new

material which is about 40% to 80% as that of the obtained product, blending of existing polymers have economic advantages. This reduces the cost of the investment on a new chemical plant. They also have an attractive cost/performance ratio. An expensive polymer can be blended with a less expensive one for the given application. Now a day the release profile of a drug formulation is controlled through the use of biocompatible polymer blends [33, 34].

The polyblends or polymer blend-composites show high performance at very low price, their performance can be altered based on the demand, expensive resins can be blended with less expensive ones, used plastic wastes can be re-used, and are unique products.

Even the multiphase polymer blends (immiscible polymer blends) have also commercial applications [35]. The mechanical properties of immiscible polymers can be improved by the usage of compatibilizers, which will release the repulsive stress between the polymers in the mixture.

1.4 Magnetic Nanoparticles

Nanoparticles are being used in different fields of research in biomedicine, because of their unique properties. One of the prime considerations is nanoparticles stability in biological environments. Biomolecules are also biopolymers, they are long chain molecules. Experimental observations showed that nanoparticles undergo steric stabilization. The biopolymers adsorb on the surface of nanoparticles stabilizing them. The steric stabilization of nanoparticles creates opportunity for them in drug delivery systems [36].

Magnetic nanoparticles find numerous applications in information storage, as ferrofluids, for audio-video recording tapes, bioprocessing, gas sensing, refrigeration, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), etc. [37]. They also find applications in magnetically controlled drug delivery systems, diagnostics, biosensing, nucleic acid purification, cloning, and cell separation [38-41]. Magnetic nanorods, nanotubes, and nanowires find applications in microfluidics, data storage, and magnetic force microscopes [42-44]. Core-shell structures of magnetic nanoparticles with biomolecules have been studied and characterized using different analytical methods and have applications in biosensing, immunosensing, and monitoring [45-47].

1.5 Iron Oxide Magnetic Nanoparticles

Iron oxides are transition metal oxides. 16 pure phases of iron oxides are known to date and are given in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1: Types of iron oxides

Types	Chemical formula	Common name	Colour
Oxides	α -Fe ₂ O ₃	Hematite	Red
	β -Fe ₂ O ₃	(Synthetic)	--
	γ -Fe ₂ O ₃	Maghemite	Red-brown
	ε -Fe ₂ O ₃	(Synthetic)	--
	Fe ₃ O ₄	Magnetite	Black
Oxide hydroxide	FeO	Wustite	Black
	α -FeOOH	Goethite	Yellow-brown
	β -FeOOH	Akagenite	Yellow-brown
	γ -FeOOH	Lepidocrocite	Orange
	δ -FeOOH	(Synthetic)	Red-brown
	δ -FeOOH	Feroxyite	Red-brown
	Fe ₁₆ O ₁₆ (OH) _y (SO ₄) _z .nH ₂ O	Schwertmannite	Yellow-brown
	High-pressure FeOOH	(Synthetic)	--
Hydroxides	Fe ₅ HO ₈ .4H ₂ O	Ferrihydrite	Red-brown
	Fe(OH) ₃	Bemalite	Green
	Fe(OH) ₂	(Synthetic)	White

Their important characteristics are the trivalent state, low solubility, and brilliant colours. The four main fields of applications of iron oxides are listed below [48]:

1. Soil science, mineralogy: Soil science is the study of properties of soil and the management of soil. Mineralogy is the study of properties of minerals. The iron oxides used for these applications are goethite, hematite, magnetite, ferrihydrite, maghemite, akaganeite.
2. Corrosion science: The factors affecting the rate of corrosion and prevention of corrosion are termed as corrosion science. Maghemite, magnetite, and lepidocrocite find applications in corrosion science.
3. Industry: The most industrially applied iron oxides are hematite, magnetite, goethite, ferrihydrite, and maghemite.

4. Biology: The iron oxides having applications in biological studies are ferrihydrite, lepidocrocite, magnetite, and goethite.

α -Fe₂O₃ & γ -Fe₂O₃ occur in nature, whereas β -Fe₂O₃ & ε -Fe₂O₃ are synthesized [49]. Nanosized iron oxides show superparamagnetism. They are non-toxic and biocompatible. The cost of production of nanosized iron oxide nanoparticles are comparatively less [50]. Curie temperature is the critical temperature above which materials lose their permanent magnetic property. Nanosized iron oxides show low Curie temperature. The measure of a materials ability to get magnetized in an applied magnetic field is its magnetic susceptibility. Nanosized iron oxide nanoparticles are having high magnetic susceptibility. In recent years researches in both the crystalline and amorphous Fe₂O₃ have attracted much interest [51]. Magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles are safe and stable [52].

1.5.1 Superparamagnetism in iron oxide magnetic nanoparticles

Iron oxide nanoparticles show superparamagnetism [53]. Superparamagnetism is observed due to size reduction in magnetic materials in the nano scale. This phenomenon is observed in small ferromagnetic or ferrimagnetic nanoparticles. Ferrimagnetic materials are those in which some of the magnetic domain point in the same directions whereas they all point in the same direction in ferromagnetic materials. In sufficiently small size, a random flip in direction with change in temperature is observed and time between two successive flips are the Neel relaxation time.

1.5.2 Maghemite (γ -Fe₂O₃)

The ability of a material to exist in more than one form is known as polymorphism. The second most common polymorph of iron oxide is γ -Fe₂O₃ (maghemite). It can exist in bulk as well as nanosize. Maghemite contains positively charged ions in two sites namely tetrahedral and octahedral positions. Figure 1.1 gives the crystal structure of maghemite. The γ -Fe₂O₃ is cubic in structure with each unit contains $2\frac{1}{3}$ vacancies, 32 O²⁻ ions, and $21\frac{1}{3}$ Fe³⁺ ions [53]. Oxygen ions are arranged in cubic close-packing, whereas ferric ions are in tetrahedral and octahedral sites. Depending on the ordering of vacancies 3 different crystal structures of maghemite have reported [54]; a cubic vacancy (disordered) structure, a cubic vacancy (ordered) structure, and a tetragonal.

Figure 1.1: Crystal structure of $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$

Like magnetite, maghemite is also ferromagnetic. It has a quick response towards magnetic field and gets magnetized instantaneously. The theory of super magnetism was developed while studying the properties of maghemite. At higher temperatures (above a threshold value) $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ will be converted to $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$. Several parameters decide the threshold value of maghemite.

1.5.3 Properties of iron oxide nanoparticles

Iron oxide nanoparticles have unique opto/electro/magnetic properties due to the effects of finite size, interface, and quantum size. Iron oxide nanoparticles are important materials for many industrial applications. The natural and synthetic materials are used as pigments in the construction and film-coating industries. These pigments are used for coloring bricks and paving stones, and paints. The natural red iron oxide nanoparticles are used in primers for car and steel constructions to reduce corrosion.

Iron oxide nanoparticles in the form of magnetic nanocrystal arrays are used for data storage. Other applications include biomedical, optoelectronics, smart imaging, microspheres (biodegradable), drug/gene delivery systems, and hyperthermic cancer treatment [55-58].

The superparamagnetic properties of iron oxide make it a potential candidate for biomedical applications [59]. Superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles are the inorganic based particles with a coating of organic/inorganic materials [60].

Superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles can be directed to a defined location by external magnetic field. This particular application suits for cell treatments [61]. Superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles can be used for controlled drug liberation, cell separation, and labeling [62]. They are also used as catalysts, sorbents, pigments, flocculants, coatings, gas sensors, ion exchangers, and for lubrication [63].

1.5.4 Applications of maghemite

Maghemite (nanosized $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) is non-toxic, biodegradable, biocompatible, and chemically stable material. Maghemites have applications in the magnetic recording industry, chemistry, biomedicine, and biotechnology [64]. Some of the applications of maghemite are [65]:

- solar cell applications to produce additional electrical charge carriers,
- for biomagnetic separation,
- as a tool for diagnostic and therapeutic applications, drug delivery, magnetic hyperthermia, in vitro diagnostics,
- biomedical applications, destruction of bacterial membranes, blood-brain barrier therapeutic interventions, and as contrasting agents,
- for magnetic hyperthermia, magnetic resonance imaging, and magnetic refrigerant.

1.6 Polymer - Magnetic Nanocomposites

Composites are made from two or more materials. A composite material is a product formed by combining two or more material having varying physical and chemical properties. When these materials are combined the property of the material will be different from the individual components.

In nanocomposites at least one of the phases has dimensions in the nano range (1-100 nm). Composites are also called tailored materials; nanocomposites offer the advantage of tuneable properties of the composite with nanosize in addition to the volume fraction of the base or matrix.

As in the case of micro composites, nanocomposite materials can be classified as the ceramic matrix (CMNC), metal matrix (MMNC), and polymer matrix (PMNC). PMNCs are also known as nanostructured materials because it improves the performance properties of the polymer by doping inorganic nanoparticles [66]. There are a quite large

number of reviews on PMNCs [67-71] and biocompatible/biodegradable polymer-based systems [72-74].

1.6.1 Controlled drug delivery systems

The conventional pharmaceutical dosage forms include capsules, pills, tablets, ointments, liquids, aerosol, and injectables. Even today these conventional drug delivery systems are used. This type of drug delivery system usually releases the drug content immediately to the body fluids. To achieve/maintain the effective therapeutic range these types of drug delivery systems is necessary to be supplied several times a day [75].

The controlled delivery of the drug in which the drug is released near to the infected cells at a constant and preset manner is the solution to maintain the required therapeutic level. The drug can be the incorporation of the drug content to the polymer membrane and its diffusion into the tissues. These ideal drug delivery system should be inert, biocompatible, mechanically strong, capable of achieving high drug loading, safe from accidental release, simple to apply and remove, easy to fabricate and sterilize, and comfortable for the patient [76]. A controlled release drug delivery system should necessarily consist of a barrier, which is generally a polymer. Naturally occurring polymers that are used in controlled release formulation may be obtained from plant extrudates (gum acacia, gum tragacanth, etc.), seed or root (tamarind root, locust bean gum, orka gum), seaweed extract (chitin/chitosan, algin, carrageenan) and miscellaneous like pectin, gelatin, and starch.

Natural polymers have some disadvantages. They are having limited mechanical strength, inconsistency, and poor cell adhesion. To overcome these disadvantages semi-synthetic or synthetic polymers are employed. Some of the semi-synthetic polymers are cellulose-based (methylcellulose, carboxymethylcellulose, hydroxypropyl cellulose, hydroxypropylmethylcellulose, hydroxyethylcellulose), starch-based (dextrin, carboxymethyl starch, starch amylopectin, hydroxyethyl starch, hydroxypropyl starch) and miscellaneous like poly (propylene glycol), pectin, carboxy locust bean gum, carboxymethyl guar hydrogel, etc. Synthetic polymers that are generally employed in controlled formulations are vinyl polymers (PVP, PVA, carboxy vinyl copolymers), acrylic polymers (polyacrylic acid, polyacrylamide) and ethylene oxide polymers (polyox, various polaxamer) [77-89].

1.6.2 Polymer-magnetic nanocomposites for drug delivery

Polymer - magnetite nanocomposites can serve as a controlled drug delivery system even with the possibility of controlling the drug delivery with an external magnetic field. This approach enables the long-term drug delivery process and supports tissue regeneration [90, 91]. The development of polymer nanocomposites using polysaccharide materials has become increasingly important over the recent decade. Polysaccharides are considered as the green alternative for the synthetic polymers in the preparation of soft and lightweight nanomaterials. The main advantages of the polysaccharide-based polymer nanocomposites are simple to use, easily recyclable, inexpensive, non-toxic, and eco- friendly. Many attractive properties of biopolymers such as biodegradability, biocompatibility, non-corrosiveness, lightweight, and flexibility can be utilized along with electric and magnetic properties of nanoparticles to make multifunctional material [92]. Several types of polymer nanocomposites have been obtained by the incorporation of various nanophase materials such as metal oxides nanoparticles and carbon-based nanofillers on the biopolymer matrix [93-95]. It's properties mainly depend upon the type of the filler, matrix, and interface between filler and polymer chains [96]. Other factors such as size, shape, orientation, and dispersion of the nanofiller also affect the properties of the composites [96].

Due to the high surface to volume ratio of the nanostructures, nanocomposites present many interfaces between the constituent intermixed phases [97]. Special properties of nanocomposite materials often arise from the particle size effect of its nanoparticles. An excellent example of this phenomenon is the superparamagnetic behavior of the magnetic nanoparticles filled polymer composites [97, 98].

1.7 Literature Survey

Our research group has done extensive research work in the field of water-soluble natural, synthetic, and semi-synthetic biocompatible polymers for their applications in biomedicine and drug release applications [99-115].

Tiwari Alka and Sharma Neeraj investigated the efficiency of iron oxide loaded poly (acrylamide-co-acrylic acid) hydrogel as an adsorbent for the removal of lead ions from water. The superparamagnetic hydrogel is found to be a very effective. [116].

J. SudhaVani et al. did work on the synthesis of NaCMC/Polyacrylamide magnetic nanocomposites semi- inter penetrating networks and characterized. The

resulting magnetic nanocomposite effectively removed copper and nickel ions from solution [117].

Tayyab Ali and A. Venkataraman worked on PVA coated functionalized γ -Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles and showed the superparamagnetic behavior of the composite and improved thermal stability of the polymer [118].

H. Mittal et al. reported the removal of malachite green from water using XG - Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles filled hydrogel [119]. H. Mittal and Shivani B. Mishra reported the magnetic iron oxide reinforced poly (acrylic acid-co-acrylamide) which is cross linked with gum ghatti [120]. Dingqi and Rajandrea showed that viscoelastic gels of GG and XG mixtures provide long term stabilization of iron micro and nanoparticles [121].

Zhanhu Guo et al. studied the effects of iron oxide NPs on PVA interfacial layer and bulk nanocomposite thin films. They concluded that the addition of nanoparticles supported the cross-linking of PVA, and an increase in the lower temperature melting point. The resulting nanocomposite showed better thermal stability [122]. The necessity of analysing the mineral composition of aquifer soil and the transport mechanism of iron particles were reported by Erica Pensini et al. [123].

S. Kayal and R.V. Ramanujan analysed the drug loading and release profile of conjugated doxorubicin with various PVA coated iron oxide nanoparticle. They prepared iron oxide nanoparticles by coprecipitation method and was coated with different weight % of PVA [124].

P. Mendoza Zelis et al. studied the properties of iron-oxide nanoparticles/PVA ferrogels for their potential biomedical applications [125]. Nhiem Tran et al. investigated the effect of iron oxide nanoparticles on bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*. They showed that iron oxide/PVA nanoparticles inhibited *S. aureus* growth at the highest concentration at all-time points [126]. Alexis Patanarut et al. worked on dye incorporated acrylamide-based iron oxide nanoparticle composites, for biomarking and biomedical separation [127]. Xing-ping Qiu and Françoise Winnik prepared PVA coated magnetic nanoparticles and the magnetometric measurements revealed the superparamagnetic property of the composite [128].

Several researchers worked on polymer-coated magnetic nanoparticles and proved their stability against oxidation [129, 130]. The polymeric shell of cellulose acetate hydrogen phthalate with colloidal nanoparticles was investigated [131]. Starch, dextran, and chitosan were used to stabilize the MNPs towards their aggregation due to strong magnetic dipole-dipole attractions [132]. In vivo drug release of antibodies, proteins, or

ligands modified drugs were studied with chitosan-coated Fe_2O_3 MNPs [133] and for targeting photodynamic therapy [134]. Dextran and covalent conjugates of urokinase were tested for targeted thrombolysis [135] and as an implant to improve magnetic drug carrier capture capacity in capillary tissues [136]. Magnetic hyperthermia and chemotherapeutic drug release by iron oxide–poly-(N-isopropyl acrylamide) (PNIPAM) composite were reported [137, 138]. Hoare et al. synthesised PNIPAM-based nanogels & magnetite nanoparticles [139] having temperature-dependent swelling and drug release properties. Co-precipitation method to prepare iron oxide nanoparticles and their applications in drug release were done by many researchers [140, 141]. Liu and co-workers investigated on magnetic nanoparticles using temperature-responsive polymers [142]. Poly (vinyl alcohol) [143] and poly (ethylene glycol) [144] were used as the coating material for magnetic nanoparticles and tested for their toxicity. Alginates [145], Arabic gum [146], and gelatin [147] coated MNPs showed their applications in drug release.

Arias and colleagues prepared a diclofenac-Na loaded magnetic iron oxide – ethylcellulose composite shell for parenteral administration [148]. Zhou et al. developed MNPs and hybrid nanoparticles coated with poly ((2-dimethylamino) ethyl methacrylate) for controllable drug release studies [149]. Polylactide acid and poly(1-lactide acid-co-glycolide) with Fe_3O_4 MNPs were studied for drug loading efficiencies [150]. Mono-dispersed Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles were prepared by the reaction of ferric acetylacetonate and an organic alcohol [151], and with ether as solvent [152]. Further their efficiencies were analysed by mixing with oleic acid in hexane solution in a porous silicon matrix [153].

Polymer nanocomposites (PNC's) with the superparamagnetic property have been developed for various practical applications ranging from material science to biomedical applications. There are different types of polymer matrix both bio and synthetic polymers have been used for the preparation of superparamagnetic polymer nanocomposites. Poly (methyl methacrylate) [154], alginate [155], and poly (methyl methacrylate)/polypyrrole bilayers containing iron oxide nanoparticles are used for the preparation of superparamagnetic polymer nanocomposites.

The superparamagnetic PNC's of waterborne polyurethane containing iron oxide nanoparticles prepared by the in situ polymerization process have been reported for microwave absorption applications. The electrical conductivity and microwave absorption properties have been enhanced with an increase of iron oxide concentration [156]. The epoxy matrix containing oleic acid-coated iron oxide nanoparticles is developed for magnetic hyperthermia and shape memory applications [157]. Recently, the PNC's of

chitosan containing superparamagnetic iron oxide have been reported for biosensor [158], MRI contrast agents [159], and magnetic hyperthermia applications [160].

1.8 Scope of the Present Work

The use of newer biocompatible materials will replace the old and conventional materials in biomedicine. Synthesizing newer material or modifying the existing material is essential to meet the increasing demands. Many conventional drug release devices fail to meet the requirements for specific applications. A single material cannot be used for all the drugs for its controlled release. Even the drug content requirement varies from case-to-case. Hence the research on blending the existing biomaterials and nanomaterials may lead to the development of systems for specific applications.

This research work will lead to the preparation of novel biocompatible polymer blends, and biocompatible polymer blend – nanocomposites for their applications in biomedical engineering, especially in transdermal drug release applications. The results of this research work can be continued for targeted or sustained drug release applications for various drugs. The composites prepared would be blended with other biocompatible polymers (immiscible blends) and find application as a magnetic field controlled targeted drug release.

1.9 Objectives

Many researchers studied the polymer – magnetic nanocomposites for their potential applications in biomedicine. They have used magnetic nanoparticles as the drug carrier coated with biocompatible polymers. This work is aimed at preparing or incorporating magnetic nanoparticles in the biocompatible polymer medium to prepare novel polymer blend – magnetic nanocomposites for biomedical engineering applications.

The main objective of this proposed research work is to study the miscibility of the water-soluble biocompatible polymer of natural, semi-synthetic, and synthetic origin, the effect of maghemite magnetic nanoparticles in biocompatible polymer medium (i.e., biocompatible polymer – magnetic nanocomposites) on miscibility and to characterize them for their applications in transdermal drug release applications.

The magnetic nanoparticle used is maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) and the water-soluble polymers are xanthan gum (XG), guar gum (GG), methyl cellulose (MC), hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose (HPMC), and poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA).

Chapter 1

Section B

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The water soluble polymers used for this research work are natural polymers - GG (guar gum), XG (xanthan gum), modified natural polymers - MC (methylcellulose), HPMC (hydroxypropyl methylcellulose), and a synthetic polymer - PVA (poly (vinyl alcohol)). The compatibilizing agent used is maghemite magnetic nanoparticle. Various methods used are refractive index measurements, density measurements, ultrasonic velocity measurements, and dilute solution viscometry in aqueous solution. UV-Vis spectroscopy was used to analyse the drug release kinetics. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Fourier Transform Infra-Red Spectroscopy (FTIR), Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), and Universal Testing Machine (UTM) were used to characterize the samples in solid state (thin films). The chemistry and properties of the polymers and the theory and principle of various instruments are discussed in detail. All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. Distilled water was used throughout this work.

1.10 Guar Gum (GG)

1.10.1 Chemistry of guar gum

Guar gum extracted from the endosperm of *Cyamopsis tetragonoloba* is a naturally occurring polysaccharide. Guar bean (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*) is a commercially important crop of India. It used in the industrial production of the galactomannan gum (Guar Gum). Chemically, guar gum is a straight-chain polymer consisting of galactose and mannose in a ratio $\approx 1:2$ [161]. The schematic representation of molecular formula of guar gum is given in Figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2: Schematic representation of GG

1.10.2 Properties and applications of GG

The distribution ratio of mannose back bone and galactose is not uniform. It occurs in blocks with galactose rich and deficient regions [161-163]. The growing season influences the ratio of galactose to mannose.

GG will attain very high viscosity even at low concentrations. This is due to its ability to hydrate even in cold water. It is used as an emulsifier and stabilizer in food materials with cost-effectiveness and also its improves the texture and mouthfeel by controlling crystal formation. Some of the properties of GG are listed below:

- Solubility in cold/warm water and insolubility with organic solvents.
- Ability to form strong H-bonding with polar solvents.
- Excellent film forming property.
- Thickening, emulsifying, and stabilizing effect
- Ability to control rheology.

GG shows drug release retarding property and is susceptible for microbial degradation in the large intestine, hence it can be a vehicle for controlled drug release formulations and also for colon targeting [162-164].

GG is a water soluble fibre. Hence in food and pharmaceutical industry uses GG to relieve constipation, to promote regular bowel movements, and other bowel ailment functions. It also increases the movement of toxins, waste, and bacteria from the bowel and colon. It can also absorb toxic substances. The high fibre content of GG makes its use as an ingestion to reduce human serum cholesterol level [164]. It is also used in diabetic and weight loss diets and is thermogenic [165].

1.11 Xanthan Gum (XG)

1.11.1 Chemistry of xanthan gum

Xanthan gum is a kind of bio-polysaccharide. It is composed of glucose, mannose, glucuronic acid, acetic acid, and pyruvic acid. The main chain of Xanthan is built up of D-glucose units linked through the β -1 position of one unit with the 4th position of the next unit. The linear backbone is identical to the chemical structure of cellulose. It is prepared commercially by aerobic submerged fermentation from *Xanthomonas campestris* [166].

Figure 1.3: Schematic representation of XG

1.11.2 Properties and applications of xanthan gum

It is soluble in both hot and cold water. It gives hazy and neutral pH solutions. 1% XG solutions are usually in the 1500 to 2500 cps viscosity range. They are pseudoplastic and shear-thinning. At elevated temperature XG show stable viscosity properties with the presence of small amounts of salt and possess excellent yield value. It is tolerant to electrolytes, acids, and bases compared to other organic gums. It can be gelled or precipitated with certain polyvalent metal cations. XG solutions show viscosity stability over the pH 2 to 12. It is tolerant to water-miscible solvents.

XG is compatible with most nonionic and anionic gums. It is resistant to shear, heat, bacterial, enzyme and UV degradation. XG is biodegradable and biocompatible. It forms a gel in water. Hence, XG is mainly used for biomedical applications [167-170].

XG need to be properly hydrated prior to its application to obtain optimum functionality. The particle size, agitation rate of the solvent, composition of the solvent, and dispersion of XG decides the rate of hydration. XG is a polyelectrolyte and the ionic strength of its side chains and the free ions in the solvent decides its molecular structure [168]. In the absence of added ions (salts), the viscosity of XG solution will be affected. When salt is added, the side chain collapses down to the backbone structure and gives a rod-like structure to the molecule. At moderate temperatures XG exhibits ordered conformation but on increasing the temperature the viscosity increases rapidly. A xanthan solution in the presence of salts like NaCl or KCl can maintain its ordered structure and viscosity stability up to 100°C [168-170].

Though food and beverages are the main application fields of xanthan gum it has been widely used in many other applications such as agricultural products, ceramic industry, as a cleansers, coating, polisher, oil-drilling aids and fluids, paper industry, personal care, pharmaceutical, and textile applications [167-170].

1.12 Methyl Cellulose (MC)

1.12.1 Chemistry of methylcellulose

Methylcellulose (MC) is the simplest cellulose derivative, where C-2, C-3 and/or C-6 positions of anhydro-D-glucose units, the hydroxyl groups are substituted with methyl groups (-CH₃).

Figure 1.4: Schematic representation of MC.

1.12.2 Properties and applications of MC

Methylcellulose is a type of cellulose ether with many industrial applications. MC is having amphiphilic property and its solubility in water or organic solvents depends on the degree of substitution. Its viscosity is slightly dependent on the temperature. It shows constant viscosity at room temperatures and continues to increase with temperature till it becomes thermoreversible gel. The viscosities are stable over a large range of pH (3–11) but degraded slowly in strong acids or bases. These characteristics classify methylcellulose as a lower critical solution temperature polymer (LCST). For the faster dissolution of MC it has to be dispersed in water with a temperature of about 70°C and then cool down. This method provides faster dissolution of the particles resulting in a homogeneous solution.

Methylcellulose is a white powder or sometimes as coarse particles in pure form. In general, methylcellulose is a non-ionic polymer able to be mixed with other polymers, salt, and different ingredients. Methylcellulose is non-toxic, enzyme resistant, not digestible in the body, and are non-allergic. MC is a binder for many types of systems including pigments, cellulosic fibers, pharmaceutical products, ceramics, and others. Methylcellulose form antioxidant properties and act as excellent barriers against UV and visible radiations along with other additives [171-173].

All those properties make methylcellulose applicable for many life areas like food, ceramics, personal care, pharmaceuticals, biomedical, construction, adhesives, agriculture, and many other applications [174-176].

1.13 Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC)

1.13.1 Chemistry of hydroxypropyl methylcellulose

Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) is a polysaccharide prepared by swelling cellulose with NaOH and then reacting with methyl chloride and propylene oxide. Chemically, it is a cellulose-ether in which hydroxypropyl groups have been substituted by one or more of the three hydroxyl groups present in each anhydro-glucose ring of cellulose [177]. A typical basic structure of HPMC is given in Figure 1.5.

Figure 1.5: Schematic representation of HPMC

1.13.2 Properties and applications of hydroxypropyl methylcellulose

A wide range of properties are possible by controlling the amount and type of the solution. It is soluble in cold water and gives clear, colorless, and surface-active solutions with neutral pH. Alkali soluble to organic soluble varieties can be achieved by altering the hydroxypropyl content. A two substituted groups per anhydrous-glucose ring are usually alkali soluble and three hydroxypropyl substituted HPMC are organic soluble. HPMC are available in grades from very low - extremely high viscosity. The solutions are pseudoplastic. Depending upon the grade, they show the characteristic gelation temperatures between 50°C and 85°C. These gels are reversible and return to fluidity on cooling. Below the gelation temperature, solutions show a decrease in viscosity as temperature increases [177].

HPMC shows good viscosity stability between pH 3 to 11. It is tolerant to water-miscible solvents. Some grades are soluble in specific polar organic liquids. It is more resistant to bacterial and enzymatic degradation than most cellulose derivatives.

HPMC is having extremely low toxicity. It forms non-ionic solutions and are used as surfactant, as adhesives, and possesses thermal gelling characteristics. HPMC thin films can be cast from organic solvent system which are heat-sealable, resistant to greases and oils, and are water soluble. The amount and nature of plasticizers influence the flexibility of HPMC thin-films. The plasticizers used for HPMC includes sorbitol, glycerol, ethylene glycol, propylene glycol, triethanolamine, diethylene glycol, polypropylene glycol and hydroxypropyl sucrose [177-179].

1.14 Poly (Vinyl Alcohol) (PVA)

1.14.1 Chemistry of poly (vinyl alcohol)

Chemically, PVA can be classified broadly as a polyhydric alcohol with secondary hydroxyl groups on alternate carbon atoms. Poly (vinyl alcohol) was first prepared by Hermann and Haehnel in 1924 by hydrolyzing polyvinyl acetate in ethanol with potassium hydroxide.

PVA is prepared using the monomer vinyl acetate. The monomer is polymerized with partial hydrolysis to obtain PVA. The hydrolysis is based on the partial replacement of the ester group in vinyl acetate with the hydroxyl group. The process is completed in the presence of aqueous sodium hydroxide and by the gradual addition of the aqueous saponification agent (which decides the degree of hydrolysis) [180]. The schematic representation of PVA is given in Figure 1.6.

Figure 1.6: Schematic representation of PVA

1.14.2 Properties and applications of poly (vinyl alcohol)

PVA is an odorless and tasteless, translucent, white or cream-colored granular powder, which is soluble in water. PVA is slightly soluble in ethanol and insoluble in other organic solvents. Typically a 5% solution of PVA exhibits a pH in the range of 5.0 to 6.5. It has a melting point of 180 to 190°C [206]. It has a molecular weight between 26,300 and 30,000, and a degree of hydrolysis of 86.5 to 89%.

PVA is classified into two classes namely partially hydrolyzed and fully hydrolyzed [206]. Partially hydrolyzed PVA is used in the foods. It is used as a moisture barrier for food supplement tablets, and for dry food. The unique product properties of PVA make it one of the most multipurpose water-soluble resins. Among the valuable properties are water solubility, grease, oil, and solvent resistance, ease of forming thin films, high tensile strength, adhesive and binder properties [181, 182].

The film and coating formation with PVA occur readily by solution evaporation from the solution. The mechanical properties of PVA is high compared with plastics. The

addition of plasticizers reduces the tensile strength but improves the elasticity. PVA is resistant to oils, grease, and petroleum hydrocarbons. Partially hydrolyzed grades are considerably resistant to most of the organic solvents. It is impermeable to many gases.

Industries such as paper sizing, adhesives, textile, etc. extensively use PVA. They are used as adhesives in boxboard, wallboard, paper bags, and as binder for textile fabric, cork, plaster, etc. PVA is used as emulsifier for vegetable and mineral oils. It is also used as a solvent, plasticizer, and resin [183, 184].

1.15 Refractive Index Measurements

Refractive index (RI) is the measure of the fastness of light through a given medium. For example in water light travels 1.333 time as fast in vacuum as in water. Refractive index values are dimensionless number. A higher refractive index value indicates that the speed of light travelling in that medium is lower. RI is defines as: $RI = c/v$, where c is the speed, and v is the velocity of light in the medium.

An Abbe's refractometer is an high precision refractometer to measure refractive index values. Its working principle is based on critical angle. At critical angle the light get refracted in such a way that it becomes parallel to the phase boundary surface. For smaller incident angles the light rays passes through the boundary and for large incident angles the get reflected back.

Figure 1.7: Abbe's refractometer

A typical Abbe's refractometer is represented in Figure 1.7. In the Abbe' refractometer the sample is placed as a thin layer between an illuminating prism (A) and a refracting prism (B). A monochromatic light is projected through the illuminating prism. The refracting prism is roughened such that each point on that surface can reflect light in all directions. The refracted light produces light regions and dark regions depending on the sample. The border line of these dark-light regions are dependent on the sample and hence its refractive index. The position of the border line is used to determine the refractive index of samples.

By circulating thermostat water the water jacket (J) the measuring temperatures are maintained. A thermostat is used to get a thermal stability of $\pm 0.05^{\circ}\text{C}$. The refractometer was calibrated with double distilled water before measuring the RI of the blend/blend-composite solutions. The refractive index of water was taken from the literature [185]. The source of light used was a sodium vapor lamp of λ value 5893°A . The solvent and followed by acetone was was done to the prisms before measuring the RI values. An accuracy of $\pm 0.02\%$ was maintained throughout the experiment.

1.16 Ultrasonic Velocity Measurements

Interferometric technique [186], and ultrasonic interferometer (M/S Mittal enterprises, New Delhi) was used to measure the ultrasonic velocity values of the polymer, polymer blend, and blend-composite solutions. Figure 1.8 represents the ultrasonic interferometer (A) and the experimental cell (B). A 2 MHz ultrasonic waves are generated by the quartz crystal travel through the medium (sample) gets reflected by the movable plate. If the separation between quartz plate and the movable metallic plate is exactly equal to the multiples of λ , standing waves are formed. These standing waves produce an electrical reaction on the generator. Thus the anode current becomes maximum, which was indicated by the maximum deflection of the measuring needle.

When the distance between the plates is increased or decreased the variation is exactly $\lambda/2$ or multiples of it, the anode current and hence the measuring needle shows deflection maximum. Thus the to-and-fro movement of the measuring needle represents the distance or $\lambda/2$.

$$d = n \times \lambda/2 \quad (1.1)$$

where d is the distance of moving plate moved between consecutive maximum deflection, and n is the number of maximum deflection. If $n = 1$, then $d = \lambda/2$; or $\lambda = 2d$.

The velocity can be obtained from the following relation

$$v = \lambda \times f \quad (1.2)$$

Thermostated water with a thermal stability of $\pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$ was circulated through the water jacket. $\pm 0.3\%$ accuracy was maintained during the experiment. The cell was rinsed with distilled water and with test solution before each measurement.

Figure 1.8: Schematic of (A) ultrasonic interferometer instrument and (B) experimental cell

1.17 Dilute Solution Viscometry

Viscosity is the resistance offered by the molecules to flow. Various factors like intermolecular interactions, temperature, etc. affect the viscosity of a solution. Less viscous liquids will show less resistance to flow and more viscous liquids have high resistance to flow. For experimental purpose to measure the viscosity of solution Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer (USLV) are used. A schematic representation of USLV is given in Figure 1.9. USLV is a glass apparatus with three glass tubes fused. The one wider glass tube is to add the liquid sample to the glass bulb at the bottom, one tube with capillary is to suck the solution above the flow measurement region, and the third

tube is to avoid the pressure generated inside the tube. Hence the advantage of using USLV with normal viscometer is that it is volume independent. During this research work constant temperatures were maintained by holding the viscometer in a thermostat water bath with $\pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$ accuracy.

Figure 1.9: Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer (USLV)

In the present study the flow time is measured using a stop watch with an accuracy of 0.1 seconds. For each concentration/composition the average of three time-of-flows were recorded. The determination of relative viscosity, specific viscosity, and reduced viscosity are given below:

$$\text{Relative viscosity } \eta_r = \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = \frac{t_1}{t_0} \quad (1.3)$$

$$\text{Specific viscosity } \eta_{sp} = \frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0} = \eta_r - 1 \quad (1.4)$$

$$\text{Reduced viscosity } \frac{\eta_{sp}}{C} = \frac{\eta_r - 1}{C} \quad (1.5)$$

Where C is the concentration of the solution, t_0 is the time-of-flow for the reference solution (distilled water in the present study), t_1 is the time-of-flow of the sample solution, η is the viscosity of sample, and η_0 is the viscosity of reference.

The plot of reduced viscosity against concentration is called Huggins's plot, which is used to assess the miscibility of polymer blends and compatibility of polymer blend – nanocomposite solutions.

1.18 Density Measurements

Density or volumetric mass density is the mass per unit volume of solution. The mutual attraction/repulsion of the molecules, temperature, miscibility of liquids, etc. decides the density of the solution. Density of polymer solutions, blend solutions, and blend – nanocomposite solutions were measured by using specific gravity bottle [187]. $\pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$ accuracy temperatures were maintained using thermostat water bath. The following equation was used to measure the density of test solution,

$$\text{Density} = \frac{\text{Weight of solution}}{\text{Weight of water}} \times \text{Density of water} \quad (1.6)$$

Weight of solution and weight of water were measured using electronic balance capable of measuring up to 0.0001 g. The accuracy in the measurement is better than $\pm 0.01\%$.

1.19 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

The active functional groups, as well as the nature of bonding between the molecules will absorb the energy of infrared radiation and the presence can be identified using infrared (IR) spectroscopy. Infrared lights are having longer wavelength than normal visible light. To measure the fundamental vibrations, mid-infrared light ($4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) are generally used in IR spectroscopic studies.

A fourier transform decomposes a function (such as a signal) into its constituent frequencies. With the advent of modern computers fourier transform is used in modern IR spectroscopy devices. Such devices are now called FTIR spectroscopy. A modified sampling technique ATR (Attenuated total reflectance) is used with FTIR which enables the examination of solid, liquid, or gas molecules directly or without any complicated sample preparations. The multiple reflection of IR light in the sample gives more efficient results [188]. A schematic representation is given in Figure 1.10.

Figure 1.10: Schematic representation of a multiple reflection ATR system

1.20 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

A scanning electron microscopy uses the interaction between the electrons off the electron beam and the surface atoms and the atoms at the depth of the test sample to get the surface images. Various types of signals are produced when electron interacts with atoms like secondary electrons (SE), backscattered electrons (BSE), cathodoluminescence (CL), absorbed current, and transmitted electrons [189, 190]. Secondary electrons and backscattered electrons signals gave the information about the test samples surface morphology. Non-conducting test sample surfaces are made conducting by the coating of conducting metals. The working of a scanning electron microscopy is given in Figure 1.11.

Figure 1.11: Schematic representation of working of SEM

A magnification of 10 times that of a hand-lens to 250 times is possible with a normal SEM microscope. The advantage of SEM analysis is that it is a "non-destructive" method and the same test samples can be used multiple analysis [191].

1.21 Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

The difference in heat flow between the test sample and reference, as a function of temperature, is measured by DSC. During the measurement the same temperature of test sample and reference were maintained. When the sample under goes any phase transition, in order to maintain uniform temperature, heat flows to the sample from reference or heat is withdrawn from the sample by the reference [192, 193]. Figure 1.12 represents a cross section of DSC cell.

Figure 1.12: A DSC cell

The phase transition such as glass transition (T_g), melting, oxidation and decomposition are endothermic and the sample absorb heat from the reference, whereas crystallisation of the sample, cure or cross linking are exothermic and the sample releases heat to the reference. These changes of phases can be measure as a function of temperature. Figure 1.13 represents the schematics of DSC thermograms.

Figure 1.13: Schematic DSC thermogram

1.22 Thermo Gravimetric Analysis (TGA)

The thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) technique measures the change in weight of the sample with increase in temperature. TGA thermograms are the plot of mass versus time [194].

Figure 1.14: Schematic illustration of modern thermobalance

The thermal stability of materials can be measured using TGA. During the loss of moisture from the sample, depolymerisation, decomposition, etc. the sample loses weight. The weight change is measured accurately. The upper use temperature of a material can

be decided with TGA measurements. As the polymers melt before decomposition, TGA is mainly used to measure the thermal stability of polymers.

A schematic of TGA is given in Figure 1.14. TGA instrument consists of recording balance, furnace, furnace temperature programmer or controller, and recorder.

1.23 UV-Vis Spectrometer

UV-vis spectroscopy [195] can be used to measure the absorbance values of both coloured and colourless samples. When light travels through a medium (sample) a part of the light is absorbed and remaining is transmitted. By measuring the amount of light transmitted the absorbance properties can be assessed. The absorbance of samples depends on the concentration of solute in it as per Beer's law. Any test samples obeying Beer's law can be estimated by UV-vis spectroscopy. By knowing the intensity of light used (I_0) and intensity of light passing through the sample (I), the transmittance is calculated as I/I_0 and is expressed as %T. The absorbance $A = -\log(\%T / 100\%)$

A schematic representation of UV-Vis spectrometer is given in Figure 1.15. It consists of a light source, a holder for the sample, a diffraction grating in a monochromator or a prism to separate the different wavelengths of light, and a detector. The samples are taken in a sample holder (cuvette) with a path length of 1 cm, made of quartz which do not allow any light intensity to reflect.

In a single beam spectrometer the I_0 is measured by removing the sample, whereas in the modern double beam spectrometers the light is split into two beams. One beam is used as the reference; the other beam for the sample.

Figure 1.15: Schematic of a UV-visible spectrophotometer

1.24 Tensile Strength Measurements

In tensile testing the sample is subjected to a controlled tension till it fails. Ultimate tensile strength, maximum elongation, and reduction in the area were measured during tensile testing which provides information about Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, yield strength, and strain-hardening characteristics. The most common method used is uniaxial tensile testing.

Tensile measurements are done with UTM (Universal Testing Machine). The schematic representation of a UTM with uniaxial loading is given in Figure 1.16.

Figure 1.16: Schematic of a UTM

The preparation of test specimens depends on the purposes of testing and on the governing test method or specification. One of the most common specifications used for thin-film plastic sheeting is ASTM D882. Here, the sample is pulled vertically to measure elongation, tensile modulus, tensile yield strength, and tensile strength at break. For ASTM D882 standards the specimens used were of rectangular strips of films. This can avoid the use of an extensometer, as the samples are having higher elongation during the testing.

Chapter- 2

**Biocompatible Maghemite Nanocomposites of
Guar Gum, Methylcellulose and their Blends**

“For, each man can do best and excel in only that thing of which he is passionately fond, in which he believes, as I do, that he has the ability to do it, that he is in fact born and destined to do it.”

- Homi Jehangir Bhabha

Chapter 2

BIOCOMPATIBLE MAGHEMITE NANOCOMPOSITES OF GUAR GUM, METHYLCELLULOSE AND THEIR BLENDS

2.1 Introduction

The blending of polymers is one of the simplest methods to obtain desired physical and chemical properties from the constituent polymers. Based on the miscibility polymer blends are classified as miscible, semi-miscible, and immiscible [24-28]. The miscibility of polymer blends is studied using density, refractive index, ultrasonic interferometry, viscometry, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopic (FTIR) methods. The thermal and mechanical properties of blends are studied using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), differential thermal analysis (DTA), and tensile strength measurement techniques [196-197]. Most of the study's lead to their applications in specific drug release formulations. Natural biopolymer polymer usually showed better release profile for chemical drugs but they lack thermal and mechanical strength. Semi-synthetic biopolymers are the modified natural polymer.

In this chapter the blending of a natural water soluble polymer guar gum and a semi-synthetic water soluble polymer methylcellulose is discussed in detail. Guar gum (GG) and methylcellulose (MC) have been studied for their applications in the biomedical and food industry. Guar gum (GG) is extremely, hydrophilic polymer, the solution of which is highly viscous in nature. This property has allowed these polymers and their derivatives to be commercialized in fields such as textiles, foods, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals and oil recovery and drilling [196-198]. The reaction of alkali cellulose with methyl chloride or dimethyl sulfate will produce MC [199, 200]. It is used as a thickener, and as a matrix for the controlled release of drugs [200].

In the literature the miscibility studies of these two polymers are not available and these blends may find specific applications. The miscibility can be enhanced by the incorporation of suitable compatible agents. Maghemite is a biocompatible magnetic nanoparticle having potential applications in the biomedical field. In this chapter miscibility of guar gum and methylcellulose at different compositions were studied in solution state at 30°C and 40°C by density, and viscosity measurement techniques. The effect of biocompatible maghemite nanoparticles on the miscibility of GG/MC blends are

studied in the solid state by SEM and FTIR. Thermal and mechanical properties were studied by DSC, TGA, and UTM.

2.2 Experimental Procedure

The polymers employed in the present study are guar gum (GG), methylcellulose (MC), and nanoparticles of maghemite were purchased from Merck, India. Schematic representation of guar gum and methyl cellulose are shown in Figures 1.2 and 1.4 respectively.

0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, and 0.05 wt% maghemite nanocomposites were prepared separately with guar gum (0.5% w/v) and with methyl cellulose (0.5% w/v). The mixtures were stirred for 6 hours with polymer mixer and kept for ultrasonication for 4 hours for uniform mixing. The prepared samples were taken in test tubes and kept in contact with strong magnet for 30 minutes to check the stability of the solution. All the maghemite-MC composite solutions showed stability towards magnetic field, whereas the solutions of guar gum containing 0.05, 0.04, and 0.03 wt% of maghemite showed settlement of maghemite on the sides of the test tube attracted by the strong magnet. Hence the experiments were continued with 0.02 wt% of maghemite.

Blends of GG/MC of different compositions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30 and 90/10) were prepared in distilled water. The densities, refractive index, and ultrasonic sound velocity of the GG, MC, and GG/MC blend solutions (0.5%, w/v) with and without maghemite nanoparticles (0.02 wt%) were measured at 30°C and 40°C. For ultrasonic studies the F-81, Mittal Entreprises, India, was used. Adiabatic compressibility was also calculated for the above compositions. Different temperatures were maintained using a thermostat bath with a thermal stability of $\pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$.

Stock solutions of GG, GG – maghemite composite, MC, and MC – maghemite composite were prepared (0.1% w/v). The blend stock solutions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30 and 90/10) and blend – maghemite composite stock solutions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30 and 90/10) were prepared by stirring the mixtures at room temperature for about 45 min. Using these stock solutions, different 0.01 to 0.1 w/v blend solutions were prepared, and viscosity were measured at 30°C and 40°C..

The prepared polymer/polymer blend - maghemite nanocomposites were solution casted and characterized. SEM photographs were recorded using a ZEISS Sigma FESEM 300 analyzer. FTIR spectra were recorded using NICOLET AVATAR 530 spectrophotometer.

A TA Q200 Differential Scanning Calorimeter, under N₂ environment were used for DSC measurements. In the 1st temperature cycle the sample was heated 90°C; maintained the temperature for 15 min. to remove the moisture from the samples. The sample was then cooled to 20°C and immediately reheated to 250°C with a heating/cooling rate of 10°C/min. The thermal properties (T_g determination) of GG, XG, MC, HPMC, and PVA and their corresponding miscible blend compositions with and without maghemite nanoparticles were studied. The mid-point of change of slope is taken as the T_g value [87]. The T_g of the miscible blend can be calculated using Fox Equation (2.1) [201], or Wood's Equation (2.2) [202].

$$1/T_g = (w_1/T_{g1}) + (w_2/T_{g2}) \quad (2.1)$$

$$T_g = (w_1 T_{g1}) + (w_2 T_{g2}) \quad (2.2)$$

where w_1 , w_2 , $T_{g,1}$, and $T_{g,2}$ are the weight fractions, and T_g of polymer 1 and polymer 2, respectively.

Thermogravimetric analysis of the blend films was performed over the temperature range of 20 – 500°C, using Thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA Q50 V20.2 Build 27) under N₂ environment at a scan rate of 10°C/min. The TGA analysis of homopolymers, polymer nanocomposites, blends, and blend - nanocomposites of GG/MC, GG/HPMC, XG/MC, and XG/PVA were performed. The temperatures such as T₀, T₂₀, T₄₀, T₅₀, T₆₀, and T_{max} corresponding to onset of decomposition, and mass loss of 20%, 40%, 50%, 60%, and maximum weight loss were observed. These are the main criteria to explain the thermal stability [99].

Mechanical properties [83, 86, 99, 182, 183, 203-205] of thin films were measured under tensile strain. 5 samples of 10 x 150 mm dimensions for each composition were tested. A micrometer of sensitivity of 1µm was used to measure the thickness of the samples and are found to be between 0.08 – 0.1 mm. Tensile strength at yield, modulus, and % elongation at break were measured with an LLYODS UK model analyzer (LR 100K). An ASTM standard D882 was used for testing the samples. The test was run at 100 mm/minute and at room temperature.

2.3 Results and Discussions

2.3.1 Refractive index measurements

The refractive index (RI) values of pure polymers and their blends were measured. The RI value for MC is 1.3420 and 1.3410, and for GG is 1.3402 and 1.3385 at 30°C and

40°C, respectively. A slight linearity is observed for 10/90 GG/MC blend compared with RI values of pure GG and MC both at 30°C and 40°C (Figure 2.1).

With the addition of 0.02 wt% maghemite showed RI value about 1.46 for pure GG, MC and their blend compositions at 30°C and about 1.44 at 40°C. The RI measurement technique is not suitable to assess the miscibility of maghemite nanocomposites as the colour developed are almost the same.

Figure 2.1: Variation of RI of GG/MC blends

2.3.2 Density measurements

The density value of guar gum (GG) is $0.9972 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $0.99376 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and for methyl cellulose (MC) is $0.9985 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $0.99525 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, at 30°C and 40°C respectively. The density values of the blend compositions are in between that of GG and MC. The density values are higher for methyl cellulose compared to guar gum. The graph shows only non-linear regions indicating the immiscible nature of the GG/MC blend at both 30°C and 40°C (Figure 2.2A). Linearity is observed for miscible and non-linearity for immiscible blends [99-108].

Figure 2.2: Variation of density with composition of A) GG/MC blends, and B) GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposites

The density values for maghemite nanocomposites are higher compared with polymers without maghemite. Density values for 0.02 wt% maghemite-GG nanocomposites is 1.007×10^3 Kg/m³, and 0.9985×10^3 Kg/m³, and for 0.02 wt% maghemite-MC nanocomposites is 1.031×10^3 Kg/m³, and 1.012×10^3 Kg/m³, at 30°C and 40°C respectively (Figure 2.2B). Only 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite composite showed linearity compared with the maghemite nanocomposites of GG and MC, other

compositions got deviated from linearity. The non-linear regions indicate that the presence of maghemite does not improve the miscibility nature of GG/MC blends.

2.3.3 Ultrasonic velocity measurements

The ultrasonic velocity value for methyl cellulose is 1525 m/s and 1545 m/s, and for GG is 1479 m/s and 1519 m/s, at 30°C and 40°C, respectively. The ultrasonic sound velocity values for the entire blend compositions (Figure 2.3A) are found to be in between that of pure GG and MC, but the graph shows non-linear regions. This indicates that GG/MC blend is immiscible at all compositions [99-108].

The incorporation of maghemite nanoparticles decreased the ultrasonic velocity values of GG, MC, and GG/MC blends. It is found to be 1510 m/s, and 1524 m/s for MC-maghemite nanocomposite, and 1464 m/s, and 1488 m/s for GG-maghemite nanocomposites respectively at 30°C and 40°C. The observation with ultrasonic velocity measurement studies is similar to that of density and refractive index studies. The presence of maghemite might have influenced the miscibility of GG/MC blend for the 10/90 blend composition.

A

B

Figure 2.3: Variation of ultrasonic velocity with composition of A) GG/MC blends, and B) GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposites

2.3.4 Adiabatic compressibility measurements

The adiabatic compressibility (β_{ad}) were calculated for GG, MC, and GG/MC blends, and GG - maghemite nanocomposite, MC - maghemite nanocomposite, and GG/MC - maghemite nanocomposites of varying compositions and plotted a graph of β_{ad} against percentage composition of GG. The values found to be $4.30638 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, and $4.20931 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$ for methylcellulose and $4.62181 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, and $4.42503 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$ for guar gum, at 30°C and 40°C, respectively (Figure 2.4A). The plots are non-linear indicating immiscible nature of GG/MC blends [99-108].

Figure 2.4: Variation of adiabatic compressibility with composition of A) GG/MC blends, and B) GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposites

The calculated β_{ad} values of MC-maghemite nanocomposites and GG-maghemite nanocomposites are $4.39236 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, and $4.32611 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, and $4.67881 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, and $4.54478 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, at 30°C and 40°C respectively (Figure 2.4B). The variation of adiabatic compressibility with % composition of GG of blend - maghemite

nanocomposites shows linear region only up to 10/90 blend composition. The remaining compositions showed non-linear regions.

2.3.5 Reduced viscosity measurements

Reduced viscosities of GG, MC and their blend compositions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30 and 90/10) were measured at 30°C and 40°C. Huggin's plots of reduced viscosities of the pure polymers and their blend compositions against concentrations are shown in Figures 2.5 (A and B). Reduced viscosities of GG - maghemite nanocomposite, MC - maghemite nanocomposite, and the blend - maghemite nanocomposite compositions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30 and 90/10) were measured at 30°C and 40°C. Huggin's plots of reduced viscosities against concentrations are shown in Figures 2.5 (C and D).

B

C

D

Figure 2.5: Huggins's plot for A) GG/MC blend at 30°C, B) GG/MC blends at 40°C, C) GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposites at 30°C, and D) GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposites at 40°C

Reduced viscosities of GG, MC and their blend compositions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30 and 90/10) were measured at 30°C and 40°C. Huggin's plots are shown in Figures 2.5A, and 2.5B, respectively. Reduced viscosities of GG-maghemite composite, MC - maghemite nanocomposite, and the blend - maghemite nanocomposite compositions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30 and 90/10) were measured at 30°C and 40°C. Huggin's plots are shown in Figures 2.5C, and 2.5D, respectively.

Higher slope variations (Table 2.1) for 10/90 GG/MC blend compositions with maghemite nanoparticles may be due to the mutual attraction of macromolecules which increases the hydrodynamic volume [99-108]. The 90/10, 70/30, 50/50, and 30/70 GG/MC blend compositions showed lower slope, which may be due to the phase separation of polymers. According to reduced viscosity-concentration criteria, this polymer blend is miscible for 10/90 compositions and immiscible for 90/10, 70/30, 50/50, and 30/70 blend compositions in the presence of 0.02 wt% maghemite.

Table 2.1: Slope values from Huggins plots

Composition	Blends of GG/MC		Blend – composites of GG/MC	
	30°C	40°C	30°C	40°C
0/100	217.884	152.496	139.618	131.478
10/90	154.090	140.490	163.739	179.218
30/70	150.630	117.715	140.115	126.351
50/50	158.218	117.612	136.030	124.842
70/30	166.218	132.654	142.630	128.915
90/10	172.006	123.327	139.236	128.266
100/0	170.260	154.666	142.721	124.333

2.3.6 Morphological studies

Figure 2.6: SEM images of a) GG, b) GG - maghemite nanocomposite, c) MC, d) MC - maghemite nanocomposite, and e) 10/90 GG/MC blend - maghemite nanocomposite

Morphology studies were carried out to identify the interaction between maghemite and the polymers and the influence of maghemite on the miscibility of GG/MC blend. SEM images recorded for GG, MC, and maghemite incorporated GG, MC, and 10/90 GG/MC blend (Figure 2.6).

The SEM images confirms that guar gum form weak interaction with maghemite, where as the maghemite is well dispersed in methyl cellulose. The 10/90 GG/MC blend with maghemite does not show any phase separation. The presence of maghemite might have stabilized the structure of guar gum to form miscible blend with MC at 10/90 blend composition.

2.3.7 FTIR spectroscopic measurements

FTIR spectra of GG, GG – maghemite nanocomposite, MC, MC – maghemite nanocomposite, and 10/90 GG/MC blend - maghemite nanocomposite were recorded in the wave length range of $4000\text{-}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Figure 2.7).

Figure 2.7: FTIR spectra of a) GG, b) MC, c) GG - maghemite nanocomposite, d) MC - maghemite nanocomposite, and e) 10/90 GG/MC blend - maghemite nanocomposite

Guar gum showed (Figure 2.7a) the characteristic peaks. 3347.3 cm^{-1} for $-\text{OH}$ bond stretching, 2918.2 cm^{-1} of $-\text{CH}$ group stretching, 1638.3 cm^{-1} for $-\text{OH}$ bond, 1370.9 cm^{-1} for $-\text{CH}_2$ group bending, 1012.7 cm^{-1} for $-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-$ bending [206].

The FTIR spectra of MC (Figure 2.7b) showed a $-\text{OH}$ stretching at 3350.3 cm^{-1} , 1593.7 cm^{-1} for $-\text{OH}$ bond, C-H stretching at 2916.7 cm^{-1} , a $-\text{CH}_2$ scissoring at 1412 cm^{-1} , and $-\text{O}-$ stretching at 1026 cm^{-1} [207, 208].

FTIR spectroscopy of 10/90 GG/MC blend - maghemite nanocomposite (Figure 2.7c) indicates that the major peaks are associated with alcohol (ν_{OH}) strong stretching band observed at 3310 cm^{-1} . Alkyl stretching, carbonyl group stretching, and $-\text{CH}$ bending, $-\text{C}-\text{O}$ stretch are observed at 2941 cm^{-1} , 1735 cm^{-1} , 1245 cm^{-1} , 1088 cm^{-1} , respectively. The peak at 537 cm^{-1} corresponds to vibration of Fe-O, and the other peaks at pure maghemite are $454, 632\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [209-211]. The instrumental limitation did not allow these two peaks to be clearly shown. The hydroxyl characteristic bands for 10/90 GG/MC blend - maghemite nanocomposite got shifted to lower wave length compared to GG and MC, due to intermolecular H-bonding between guar gum and methylcellulose in the presence of maghemite. Hence, the FTIR spectroscopic measurement confirms that incorporation of maghemite influenced the miscibility of GG/MC blend, and 10/90 GG/MC blend is miscible in the presence of 0.02 wt% maghemite.

2.3.8 Glass transition temperature measurements

The experimental T_g value of GG, MC, GG – 0.02 wt% maghemite composite, MC – 0.02 wt% maghemite composite, and 10/90 GG/MC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites are represented in Figure 2.8 and they are found to be 56.6°C , 39.4°C , 62.4°C , 43.7°C , and 45.8°C , respectively. The T_g value of 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite is found to be composition dependent on that of nanocomposites of GG and MC confirming the compatibility of the blend.

The experimental T_g value for 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite compared with theoretical T_g value [212, 213]. The theoretical T_g values calculated using the Fox Equation, and Wood's Equation are 45.05°C , and 45.57°C , respectively. Experimental T_g value for 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite composite is found to be higher than that of theoretically calculated T_g value which indicates the intermolecular interaction between the polymers [81, 213].

Figure 2.8: DSC thermograms of a) GG, b) GG – maghemite nanocomposite, c) MC, d) MC – maghemite nanocomposite, and e) 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite

2.3.9 Thermogravimetric analysis

The samples of GG, GG – maghemite nanocomposite, MC, MC – maghemite nanocomposite, and 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite were characterized by a thermogravimetric analyzer under nitrogen environment. TG curve shows that the samples have two degradation stages - the 1st stage is the water loss and the 2nd stage for the depolymerization, cellulose ethers degradation, decomposition, steaming, and disposal of volatile compounds [214].

The temperature characteristics are calculated and shown in Table 2.9. The addition of maghemite nanoparticle improved the thermal stability of the pure polymers. It is also observed that the degradation temperature of 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposites were higher than that of GG- maghemite composite, and MC – maghemite composite. This improved thermal stability attributes to the presence of maghemite and the interaction of GG and MC in the blend.

Figure 2.9: TGA curves of a) GG, b) GG – maghemite composite, c) MC, d) MC – maghemite composite, and e) 10/90 GG/MC – maghemite composite

Table 2.2: Parameters calculated from the thermograms of GG, MC, their maghemite nanocomposites, and 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite

Composition	Temperature ($\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$)					
	T_0	T_{20}	T_{40}	T_{50}	T_{60}	T_{\max}
MC	184	199	240	256	285	305
MC – maghemite nanocomposite	203	235	264	277	301	318
10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite	231	265	290	304	320	365
GG	207	217	251	268	283	301
GG – maghemite nanocomposite	194	202	274	290	309	331

2.3.10 Tensile strength measurements

The tensile strength at yield (TS), % elongation, and tensile modulus (E) of pure GG, MC, GG – maghemite nanocomposite, MC – maghemite nanocomposite, and 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite were measured and the obtained values are given in Table 2.3. 10/90 GG/MC – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite showed composition-dependent mechanical properties with that of GG – maghemite

nanocomposite, and MC – maghemite nanocomposite. But the incorporation of maghemite nanoparticle reduced the tensile properties as it may be due to the brittleness caused by maghemite.

Table 2.3: Tensile strength at yield, % of elongation and tensile modulus of GG, MC, their maghemite nanocomposites, and 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite

Composition	Tensile Strength at Yield (MPa)	% Elongation	Tensile Modulus (MPa)
MC	38.21	10.74	978.6
MC – maghemite nanocomposite	36.5	9.54	945.8
10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite	24.6	6.78	589.3
GG	25.7	6.41	621.3
GG – maghemite nanocomposite	21.3	5.12	542.3

Chapter- 3

**Biocompatible Maghemite Nanocomposites of Guar Gum,
Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose and their Blends**

“No, it is a very interesting number, it is the smallest number expressible as a sum of two cubes in two different ways.”

- Srinivasa Ramanujan

Chapter 3

BIOCOMPATIBLE MAGHEMITE NANOCOMPOSITES OF GUAR GUM, HYDROXYPROPYL METHYLCELLULOSE AND THEIR BLENDS

3.1 Introduction

In the previous chapter the miscibility of guar gum and methylcellulose and maghemite nanoparticles compatibilization effect of on guar gum/methylcellulose blends were discussed. Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose is also a semi-synthetic water soluble polymer derived from cellulose. Chemically, HPMC is a cellulose-ether with hydroxyl groups have been substituted with hydroxypropyl groups. It is having many properties suitable for its applications in biomedical fields [177-179].

In this chapter miscibility of natural polymer guar gum and a semi-synthetic polymer hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) at different compositions were studied by refractive index, density, ultrasonic velocity and viscosity measurement techniques in their dilute solution at 30°C and 40°C. The influence of maghemite nanoparticles on the miscibility of GG/HPMC blends were studied by refractive index, density, ultrasonic velocity and viscosity measurement techniques in their dilute solution at 30°C and 40°C. Further SEM, FTIR, DSC, TGA, and tensile strength measurements were done.

3.2 Experimental Procedure

GG, HPMC, and maghemite magnetic nanoparticles were purchased from Merck, India. Schematic representation of guar gum and HPMC are given in Figure 1.2, and Figure 1.5, respectively [Chapter 2].

Blends of GG/HPMC of different compositions were prepared using distilled water. Ultrasonic velocity, refractive index, and density of the blend solutions of total polymer concentration of 0.5 % (w/v) were measured at 30°C and 40°C.

Stock solutions and blend stock solutions were prepared as per the procedure given in Chapter 2. The maghemite nanocomposites of 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, and 0.05 wt% were prepared separately with guar gum (0.2% w/v) and hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose (0.5% w/v). The prepared mixtures were stirred for 6 hours in a polymer mixer and then kept for ultrasonication for 4 hours to get uniform mixing. The prepared samples

were taken in test tubes and kept in contact with strong magnet for 30 minutes to check the stability of the solution. All the maghemite-HPMC composite solutions showed stability towards magnetic field, whereas the solutions of guar gum containing 0.05, 0.04, and 0.03 wt% of maghemite showed settlement of maghemite on the sides of the test tube attracted by the strong magnet. Hence the experiments were continued with 0.02 wt% of maghemite.

The prepared polymer/polymer blend - maghemite composites were solution casted and characterized. SEM, FTIR, DSC, TGA, and tensile strengths were measured as per the procedure mentioned in Chapter 2, section 2.2.

3.3 Results and Discussions

3.3.1 Refractive index measurements

The RI values of HPMC, and GG is 1.3413, and 1.3423, and 1.335, and 1.3402, respectively at 30°C and 40°C. The RI values of blend compositions of 10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 GG/HPMC are found to be in between that of HPMC and GG. At 30°C 90/10 GG/HPMC blend is composition dependent, whereas other compositions deviated from linearity.

Figure 3.1: Variation of refractive index with composition of GG/HPMC blend

The blend compositions 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 GG/HPMC show linearity in RI with respect to the pure polymers, whereas 10/90, and 30/70 GG/HPMC blend compositions deviated from the linearity (Figure 3.1) at 40°C. This indicates that GG/HPMC blends are miscible with more than 50% GG in the blend [99-108].

3.3.2 Ultrasonic velocity measurements

The Ultrasonic velocity values for HPMC is 1530 m/s, and 1552 m/s, and for GG is 1473 m/s, and 1508 m/s, respectively at 30°C and 40°C. The variation of ultrasonic velocity with % composition of GG plots showed linearity for 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 GG/HPMC blend compositions compared with GG and HPMC. This indicates that GG/HPMC blend is miscible when GG content is more than 50% in the blend [99-108].

The maghemite nanocomposite solution with HPMC has ultrasonic velocity value of 1512 m/s, and 1528 m/s, and for GG is 1464 m/s, and 1488 m/s, respectively at 30°C and 40°C. Compared with the plot of pure GG, HPMC, and their blends the maghemite nanocomposites showed linearity for all the compositions of GG/HPMC (Figure 3.2A). The incorporation of maghemite nanoparticles improved the miscibility nature of GG/HPMC blends (Figure 3.2B).

A

Figure 3.2: Variation of ultrasonic velocity of A) GG/HPMC blends, and B) GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposites

3.3.3 Density measurements

The density value of HPMC is $0.9988 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $0.9950 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and for GG is $0.9972 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $0.99376 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, respectively at 30°C and 40°C. Both at 30°C and 40°C 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 GG/HPMC blend solutions density values showed linearity with GG and HPMC (Figure 3.3A). Hence the GG/HPMC blends are miscible for the blend composition containing more than 50% of GG [99-108].

With the addition of 0.02 wt% maghemite the density values of the polymers and their blends got increased. All the blend - nanocomposites showed linearity indicating complete miscibility of GG/HPMC with the incorporation of 0.02 wt% maghemite (Figure 3.3B).

Figure 3.3: Variation of density of A) GG/HPMC blends, and B) GG/HPMC blends – maghemite nanocomposites

3.3.4 Adiabatic compressibility measurements

Adiabatic compressibility values were calculated and found to be $4.27699 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, and $4.17247 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$ for HPMC and $4.62181 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, and $4.42503 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$ for GG, respectively at 30°C and 40°C . The calculated adiabatic compressibility values for maghemite incorporated HPMC is $4.16192 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, and $4.15024 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, and for GG is $4.63328 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, and $4.5232 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, respectively at 30°C and 40°C . The plot (Figure 3.4A) indicates that GG/HPMC blend is miscible when GG is 50% or more in the blend. With the incorporation of 0.02 wt% maghemite, all the compositions showed linearity (Figure 3.4B). This confirms that GG/HPMC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite composites are miscible at all compositions [99-108].

A

Figure 3.4: Variation of adiabatic compressibility of A) GG/HPMC blends, and B) GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposites

3.3.5 Reduced viscosity measurements

Reduced viscosities of GG, HPMC and their blend compositions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 30/70, and 90/10) and the corresponding 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites were measured at 30°C and 40°C. Huggin's plots of the pure polymers and their blend compositions and of maghemite composites are shown in Figure 3.5.

From the plots (Figure 3.5A, and 3.5B) it is observed higher slopes for 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 GG/HPMC blend compositions at both 30°C and 40°C (Table 3.1). This observation confirms the miscibility of GG/HPMC blends when the % composition of GG is 50 or more in the blend. Whereas the maghemite nanocomposite's reduced viscosity against concentration plots (Figure 3.5C, and 3.5D) confirms that with 0.02 wt% addition of maghemite nanoparticles all the GG/HPMC blend compositions are miscible at 30°C and 40°C.

A

B

C

D

Figure 3.5: Huggins's plot for A) GG/HPMC blend at 30°C, B) GG/HPMC blend at 40°C, C) GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposites at 30°C, and D) GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposites at 40°C

Table 3.1: Slope values from Huggins plots

Composition (GG/HPMC)	GG/HPMC blends		GG/HPMC blend – maghemite composites	
	30°C	40°C	30°C	40°C
0/100	102.927	93.218	93.981	75.496
10/90	101.775	83.593	134.957	78.181
30/70	90.406	82.260	143.090	78.612
50/50	132.812	120.684	141.315	90.333
70/30	147.763	141.187	143.933	108.769
90/10	167.927	151.048	157.327	146.369
100/0	170.260	154.666	142.721	122.793

3.3.6 FTIR spectroscopy measurements

FTIR spectra of pure GG, GG - maghemite nanocomposite, Pure HPMC, HPMC - maghemite nanocomposite, 50/50 GG/HPMC blend, and 50/50 GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposite were recorded and presented in Figure 2.7a, 2.7c (Reproduced from Chapter 2), 3.6A, 3.6B, 3.6C, and 3.6D, respectively.

Pure HPMC (Figure 3.6A) showed the characteristic peaks: 3330 cm^{-1} for O-H stretching at, 3000-2800 cm^{-1} for C-H stretching, 1642 cm^{-1} for C=O stretching, and 1300-900 cm^{-1} for C-O-C stretching [99]. The FTIR spectra of GG (Figure 2.7a) showed the following peaks: 3347.3 cm^{-1} for –OH bond stretching, 2918.2 cm^{-1} for C–H group stretching, 1628.3 cm^{-1} for –OH bond, 1370.9 cm^{-1} for CH₂ group bending, and 1012.7 cm^{-1} for CH₂–O–CH₂ [206]. HPMC-maghemite composite showed a –OH band shift to lower wave number 3325 cm^{-1} and the carbonyl peak frequency got decreased. This indicates the interaction between HPMC and maghemite. The 50/50 GG/HPMC blend showed a hydroxyl group absorption peak at about 3319 cm^{-1} which is lower than that of GG and HPMC. This confirms the miscibility nature of GG and HPMC blend. 50/50 GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposite also showed the hydroxyl group peak shifting to lower wave number 3282 cm^{-1} . This confirms the formation of hydrogen bonding between the hydroxyl groups of GG and carbonyl groups of HPMC [99].

FTIR of a) GG (Figure 2.7a), and c) GG-maghemite nanocomposite (Figure 2.7c)

[Reproduced from chapter 2]

Figure 3.6: FTIR spectra of A) HPMC, B) HPMC - maghemite nanocomposite, C) 50/50 GG/HPMC blend, and D) 50/50 GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposite

3.3.7 Morphological studies

All the solution-casted films of GG, HPMC, 50/50 GG/HPMC blend, GG - maghemite nanocomposite, HPMC - maghemite nanocomposites, and 50/50 GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposite were characterized by SEM. The results are given in Figure 3.7.

SEM images of a) GG, b) GG-maghemite nanocomposite [Reproduced from Chapter 2; Figure 2.6a, and b]

Figure 3.7: SEM images of A) HPMC, B) HPMC - maghemite nanocomposite, C) 50/50 GG/HPMC blend, and D) 50/50 GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposite

For 50/50 GG/HPMC blend, it can be observed that the HPMC granule was well distributed in the GG matrix, confirming a good interaction between GG and HPMC. The SEM image of 50/50 GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposite indicates the distribution of maghemite nanoparticles in the miscible blend of 50/50 GG/HPMC blend.

This observation indicates the homogeneity of GG/HPMC blend. These observations suggest that GG/HPMC blend is miscible when GG is 50% and more in the blend and the incorporation of maghemite nanoparticle strengthened the miscibility nature of the blends.

3.3.8 Glass transition temperature measurements

The experimental T_g value of GG, HPMC, 50/50 GG/HPMC blend, 70/30 GG/HPMC blend, and 90/10 GG/HPMC blend are represented in Figure 3.8 and they are found to be 56.6°C, 44.5°C, 49.6°C, 52.3°C, and 55.1°C, respectively. The T_g values of the blends is found to be composition depended to that of GG and HPMC confirming miscibility of the blend.

The experimental T_g value for 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 compared with theoretical T_g value calculated using Fox Equation [201] and Wood's Equation [202] and tabulated in Table 3.2. The experimental T_g values are found to be higher than the theoretical T_g values confirming intermolecular hydrogen bonding between GG and HPMC for 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 blend compositions.

Figure 3.8: DSC thermograms of a) GG, b) HPMC, c) 50/50 GG/HPMC blend, d) 70/30 GG/HPMC blend, and e) 90/10 GG/HPMC blend

The experimental T_g value of GG – maghemite nanocomposite, HPMC – maghemite nanocomposite, and their blend – maghemite nanocomposites (90/10, 70/30, 50/50, 30/70, and 10/90) are represented in Figure 3.9 and they are found to be 62.4°C,

48.3°C, 61.2°C, 58.4°C, 55.6°C, 52.8°C, and 50.1°C , respectively. The Tg values of the blend - nanocomposites is found to be composition depended to that of GG – maghemite nanocomposite and HPMC – maghemite nanocomposite confirming compatibility of the blends.

The experimental Tg value for 90/10, 70/30, 50/50, 30/70, and 10/90 compared with theoretical Tg value calculated using Fox Equation and Wood’s Equation and tabulated in Table 3.2. The experimental Tg values are found to be higher than the theoretical Tg values confirming intermolecular hydrogen bonding between GG and HPMC for all the blend – maghemite composites.

Table 3.2: Experimental and theoretical glass transition temperature (Tg) of GG, HPMC, and GG/HPMC blends

Composition	Experimental Tg values (°C)	Theoretical Tg values (°C)		
		Fox Equation	Wood Equation	
GG/HPMC blends	0/100	56.6	--	--
	50/50	50.6	49.8	50.5
	70/30	53.1	52.3	52.9
	90/10	55.4	55.1	55.3
	100/0	44.5	--	--
GG/HPMC blend – maghemite composites	0/100	62.4	--	--
	10/90	50.1	49.4	49.7
	30/70	52.8	51.8	52.5
	50/50	55.6	54.4	55.3
	70/30	58.4	57.3	58.1
	90/10	61.2	60.6	60.9
	100/0	48.3	--	--

Figure 3.9: DSC thermograms of the nanocomposites of 0.02 wt% maghemite with a) GG, b) 90/10 GG/HPMC blend, c) 70/30 GG/HPMC blend, d) 50/50 GG/HPMC blend, e) 30/70 GG/HPMC blend, f) 10/90 GG/HPMC blend, and g) HPMC

3.3.9 Thermogravimetric analysis

Table 3.3: Parameters calculated from the thermograms of GG, HPMC, GG/HPMC blends and their maghemite nanocomposites

Composition		Temperature ($\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$)					
		T_0	T_{20}	T_{40}	T_{50}	T_{60}	T_{\max}
GG/HPMC blends	0/100	230	268	281	291	311	370
	50/50	237	256	281	289	302	355
	70/30	223	244	273	286	300	337
	90/10	210	229	262	281	294	348
	100/0	207	217	251	268	283	301
GG/HPMC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite composites	0/100	250	300	303	314	322	367
	10/90	251	276	290	298	309	350
	30/70	232	264	281	288	300	329
	50/50	230	256	279	287	304	338
	70/30	215	245	269	291	308	351
	90/10	202	226	292	304	326	352
	100/0	194	202	274	290	309	331

Figure 3.10: TGA curves of a) GG, b) HPMC, c) 50/50, d) 70/30, and e) 90/10 GG/HPMC blends

Figure 3.11: TGA curves of nanocomposites of 0.02 wt% maghemite with a) GG, b) HPMC, c) 10/90, d) 30/70, e) 50/50, f) 70/30, and g) 90/10 GG/HPMC blends

The samples of GG, GG – maghemite nanocomposite, HPMC, HPMC – maghemite nanocomposite, GG/HPMC blends (90/10, 70/30, and 50/50) and GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposite were characterized by thermogravimetric analyzer under nitrogen environment (Figure 3.10, and 3.11).

The temperature characteristics are calculated and shown in Table 3.3. The thermal characteristics of the blend compositions showed composition dependency. The initial degradation temperature of 50/50 GG/HPMC blend is found to be higher than that of GG, and HPMC. Addition of maghemite nanoparticle improved the thermal stability of the pure polymers and the blends. The blend – nanocomposites showed composition depended thermal properties confirming intermolecular interaction between the polymers.

3.3.10 Tensile strength measurements

All GG/HPMC blends (50/50, 70/30, and 90/10) showed composition dependent tensile properties, where as comparatively 10/90 GG/HPMC – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite showed improved tensile strength (Table 3.4).

Table 3.4: Tensile strength at yield, % of elongation and tensile modulus of GG, HPMC, and GG/HPMC blends and their maghemite nanocomposites

Composition		Tensile Strength at Yield (MPa)	% Elongation	Tensile Modulus (MPa)
GG/HPMC blends	0/100	36.45	8.78	927.5
	50/50	31.9	7.17	669.9
	70/30	26.4	6.97	642.4
	90/10	24.1	6.84	628.9
	100/0	25.7	6.41	621.3
GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposites	0/100	35.24	8.34	946.2
	10/90	33.12	8.12	754.8
	30/70	30.2	8.04	642.5
	50/50	28.4	7.84	583.3
	70/30	26.7	6.5	564.7
	90/10	24.3	6.1	552.1
	100/0	21.3	5.12	542.3

Chapter- 4

Biocompatible Maghemite Nanocomposites of Xanthan Gum, Methylcellulose and their Blends

“You should not give up and we should not allow the problem to defeat us.”

- A. P. J. Abdul Kalam

Chapter 4

BIOCOMPATIBLE MAGHEMITE NANOCOMPOSITES OF XANTHAN GUM, METHYL CELLULOSE, AND THEIR BLENDS

4.1 Introduction

Discovered in 1963 at USA's the NCAUR, xanthan gum (XG) is one of the popular commercially produced gums. It was first derived from *Xanthomonas campestris* of the cabbage family by the bacterial action. With the help of fermentation technology, XG is now produced from cornstarch. Xanthan gum is used in pharmaceutical, personal care items, and processed food industries. Its broad usefulness as an emulsifying, gelling, film-forming, thickening and stabilizing agent makes XG one of the most attractive products [166-170].

Methylcellulose (MC) was blended with guar gum in our previous work (Chapter 2) and found to be immiscible with guar gum. Blending of polymers can not be predicted seeing the functional groups on them. The 3D structural alignment, uncoiling/coiling of polymers and other parameters decides the availability of the functional groups on polymers to for intermolecular interaction. Since xanthan gum is a biocompatible water soluble polymers having applications in drug formulations, the blend properties of XG and MC are intensively studied with refractive index, density, ultrasonic velocity, and dilute solution viscometry in solution state and the blend thin films were characterized by SEM, FTIR, DSC, TGA, and UTM. Further the influence of the biocompatible magnetic nanoparticle, maghemite on the blends were determined. Due to the non-ionic nature of xanthan gum [166], it can not be applied to the Huggins equation. Hence for the viscosity studies a 0.1 M sodium chloride was added to XG solutions.

4.2 Experimental Procedure

Xanthan gum (XG) and methylcellulose (MC) were purchased from Merck, Mumbai, India, maghemite, and research-grade NaCl (Merck make) were used in this study. The structure of XG and MC is shown in Figures 1.3 and 1.4 [Chapter 1B] respectively.

Polymer blends of XG/MC in aqueous solution of different compositions were prepared. RI, density, and ultrasonic velocity of the solutions of with total polymer concentration 0.5 % (w/v) were measured at 30°C and 40°C.

Stock solutions of XG and MC were prepared (0.5 % w/v) in 0.1 M NaCl. Viscosity measurements were performed at 30°C and 40°C as per the procedure given in Chapter 2.

0.01, 0.02 wt%, 0.03, 0.04, and 0.05 wt% maghemite nanocomposites were prepared separately with guar gum (0.5% w/v) and methylcellulose (0.5% w/v). The mixtures were stirred for 6 hours with a polymer mixer and kept for ultrasonication for 4 hours for uniform mixing. The prepared samples were taken in test tubes and kept in contact with a strong magnet for 30 minutes to check the stability of the solution. All the maghemite-MC composite solutions showed stability towards the magnetic field, whereas the solutions of xanthan gum containing 0.05, and 0.04 wt% of maghemite showed the settlement of maghemite on the sides of the test tube attracted by the strong magnet. Hence the experiments were continued with 0.02, and 0.03 wt% of maghemite.

Thin films were prepared by solution casting method. Separate aqueous solutions of XG, MC, XG/MC blend, and XG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite solutions were prepared. The total polymer concentration was kept at 0.1% (w/v). The solutions of XG, MC, XG/MC blend, and XG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite solutions were then cast onto a plastic plate and dried in a dust-free atmosphere. The dried thin films were removed and from the plate and characterized. SEM, FTIR, DSC, TGA, and tensile strength measurements were performed as per the procedure mentioned in Chapter 2, section 2.2.

4.3 Results and Discussions

4.3.1 Refractive index measurements

Refractive index (RI) of methylcellulose is 1.3423, and 1.3413 at 30°C and 40°C, and for xanthan gum it is 1.3447, and 1.3435, respectively. The RI value of XG/MC blends is found to be in between those of xanthan gum and methylcellulose. It is found from the graph (Figure 4.1) that both at 30°C and 40°C the blend compositions 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 showed linearity with respect to XG and MC. Whereas 10/90 and 30/70 XG/MC blends are not having linearity.

Figure 4.1: Variation of refractive index of XG/MC blend

4.3.2 Density measurements

The density value of methylcellulose is found to be $0.9985 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $0.99525 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$ and for xanthan gum it is $0.9999 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $0.9966 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, respectively. The density values of XG/MC blends are observed to be in between that of XG and MC but the linearity is observed for 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 XG/MC blend compositions only at both 30°C and 40°C (Figure 4.2A).

With the addition of 0.02 wt% maghemite, the density value of methylcellulose is found to $0.9996 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $0.9988 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and for xanthan gum, it is $1.0067 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $1.0032 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, respectively at 30°C and 40°C. The increase in density indicates the interaction of the polymers with maghemite. All the blend - maghemite nanocomposite compositions with 0.02 wt% maghemite showed linearity with respect to their pure polymers composites with maghemite (Figure 4.2B). It indicates that the incorporation of 0.02 wt% maghemite act as a compatibilizer to the blends [99-108].

With the addition of 0.03 wt% maghemite, the density value of methylcellulose is found to $0.9999 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $0.9992 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and for xanthan gum, it is $1.0078 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $1.0054 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, respectively at 30°C and 40°C. The 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites of XG/MC blends do not show linearity (Figure 4.2C).

A

B

C
Figure 4.2: Variation of density of A) XG/MC blends, B) XG/MC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites, and C) XG/MC blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites

4.3.3 Ultrasonic velocity measurements

The ultrasonic velocity value of methylcellulose at 30°C and 40°C is found to be 1525 m/s, and 1545 m/s and for xanthan gum it is 1473 m/s, and 1485 m/s, respectively. The ultrasonic velocity values of XG/MC blends are observed to be in between that of XG and MC but the linearity is observed for 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 XG/MC blend compositions only at both 30°C and 40°C (Figure 4.3A).

With the addition of 0.02 wt% maghemite, the ultrasonic velocity value of methylcellulose at 30°C and 40°C is found to 1510 m/s, and 1524 m/s, and for xanthan gum it is 1434 m/s, and 1462 m/s, respectively. All the blend - maghemite nanocomposite compositions with 0.02 wt% maghemite showed linearity with respect to their pure polymers composites with maghemite (Figure 4.3B). It indicates that the incorporation of 0.02 wt% maghemite act as a compatibilizer to the blends [99-108].

With the addition of 0.03 wt% maghemite, the ultrasonic velocity value of methylcellulose at 30°C and 40°C is found to 1518 m/s, and 1531 m/s, and for xanthan gum, it is 1441 m/s, and 1470 m/s, respectively. The 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites of XG/MC blends show linearity for 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10

compositions, and 10/90, 30/70 compositions do not show linearity with respect to XG - (0.03 wt%) maghemite and MC - (0.03 wt%) maghemite (Figure 4.3C).

A

B

Figure 4.3: Variation of ultrasonic velocity of A) XG/MC blends, B) XG/MC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites, and C) XG/MC blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites

4.3.4 Adiabatic compressibility measurements

The β_{ad} value at 30°C and 40°C of methylcellulose at 30°C and 40°C is $4.30638 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, and $4.20931 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$ and for xanthan gum, it is $4.60933 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, and $4.55016 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, respectively. The adiabatic compressibility values of XG/MC blends are observed to be in between that of XG and MC but the linearity is observed for 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 XG/MC blend compositions only at both 30°C and 40°C (Figure 4.4A).

With the addition of 0.02 wt% maghemite, the adiabatic compressibility value at 30°C and 40°C of methylcellulose is $4.38753 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$ and $4.31074 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, and for xanthan gum, it is $4.83061 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, and $4.66356 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, respectively. All the blend - maghemite nanocomposite compositions with 0.02 wt% maghemite showed linearity with respect to their pure polymers composites with maghemite (Figure 4.4B). It indicates that the incorporation of 0.02 wt% maghemite act as a compatibilizer to the blends [99-108].

With the addition of 0.03 wt% maghemite, the value of methylcellulose at 30°C and 40°C is $4.3401 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, and $4.2697 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, and for xanthan gum, it is

$4.77857 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, and $4.60285 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, respectively. The 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites of XG/MC blends show linearity for 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 compositions, and 10/90, 30/70 compositions do not show linearity with respect to XG - (0.03 wt%) maghemite and MC - (0.03 wt%) maghemite (Figure 4.4C).

A

B

C

Figure 4.4: Variation of adiabatic compressibility of A) XG/MC blends, B) XG/MC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites, and C) XG/MC blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites

4.3.5 Reduced viscosity measurements

Reduced viscosities of XG, MC and their blend compositions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 30/70, and 90/10), XG – 0.02 wt % maghemite nanocomposite, MC – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite, and their blend compositions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 30/70, and 90/10), XG – 0.03 wt % maghemite nanocomposite, MC – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposite, and their blend compositions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 30/70, and 90/10) were measured at 30°C and 40°C (Tables 4.5, 4.6, and 4.7, respectively). Huggin's plots of reduced viscosities against concentrations are shown in Figure 4.5.

At both 30°C and 40°C all the plots of XG/MC blend compositions were found to be linear. A higher slope variation is observed for 90/10, 70/30, and 50/50 XG/MC blends, whereas comparatively lower slope for 10/90, and 30/70 XG/MC blend compositions. It confirms that the XG/MC blend is miscible when XG content is 50% or more [99-108]. The slope value is tabulated in Table 4.1.

A

B

C

D

Figure 4.5: Huggins's plot for A) XG/MC blend at 30°C, XG/MC blend at 40°C, C) XG/MC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite at 30°C, D) XG/MC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite at 40°C, E) XG/MC blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposite at 30°C, and F) XG/MC blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposite at 40°C

Table 4.1: Slope values from Huggins plots

Composition (XG/MC)	Blends		Blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite composites	
	30°C	40°C	30°C	40°C
0/100	153.290	151.139	175.684	161.654
10/90	146.927	150.169	282.642	261.533
30/70	151.884	148.030	411.581	301.703
50/50	201.012	256.945	472.787	344.375
70/30	290.212	298.993	508.836	379.460
90/10	420.115	386.418	566.400	380.339
100/0	500.812	414.054	568.272	351.836

The plots were linear for XG, XG - 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite, MC, MC - 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite, blends of XG/MC, and blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites. But the plots were non-linear for the XG – 0.03 wt% maghemite, MC – 0.03 wt% maghemite, and XG/MC blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites. The incorporation of 0.03 wt% maghemite affected the viscosity values. All the plots of blends with 0.02 wt% maghemite showed higher slope variation confirming the miscibility. Whereas for blends without maghemite nanoparticles higher slope variation is observed for 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 blend composition. Without the presence of maghemite nanoparticles the XG/MC blend is miscible only when the XG content is 50% or more in the blend.

4.3.6 FTIR measurements

FTIR spectra of XG, XG – 0.02 wt% maghemite composite, MC, MC – 0.02 wt% maghemite composite, and their blend films (50/50) were recorded. Figure 4.6 shows, the FTIR spectra of pure and blend films in the wavelength range of 4000-500 cm^{-1} . The FTIR spectra of MC (Figure 2.5b) showed the characteristic peaks: 3350.3 cm^{-1} , and 1593.7 cm^{-1} for –OH stretching, and –OH bond, 2916.7 cm^{-1} for C-H stretching, 1412 cm^{-1} for –CH₂ scissoring, and 1026 cm^{-1} for -O- stretching [207, 208]. On the other hand, the bands of XG (Figure 4.6A) appeared at 3320.0 cm^{-1} for the hydroxyl groups and at 1601.2 cm^{-1} and 1371.3 cm^{-1} for the asymmetric –COO⁻ stretching vibration and symmetric –COO⁻ stretching vibrations of pyruvate and glucuronate groups respectively [101].

FTIR spectra of b) MC, and d) MC – maghemite nanocomposite
[Reproduced from Chapter 2; Figure 2.7b, and 2.7d]

Figure 4.6: FTIR spectra of A) XG, B) XG – maghemite nanocomposite, C) 50/50 XG/MC blend, and D) XG/MC – maghemite nanocomposite

The spectrum of the XG/MC blend film was characterized by the presence of the absorption bands typical to that of the pure components, with the intensity roughly

proportional to the blending ratio. In the case of 50/50 XG/MC and 50/50 XG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite, the asymmetric -COO^- stretching vibration and symmetric -COO^- stretching vibrations of pyruvate and glucuronate groups shifted to 1598.2 cm^{-1} , 1405.8 cm^{-1} and 1596.4 cm^{-1} , 1405.6 cm^{-1} respectively (Figure 4.6C, and 4.6D). It is noticed that the hydroxyl stretching bands became much broader with increasing MC content. The results confirm the presence of hydrogen bonding between the hydroxyl groups of MC and carbonyl groups of XG.

4.3.7 Morphological studies

All the solution-casted films of XG, XG – maghemite nanocomposite, MC, MC – maghemite nanocomposite and their blend films (50/50) were characterized by SEM to check the morphology of the blends/nanocomposites. The results are given in Figure 4.7.

SEM images for c) MC, d) MC – maghemite nanocomposite

[Reproduced from Chapter 2, Figure 2.4c, and 2.4d]

Figure 4.7: SEM micrographs for (A) XG, (B) XG – maghemite nanocomposite, (C) 50/50 XG/MC blend, and (D) 50/50 XG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite

50/50 XG/MC blend (Figure 4.7C) did not show any aggregated particles. It can be seen that the MC granule was well distributed in the XG matrix. This confirms a good interaction between XG and MC. It was distinctly observed that the blend is homogeneous, and displayed in the form of a sandwich, which suggests that these blends were miscible [99]. The XG – maghemite nanocomposite (Figure 4.7B) and 50/50 XG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite (Figure 4.7D) shows the uniform distribution of maghemite nanoparticles.

4.3.8 Glass transition temperature measurements

The experimental T_g value of XG, MC, and their blends (90/10, 70/30, and) are represented in Figure 4.8 and they are found to be 63.3°C, 39.4°C, 61.3°C, 56.5°C, and 51.6°C, respectively. The T_g values of these blends is found to be composition depended to that of XG, and MC confirming miscibility of the blends. Whereas the 30/70, and 10/90 XG/MC blends showed two T_g values (Figure 4.8f, and Figure 4.8g, respectively) confirming phase separation of the polymers.

Table 4.2: Experimental and theoretical glass transition temperature (T_g) of XG, MC, and XG/MC blends and their maghemite composites

Composition	Experimental T _g values (°C)	Theoretical T _g values (°C)		
		Fox Equation	Wood Equation	
GG/HPMC blends	0/100	39.4	--	--
	50/50	51.6	48.5	51.3
	70/30	56.5	53.5	56.1
	90/10	61.3	59.6	60.9
	100/0	63.3	--	--
GG/HPMC blend - maghemite composites	0/100	43.7	--	--
	10/90	46.5	45.3	46.1
	30/70	51.3	48.9	51.0
	50/50	56.4	53.2	55.9
	70/30	61.1	58.3	60.7
	90/10	65.9	64.4	65.6
	100/0	68.1	--	--

The experimental T_g value for 90/10, 70/30, and 50/50 XG/MC blends compared with theoretical T_g value calculated using Fox Equation and Wood's Equation and tabulated in Table 4.2. The experimental T_g values are found to be higher than the theoretical T_g values confirming intermolecular hydrogen bonding between XG and MC for the blend composition with more than 50% of XG.

The experimental T_g value of the composites of 0.02 wt% maghemite with XG, MC, and their blends (90/10, 70/30, 50/50, 30/70, and 10/90) are represented in Figure 4.9 and they are found to be 68.1°C, 43.7°C, 65.9°C, 61.1°C, and 56.4°C, 51.3°C, and 46.5°C, respectively. The T_g values of these blend - nanocomposites is found to be composition depended to that of the composites of XG, and MC confirming compatibility of the blends.

Figure 4.8: DSC thermograms of a) XG, b) MC, c) 50/50 XG/MC blend, d) 70/30 XG/MC blend, e) 90/10 XG/MC blend, f) 30/70 XG/MC blend, and g) 10/90 XG/MC blend

Figure 4.9: DSC thermograms of the composites of 0.02 wt% of maghemite and a) XG, b) 90/10 XG/MC blend, c) 70/30 XG/MC blend, d) 50/50 XG/MC blend, e) 30/70 XG/MC blend, f) 10/90 XG/MC blend, and g) MC

.The experimental Tg value compared with theoretical Tg value calculated using Fox Equation and Wood's Equation and tabulated in Table 4.2. The experimental Tg values are found to be higher than the theoretical Tg values confirming intermolecular hydrogen bonding between XG and MC for the blend composition with the presence of 0.02 wt% maghemite.

4.3.9 Thermogravimetric analysis

The samples of XG, XG – maghemite nanocomposite, MC, MC – maghemite nanocomposite, XG/MC blends (90/10, 70/30, and 50/50) and XG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite were characterized by thermogravimetric analyzer under nitrogen environment (Figure 4.10, and 4.11). TG curve showed two mass loss stages - the 1st is the moisture loss of films and the 2nd stage for the depolymerisation, degradation, decomposition, steaming, and evolution of volatile compounds [214].

Figure 4.10: TGA curves of a) XG, b) 90/10 XG/MC, c) 70/30 XG/MC, d) 50/50 XG/MC, and e) MC

Table 4.3: Parameters evaluated from the thermograms of XG, MC, XG/MC blends and their maghemite composites

Composition		Temperature ($\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$)					
		T ₀	T ₂₀	T ₄₀	T ₅₀	T ₆₀	T _{max}
GG/HPMC blends	0/100	184	199	240	256	285	305
	50/50	187	215	261	277	297	329
	70/30	206	222	264	272	281	313
	90/10	230	247	278	284	295	318
	100/0	244	263	289	293	303	351
GG/HPMC blend – maghemite composites	0/100	203	235	264	277	301	318
	10/90	199	237	276	294	313	331
	30/70	204	253	291	309	321	335
	50/50	214	261	296	310	336	355
	70/30	227	274	299	311	339	359
	90/10	247	282	315	328	348	364
	100/0	271	293	324	337	365	375

Figure 4.11: TGA curves of composites of 0.02 wt% maghemite with a) XG, b) 90/10 XG/MC, c) 70/30 XG/MC, d) 50/50 XG/MC, e) 30/70 XG/MC, f) 10/90 XG/MC, and g) MC

The temperature characteristics are calculated and shown in Table 4.3, and 4.4. The thermal characteristics of the blend compositions showed composition dependency. Addition of maghemite nanoparticle improved the thermal stability of the pure polymers and the blends. The blend – composites showed composition depended thermal properties confirming intermolecular interaction between the polymers.

4.3.10 Tensile strength measurements

XG/MC blends showed composition dependent tensile properties (Table 4.4). 90/10, 70/30 XG/MC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite composites also showed improved composition dependent tensile properties.

Table 4.4: Tensile strength at yield, % of elongation and tensile modulus of XG, MC, and XG/MC blends and their wt% maghemite composites

Composition		Tensile Strength at Yield	%	Tensile Modulus
		(MPa)	Elongation	(MPa)
XG/MC blends	0/100	38.21	10.74	978.6
	70/30	32.4	7.12	722.4
	90/10	29.7	6.45	689.8
	100/0	27.4	6.12	647.3
XG/MC blend – maghemite composites	0/100	36.5	9.54	945.8
	10/90	33.1	8.88	726.5
	30/70	32.5	7.56	682.6
	50/50	31.2	6.55	645.4
	70/30	29.6	6.21	602.3
	90/10	28.7	5.87	596.6
	100/0	26.8	5.48	587.8

Chapter- 5

Biocompatible Maghemite Nanocomposites of Xanthan Gum, Poly (Vinyl Alcohol), and their Blends

“We must teach science in the mother tongue. Otherwise, science will become a highbrow activity. It will not be an activity in which all people can participate.”

- C. V. Raman

Chapter 5

BIOCOMPATIBLE MAGHEMITE NANOCOMPOSITES OF XANTHAN GUM, POLY (VINYL ALCOHOL), AND THEIR BLENDS

5.1 Introduction

In Chapter 4, the miscibility of XG/MC blends and the effect of maghemite nanoparticle on the properties of the blends were studied. Poly (vinyl alcohol) is considered as a biodegradable polymer, and its biodegradation has been reported [181-184, 215]. PVA has been widely used in biomedical industries [180, 216, 217].

In this chapter miscibility of natural polymer xanthan gum and a synthetic polymer poly (vinyl alcohol) at different compositions were studied by refractive index, density, ultrasonic velocity and viscosity measurement techniques in their dilute solution at 30°C and 40°C, and by FTIR, SEM, DSC, TGA, and Tensile strength analysis techniques in solid state (thin films). The effect of maghemite magnetic nanoparticles on the properties of XG/PVA blends in solution and solid state are also done.

5.2 Experimental Procedure

GG and maghemite were purchased from Merck, India, and PVA from Rolex, India. Schematic representation of guar gum and poly (vinyl alcohol) are shown in Figures 1.2, and 1.6 [*Chapter 2*], respectively.

0.01, 0.02 wt%, 0.03, 0.04, and 0.05 wt% maghemite nanocomposites were prepared separately with guar gum (0.5% w/v) and PVA (0.5% w/v). The mixtures were stirred for 6 hours with polymer mixer and kept for ultrasonication for 4 hours for uniform mixing. The prepared samples were taken in test tubes and kept in contact with strong magnet for 30 minutes to check the stability of the solution. All the maghemite-PVA composite solutions showed stability towards magnetic field, whereas the solutions of xanthan gum containing 0.05, and 0.04 wt% of maghemite showed settlement of maghemite on the sides of the test tube attracted by the strong magnet. Hence the experiments were continued with 0.03 wt% of maghemite.

Polymer blends of XG/PVA of varying compositions were prepared. Ultrasonic velocity, density, and refractive index (of the 0.5 % (w/v) solutions) were measured at 30°C and 40°C.

Stock solutions of XG (in 0.1 M NaCl), PVA, and their blends were prepared (0.1% w/v) by stirring the mixtures at room temperature for about 45 minutes. Using the above stock solutions 0.01 to 0.1 w/v blend solutions were prepared and viscosity measurements were done at 30°C and 40°C.

Thin films were prepared and SEM, FTIR, DSC, TGA, and tensile strength measurements were performed as per the procedure mentioned in Chapter 2, section 2.2.

5.3 Results and Discussions

5.3.1 Refractive index measurements

Refractive index (RI) of PVA is 1.3423, and 1.3413 at 30°C and 40°C, and for xanthan gum it is 1.3447, and 1.3435, respectively. The RI value of XG/MC blends is found to be in between those of xanthan gum and PVA. It is found from the graph (Figure 5.1) that both at 30°C and 40°C the all the blend compositions showed linearity with respect to XG and PVA indicating miscibility of XG/PVA blends [99-108].

Figure 5.1: Variation of refractive index of XG/PVA blend

5.3.2 Density measurements

A

B

C

Figure 5.2: Variation of density of A) XG/PVA blends, B) XG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites, and C) XG/PVA blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites

The density of xanthan gum is found to be 0.9999×10^3 Kg/m³, and 0.9966×10^3 Kg/m³; and for PVA it is 0.9935×10^3 Kg/m³, and 0.9907×10^3 Kg/m³ at 30°C and 40°C, respectively. All the blend compositions showed composition dependent density values and the plot (Figure 5.2 A) is linear confirming the miscibility of the blends for entire blend compositions at 30°C and 40°C. Similarly the blend – 0.02wt% maghemite nanocomposites, and blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite composites showed composition dependency with their corresponding polymer – maghemite nanocomposites. From the plots (Figure 5.2 B, and C) it is confirmed that the compositions are compatible [99-108].

5.3.3 Ultrasonic velocity measurements

The ultrasonic velocity values for XG, PVA, XG – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite, PVA - 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite, XG - 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposite, PVA - 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposite are 1473 m/s, 1485 m/s; 1523 m/s, 1540 m/s; 1434 m/s, 1485 m/s; 1508 m/s, 1540 m/s; 1441 m/s, 1470 m/s; 1513 m/s, 1536 m/s at 30°C and 40°C, respectively. All the blend and blend – maghemite nanocomposite compositions showed composition dependent ultrasonic velocity values

and the plots (Figure 5.3) are linear indicating miscibility of the blends and compatibility of the blend – maghemite nanocomposites [99-108].

A

B

C

Figure 5.3: Variation of ultrasonic velocity of A) XG/PVA blends, B) XG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites, and C) XG/PVA blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites

5.3.4 Adiabatic compressibility measurements

The calculated adiabatic compressibility values for XG, PVA, XG – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite, PVA - 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite, XG - 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposite, PVA - 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposite are $4.6093 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, $4.5501 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$; $4.3394 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, $4.2561 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$; $4.8306 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, $4.5202 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$; $4.4022 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, $4.2301 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$; $4.7785 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, $4.6028 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$; $4.3583 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$, $4.2339 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$ at 30°C and 40°C, respectively. All the blend and blend – maghemite nanocomposite compositions showed composition dependent adiabatic compressibility values and the plots (Figure 5.4) are linear indicating miscibility of the blends and compatibility of the blend – maghemite nanocomposites [99-108].

A

B

C

Figure 5.4: Variation of adiabatic compressibility of A) XG/PVA blends, B) XG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites, C) XG/PVA blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites

5.3.5 Reduced viscosity measurements

Reduced viscosities of XG, PVA, their maghemite nanocomposites, blends (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10), and their blend – maghemite nanocomposites (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10) were measured. Huggin's plots of reduced viscosities against concentrations are shown in Figures 5.5. All the plots were found to be linear. The blend and blend – maghemite nanocomposite compositions showed composition dependency and higher slopes for observed. The slope values are given in Table 5.1. The higher slope variation is due to the increase in hydrodynamic volume confirming the miscibility of the blends and compatibility of maghemite nanocomposites [99-108].

A

B

C

D

E

F

Figure 5.5: Huggins's plot for A) XG/PVA blend at 30°C, B) XG/PVA blend at 40°C, C) XG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites at 30°C, D) XG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites at 40°C, E) XG/PVA blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites at 30°C, and F) XG/PVA blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites at 40°C

Table 5.1: Slope values from Huggins plots

Composition	30°C	40°C	
	0/100	15.406	18.127
	10/90	158.460	129.709
	30/70	306.248	225.551
XG/PVA blends	50/50	418.442	324.490
	70/30	496.157	454.842
	90/10	499.103	503.678
	100/0	500.812	414.054
	0/100	16.206	10.903
	10/90	149.454	145.139
XG/PVA blends – 0.02 wt% maghemite composites	30/70	296.151	271.248
	50/50	416.193	399.024
	70/30	484.351	444.157
	90/10	474.496	455.315
	100/0	568.272	351.836
	0/100	16.206	17.393
	10/90	163.133	159.836
XG/PVA blends – 0.03 wt% maghemite composites	30/70	305.254	303.430
	50/50	419.684	415.303
	70/30	488.551	485.715
	90/10	494.278	492.175
	100/0	568.272	355.272

5.3.6 FTIR spectroscopy measurements

FTIR spectra of XG, XG – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite, PVA, PVA – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite, 50/50 XG/PVA blends, and 50/50 XG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites were recorded. The FTIR spectra of PVA showed a broad peak at 3275.3 cm^{-1} indicating stretching of –OH groups and peak at 2919.2 cm^{-1} due to C-H stretching [215]. The hydroxyl stretching of xanthan gum is found at 3320 cm^{-1} , 50/50 XG/PVA blend at 3267 cm^{-1} , XG – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite at 3318.3 cm^{-1} , PVA – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite at 3273 cm^{-1} , and 50/50 XG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite at 3269 cm^{-1} .

[FTIR Spectroscopy for A) XG, B) XG – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite were reproduced from Chapter 4, Figure 4.6]

Figure 5.6: FTIR Spectroscopy for A) XG, B) XG – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite, C) PVA, D) PVA – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite, E) 50/50 XG/PVA blend, and E) 50/50 XG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite

It is noticed that the -OH stretching bands became broader and the C=O and -OH characteristic bands shifted towards lower wave numbers for the blend, and blend – maghemite nanocomposites confirming the presence of hydrogen bonding.

5.3.7 Morphological studies

Figure 5.7: Scanning electron micrographs for (A) XG, (B) XG-maghemite composite, (C) PVA, (D) PVA-maghemite composite, (E) 50/50 XG/PVA blend, (F) 50/50 XG/PVA blend-maghemite composite [Figures A and B are adapted from Chapter 4]

All the solution-casted films of XG, PVA, their maghemite nanocomposites, 50/50 XG/PVA blend and its maghemite composites were transparent. To check the morphology of the blends SEM was used. The results are given in Figure 5.7. 50/50

XG/PVA blend and 50/50 XG/PVA blend-maghemite nanocomposite show homogeneity between XG and PVA.

5.3.8 Glass transition temperature measurements

Figure 5.8: DSC thermograms of a) PVA, b) 10/90 XG/PVA, c) 30/70 XG/PVA, d) 50/50 XG/PVA, e) 70/30 XG/PVA, f) 90/10 XG/PVA, and g) XG

The DSC thermograms of XG, PVA, XG/PVA blends and their composites with 0.02 wt% maghemite, and 0.03 wt% maghemite are represented in Figures 5.8, 5.9, and 5.10. All the blend compositions with and without the presence of maghemite showed single T_g values confirming the miscibility. The experimental T_g values of all the blends are found to be higher than the theoretically calculated T_g values. It is also observed that the glass transition temperatures for the 0.03 wt% maghemite composites are higher than that of 0.02 wt% maghemite composites. The experimental and theoretical T_g values are tabulated in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2: Experimental and theoretical glass transition temperature (T_g) of XG, PVA, and XG/PVA blends and their maghemite composites

Composition		Experimental T _g values (°C)	Theoretical T _g values (°C)	
			Fox Equation	Wood Equation
XG/PVA blends	0/100	79.7	--	--
	10/90	78.2	77.6	78.0
	30/70	74.9	73.9	74.7
	50/50	71.7	70.5	71.5
	70/30	68.6	67.4	68.2
	90/10	65.2	64.6	64.9
	100/0	68.1	--	--
XG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite composites	0/100	83.4	--	--
	10/90	82.1	81.5	81.8
	30/70	79	78.1	78.8
	50/50	76.2	74.9	75.7
	70/30	72.8	72.0	72.6
	90/10	69.8	69.3	69.6
	100/0	68.1	--	--
XG/PVA blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite composites	0/100	86.1	--	--
	10/90	85	84.5	84.7
	30/70	82.3	81.4	81.9
	50/50	80.4	78.6	79.2
	70/30	76.8	76.0	79.2
	90/10	73.9	73.5	73.7
	100/0	72.4	--	--

Figure 5.9: DSC thermograms of the nanocomposites with 0.02 wt% maghemite and a) PVA, b) 10/90 XG/PVA, c) 30/70 XG/PVA, d) 50/50 XG/PVA, e) 70/30 XG/PVA, f) 90/10 XG/PVA, and g) XG

Figure 5.10: DSC thermograms of the nanocomposites with 0.03 wt% maghemite and a) PVA, b) 10/90 XG/PVA, c) 30/70 XG/PVA, d) 50/50 XG/PVA, e) 70/30 XG/PVA, f) 90/10 XG/PVA, and g) XG

5.3.9 Thermogravimetric analysis

Figure 5.11: TGA curves of a) XG, b) 90/10 XG/PVA, c) 70/30 XG/PVA, d) 50/50 XG/PVA, e) 30/70 XG/PVA, f) 10/90 XG/PVA, and g) PVA

Figure 5.12: TGA curves of nanocomposites of 0.02 wt% maghemite with a) XG, b) 90/10 XG/PVA, c) 70/30 XG/PVA, d) 50/50 XG/PVA, e) 30/70 XG/PVA, f) 10/90 XG/PVA, and g) PVA

Table 5.3: Parameters calculated from the thermograms of XG/PVA blends

Composition		Temperature ($\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$)					
		T_0	T_{20}	T_{40}	T_{50}	T_{60}	T_{\max}
XG/PVA blends	0/100	190	212	229	240	251	284
	10/90	196	228	248	260	274	293
	30/70	203	232	259	273	290	306
	50/50	215	244	256	281	294	332
	70/30	221	247	257	283	306	335
	90/10	222	252	272	285	305	334
	100/0	244	263	289	293	303	351
XG/PVA blend - 0.02 wt% maghemite composites	0/100	226	238	275	290	313	347
	10/90	233	249	286	303	322	353
	30/70	243	259	289	309	331	359
	50/50	249	272	302	318	341	362
	70/30	259	278	309	324	346	368
	90/10	267	283	315	334	356	370
	100/0	271	293	324	337	365	375
XG/PVA blend - 0.03 wt% maghemite composites	0/100	197	221	271	281	296	334
	10/90	225	240	280	296	307	344
	30/70	228	256	299	309	317	345
	50/50	256	271	301	313	326	373
	70/30	274	278	312	319	333	382
	90/10	276	305	318	327	341	384
	100/0	285	328	350	360	372	393

The samples of XG, PVA, XG/PVA blends, and 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites of XG, PVA, XG/PVA blends, and 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites of XG, PVA, XG/PVA blends were characterized by thermogravimetric analyzer under nitrogen environment (Figure 5.11, 5.12, and 5.13).

The temperature characteristics are calculated and shown in Table 5.3. The thermal characteristics of the blend compositions showed composition dependency. Addition of maghemite nanoparticle improved the thermal stability of the pure polymers and the blends. The blend – composites showed composition depended thermal properties confirming intermolecular interaction between the polymers.

Figure 5.13: TGA curves of nanocomposites of 0.03 wt% maghemite with a) XG, b) 90/10 XG/PVA, c) 70/30 XG/PVA, d) 50/50 XG/PVA, e) 30/70 XG/PVA, f) 10/90 XG/PVA, and g) PVA

5.3.10 Tensile strength measurements

XG/PVA blends with 90/10 and 70/30 showed mechanical properties higher than that of 50/50, 30/70, and 10/90 blends. 90/10, 70/30, and 50/50 XG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites showed improved mechanical properties. XG/PVA blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites showed varying mechanical properties. 0.03 wt% maghemite does not impart improved mechanical properties.

Table 5.4: Tensile strength at yield, % of elongation and tensile modulus of XG, PVA, and XG/PVA blends and their maghemite nanocomposites

Composition		Tensile Strength at	%	Tensile Modulus
		Yield (MPa)	Elongation	(MPa)
XG/PVA blends	0/100	42.8	14.6	1024.8
	10/90	36.9	14.1	835.4
	30/70	36.2	13.8	742.5
	50/50	32.5	13.5	713.4
	70/30	31.3	13.2	688.8
	90/10	28.4	12.4	652.4
	100/0	27.4	6.12	647.3
XG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite composites	0/100	40.5	13.8	1014.6
	10/90	38.9	13.4	1005.4
	30/70	37.4	13.1	948.6
	50/50	34.5	12.8	776.4
	70/30	33.2	12.4	654.6
	90/10	28.3	11.5	614.5
	100/0	26.8	5.48	587.8
XG/PVA blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite composites	0/100	39.4	12.4	998.7
	10/90	26.4	12.1	611.3
	30/70	26.3	8.7	599.9
	50/50	25.9	8.5	594.6
	70/30	26.1	6.8	587.5
	90/10	25.8	5.1	564.5
	100/0	25.8	3.45	542.6

Chapter- 6

**Transdermal Sustained Drug Release Applications of
Polymer Blends and their Maghemite Nanocomposites**

“It is better to work out than rust out.”

- Sir M. Visvesvaraya

Chapter 6

TRANSDERMAL SUSTAINED DRUG RELEASE APPLICATIONS OF POLYMER BLENDS AND THEIR MAGHEMITE NANOCOMPOSITES

6.1 Introduction

In order to improve the efficiency and to reduce the side effects of existing medication, researchers focussed on designing new drugs and dosage forms. The usage of various types of water soluble polymers in pharmaceutical industries has increased tremendously [33, 34]. The usage of conventional dosage forms with repeated dosages is producing large fluctuations of drug concentration in blood stream with toxic effects. These lead to the concept of controlled drug delivery system.

The sustained or controlled drug delivery forms reduce the frequency of dosing and increases the effectiveness of the drug. The targeted drug release systems improved the effectiveness of the drug by targeting at the site of action, reducing the number of dose required or providing uniform drug delivery. The controlled drug release systems (CDRS) provides a better control of plasma drug levels, less dosage frequency, less side effects, increased efficacy, and constant delivery. Polymers which are hydrophilic when used in CDRS made it easier to achieve a desirable drug release profile and are cost-effective. Transdermal drug release systems (TDRS) use the skin as a port for drug administration. The incorporation of drugs in to a biocompatible polymer is one of the efficient TDRS. The biocompatible polymer enhances the absorption of drugs. TDRS are non-invasive, requiring simple adhesion of the patch resulting in better patient compliance, improved bio-availability of the drug, and easy treatment termination [33, 34, 75, 76].

When a drug of relatively higher concentration inside of biocompatible polymer film (patch) is allowed to be in contact with the skin surface for a period of time, the drug will enter to the blood stream by diffusion. The variation of drug concentration on either side of the skin (membrane) allows the drug diffusion for an extended period of time and maintains constant drug concentration in the blood.

Metoprolol succinate is used as a model drug in this research work. The drug is soluble in water. It has a half-life of about 3-4 h., and its oral bioavailability has been reported to be about 50% [218].

6.2 Metoprolol Succinate

6.2.1 Chemistry of metoprolol succinate

Metoprolol is (+)-1-(isopropyl amino)-3-[p-(2-methoxyethyl)]-2-propanol succinate. A schematic representation of metoprolol is given in Figure 6.1.

Figure 6.1: Schematic representation of metoprolol succinate

6.2.2 Properties and applications of metoprolol succinate

It is whitish crystalline powder having molecular weight of 652.8 g/mol. Metoprolol succinate is soluble in water and methanol. It is sparingly soluble in ethanol, and dichloromethane; and insoluble in other organic solvents.

Metoprolol succinate is used for the treatment of diseases related cardiovascular system, like hypertension; acute myocardial infarction, ventricular tachycardia, congestive heart failure, prevention of migraine head-aches, etc. Metoprolol tartarate is an alternative of metoprolol succinate; tartarate is used for the immediate drug release formulations and metoprolol succinate is used for the sustained drug release formulations [219].

6.3 Experimental Procedure

Metoprolol succinate drug solution with polymers GG, XG, MC, HPMC, PVA, their maghemite nanocomposites, blends (GG/MC, GG/HPMC, XG/MC, and XG/PVA), and the blend – maghemite nanocomposite solutions were prepared. 50 mL each of the prepared solutions were poured to poly propylene petridishes of uniform dimensions. The thin films were prepared in a dust free atmosphere with the amount of drug in a 1 cm² patch to be about 39.339 µg. The dried thin films were peeled off from the plate and analyzed.

The average thickness of the thin films was calculated using a digital vernier calliper. The weight of three different thin films (1 cm²) of same composition was calculated by using electronic balance and the average of 3 samples were recorded. Folding endurance test carried out by repeated folding of the sample manually till it rupture for 3 test samples of each composition.

The physical stability of the samples towards humidity was tested by the % moisture absorption test. 3 samples of the same composition with 1 cm² dimension was cut from the thin film prepared by solution casting method and weighed accurately, then it was placed in a desiccator containing aluminium chloride. The relative humidity was 80%. After 36 h. the samples were removed and weighed. % moisture absorption was calculated by the following formula [218],

$$\text{Percentage Moisture Absorption (PMA)} = \frac{\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100 \quad (6.1)$$

The stability of the thin films towards dry condition is checked by percentage moisture loss test. The procedure is the same as for % moisture test but the desiccator contains anhydrous CaCl₂ and the the samples weighed after 72 hours. The % moisture loss was calculated by the following formula [218],

$$\text{Percentage Moisture Loss (PML)} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100 \quad (6.2)$$

The sample drug metoprolol succinate solution was scanned using a UV-visible spectrometer (Systronics-2202) in the wavelength region of 200 – 400 nm and λ_{max} was found to be 220.8 nm. At 220.8 nm, the absorption of a series of standard solutions of metoprolol succinate were measured and plotted a standard curve. This method obeys the Beer's law in concentration 5 to 30 µg/mL, and was having good correlation co-efficient.

Open glass diffusion tubes were used for the drug diffusion studies. The test samples of dimension of 1 cm² were kept inside the diffusion tube at the centre of a hydrated cellophane membrane, which was tied to the tube. It is then kept in contact with the receptor compartment containing 50 mL pH 7.4 phosphate buffer solution. The buffer solution was stirred at 100 rpm using a magnetic stirrer, at 37±1°C. 1 mL each of the buffer solutions containing drug diffused through the semi-permeable membrane (hydrated cellophane sheet) were withdrawn at 5, 10, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100, and 120 minutes and sink condition was maintained by replacing the equal volume of fresh buffer.

The Higuchi's model [220] and Koresmeyer-Peppas model [221] were fitted in to the kinetic data of drug release to have analyse the drug release mechanism of the films,.

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = k t^{1/2} \quad (6.3)$$

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = k t^n \quad (6.4)$$

Where M_t and M_∞ , are the amount of drug released at time t and infinite time, and k is a constant. n is the diffusion exponent and provides information about mass transport mechanism. When $n < 0.5$, the solvent diffuses and the drug is released through film with Fickian diffusion mechanism or anomalous diffusion and when $n \geq 1$ indicates zero order release [221, 222].

6.4 Results and Discussions

6.4.1 GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposites

Physicochemical evaluations

The thickness, weight, folding endurance (FE), % moisture absorbance (PMA), and % moisture loss (PML) values of metoprolol drug infused GG, MC, their maghemite nanocomposites, and 10/90 GG/MC blend - maghemite nanocomposite were measured and given in Table 6.1.

The weight and thickness of 3 samples each of the same composition were measured and found in the range of 0.087 to 0.092 mm and almost uniform weight in the

range of 218 to 223 mg. The folding endurance values were obtained in the range of 308 to 360 indicating good strength and elasticity. The folding endurance of semi-synthetic polymer methylcellulose is found to be higher compared to the natural polymer guar gum. The presence of maghemite nanoparticles reduced the folding endurance. The folding endurance test values indicates that all the thin film samples would maintain the reliability with skin during administration and can be used for transdermal drug release applications.

Table 6.1: Physicochemical parameters of GG, MC, their maghemite nanocomposites, and 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite

Composition	Thickness (mm)	Weight (mg)	FE	PMA	PML
GG	0.089 ±	221.000 ±	314 ±	7.72 ±	3.16 ±
	0.0024	1.549	2	0.80	0.03
MC	0.087 ±	218.167 ±	360 ±	4.56 ±	1.38 ±
	0.0012	1.169	2	0.44	0.00
GG – maghemite composite	0.092 ±	223.000 ±	308 ±	6.60 ±	2.38 ±
	0.0021	1.095	2	0.28	0.25
MC – maghemite composite	0.091 ±	222.167 ±	316 ±	4.51 ±	1.50 ±
	0.0018	0.753	2	0.46	0.26
10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite composite	0.087 ±	218.000 ±	315 ±	5.19 ±	2.14 ±
	0.0018	0.632	1	0.25	0.27

In order to assess the physical stability of the thin films at humid and dry conditions percentage moisture absorbance, and percentage moisture loss were measured as per the standard procedures. It is observed that the presence of maghemite nanoparticles improved the moisture absorption and moisture loss of the thin film. The samples showed percentage moisture absorbance in the range of 4.51 to 7.72, and percentage moisture loss in the range of 1.50 to 3.16.

Transdermal drug release kinetics

Figure 6.2 provides the drug release from thin films of GG, MC, their maghemite nanocomposites, and 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposites. The diffusion study showed that the drug release from methylcellulose was immediate compared to that of guar gum. The maghemite nanocomposite of methylcellulose and guar gum showed sustained release when compared with their pure polymer. The metoprolol succinate drug release from 10/90 GG/MC blend - maghemite nanocomposite was also in a sustained manner.

Figure 6.2: Drug release kinetic data for GG, MC, GG – maghemite composite, MC – maghemite composite, and 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite composite

Figure 6.3: Higuchi kinetics of GG, GG – maghemite composite, MC, MC – maghemite composite, and 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite composite

Figure 6.4: Koresmeyer-Peppas kinetics of GG, GG – maghemite composite, MC, MC – maghemite composite, and 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite composite

Table 6.2: The values of diffusion exponent and intercept from Koresmeyer-Peppas plots

Composition	Koresmeyer-Peppas model	
	Intercept (k)	Diffusion exponent (n)
GG	1.13636	0.25421
GG – maghemite composite	1.04097	0.2655
MC	1.20336	0.30718
MC –maghemite composite	1.12308	0.30138
10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite composite	1.1159	0.248

The amount of drug released vs square root of time (Higuichi method) gives the drug release nature; if the plot is linear then the system is diffusion controlled [220]. The plot of cumulative amount of drug released versus square root of time (Figure 6.3) indicated linearity and confirms that the drug release from all the system was by diffusion.

From in vitro release studies, the experimental data obtained was fit into Koresmeyer-Peppas model. From the plot (Figure 6.4) diffusion exponent n , and constant k , were determined (Table 6.2). In all the cases, the intercept $k > 0.5$, and $n < 0.5$. This confirms that the release of drug was Fickian kinetics [221, 223].

6.4.2 GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposites

Physicochemical evaluations

The thickness, weight, FE, PMA, PML values of metoprolol drug infused GG, HPMC, their maghemite nanocomposites, GG/HPMC blends (50/50, 70/30, and 90/10), and bend – maghemite nanocomposites (90/10, 70/30, 50/50, 30/70, and 10/90) were measured and given in Table 6.2, and Table 6.3.

Table 6.3: Physicochemical parameters of GG/HPMC blends

Composition	Thickness (mm)	Weight (mg)	FE	PMA	PML
0/100	0.087 ±	218.000 ±	346 ±	4.12 ±	1.53 ±
	0.0008	0.632	1	0.01	0.26
50/50	0.089 ±	220.667 ±	346 ±	5.29 ±	2.41 ±
	0.0022	1.366	1	0.26	0.26
70/30	0.085 ±	216.333 ±	327 ±	6.93 ±	2.46 ±
	0.0017	0.816	2	0.45	0.26
90/10	0.087 ±	217.833 ±	319 ±	7.04 ±	2.75 ±
	0.0024	0.753	1	0.28	0.47
100/0	0.089 ±	221.000 ±	314 ±	7.72 ±	3.16 ±
	0.0024	1.549	2	0.80	0.03

The weight and thickness of three patches each of the samples were measured. Film thickness is found in the range of 0.085 to 0.092 mm and almost uniform weight in the range of 216 to 223 mg. The folding endurance values were obtained in the range of 314 to 346 for GG/HPMC blends and 308 to 322 for maghemite nanocomposites of GG/HPMC blends indicating good strength and elasticity. The folding endurance of HPMC is found to be higher compared to GG. The presence of maghemite nanoparticles reduced the folding endurance. The folding endurance test values indicates that all the thin film samples would maintain the reliability with skin during administration and can be used for transdermal drug release applications.

Table 6.4: Physicochemical parameters of GG/HPMC blend - maghemite nanocomposites

Composition	Thickness (mm)	Weight (mg)	FE	PMA	PML
0/100	0.090 ±	221.333 ±	322 ±	3.93 ±	1.20 ±
	0.0019	1.033	1	0.70	0.26
10/90	0.086 ±	216.333 ±	321 ±	4.00 ±	1.85 ±
	0.0017	0.816	1	0.71	0.01
30/70	0.086 ±	216.667 ±	318 ±	4.14 ±	2.01 ±
	0.0028	1.033	1	0.47	0.26
50/50	0.086 ±	216.833 ±	318 ±	4.45 ±	2.16 ±
	0.0013	1.169	1	0.73	0.27
70/30	0.085 ±	216.333 ±	314 ±	4.91 ±	2.17 ±
	0.0018	1.506	1	0.30	0.27
90/10	0.087 ±	218.667 ±	310 ±	5.33 ±	2.29 ±
	0.0028	1.211	1	0.28	0.47
100/0	0.092 ±	223.000 ±	308 ±	6.60 ±	2.38 ±
	0.0021	1.095	2	0.28	0.25

In order to assess the physical stability of the thin films at humid and dry conditions percentage moisture absorbance, and percentage moisture loss were measured as per the standard procedures. It is observed that the presence of maghemite nanoparticles improved the moisture absorption and moisture loss of the thin film. The samples showed percentage moisture absorbance in the range of 4.12 to 7.72 for GG/HPMC blends, and 3.93 to 6.60 for GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposites. The percentage moisture loss is in the range of 1.53 to 3.16 for GG/HPMC blends and 1.20 to 2.38 for GG/HPMC – maghemite nanocomposites.

A

B

Figure 6.5: Drug release kinetic data for A) GG/HPMC blends, and B) GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposites

A

B

Figure 6.6: Higuchi kinetics of A) GG/HPMC blends, and B) GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposites

Figure 6.7: Koresmeyer-Peppas kinetics of A) GG/HPMC blends, and B) GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposites

Transdermal drug release kinetics

Figure 6.5 presents the drug release from thin films of GG, HPMC, their maghemite nanocomposites, GG/HPMC blends and their maghemite nanocomposites. The diffusion study showed that the drug release from hydroxypropyl methylcellulose was immediate compared to that of guar gum. The maghemite nanocomposite of hydroxypropyl methylcellulose and guar gum showed sustained release when compared with their pure polymer. The metoprolol succinate drugs release from the blends and blend – maghemite nanocomposites were also in a sustained manner.

Table 6.5: The values of diffusion exponent and intercept from Koresmeyer-Peppas plots

Composition	Koresmeyer-Peppas model		
	Intercept (k)	Diffusion exponent (n)	
GG/HPMC blend	0/100	1.12616	0.34005
	90/10	1.13751	0.26726
	70/30	1.11961	0.30936
	50/50	1.11952	0.33004
	100/0	1.13636	0.25421
GG/HPMC blend – maghemite composite	0/100	0.99855	0.3607
	10/90	1.03798	0.27317
	30/70	1.01513	0.29029
	50/50	1.02469	0.29702
	70/30	1.02512	0.30785
	90/10	1.00977	0.33182
	100/0	1.04097	0.2655

The plot of cumulative amount of drug released versus square root of time (Figure 6.6) indicated linearity and confirms that the drug release from all the system was by diffusion.

From the plot, Figure 6.7, the diffusion exponent n , and constant k , were determined and are presented in Table 6.5. In all the cases, $k > 0.5$ and $n < 0.5$ and confirms that the release of drug was Fickian kinetics [221, 223].

6.4.3 XG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposites

Physicochemical evaluations

The thickness, weight, folding endurance (FE), percentage moisture absorbance (PMA), and percentage moisture loss (PML) values of metoprolol drug infused XG, MC, their maghemite nanocomposites, XG/MC blends (50/50, 70/30, and 90/10), and bend – maghemite nanocomposites (90/10, 70/30, 50/50, 30/70, and 10/90) were measured and given in Table 6.6.

The weight and thickness of three patches each of the samples were measured. The film thickness is found in the range of 0.083 to 0.094 mm and almost uniform weight in the range of 212 to 224 mg. The folding endurance values were obtained in the range of 322 to 360 for XG/MC blends and 310 to 316 for maghemite nanocomposites of XG/MC blends indicating good strength and elasticity.

Methyl cellulose showed higher folding endurance than xanthan gum. The presence of maghemite nanoparticles reduced the folding endurance. The folding endurance test values indicates that all the thin film samples would maintain the reliability with skin during administration and can be used for transdermal drug release applications.

To assess the physical stability of the thin films at humid and dry conditions percentage moisture absorbance, and percentage moisture loss were measured as per the standard procedures. It is observed that the presence of maghemite nanoparticles improved the moisture absorption and moisture loss of the thin film. The samples showed percentage moisture absorbance in the range of 4.56 to 7.72 for XG/MC blends, and 4.51 to 7.12 for XG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposites. The percentage moisture loss is

in the range of 1.38 to 4.24 for XG/MC blends and 1.50 to 2.96 for XG/MC – maghemite nanocomposites.

Table 6.6: Physicochemical parameters of XG/MC blend - maghemite nanocomposites

Composition	Thickness (mm)	Weight (mg)	FE	PMA	PML	
XG/MC blends	0/100	0.087 ±	218.167 ±	360 ±	4.56 ±	1.38 ±
		0.0012	1.169	2	0.44	0.00
	50/50	0.083 ±	213.833 ±	345 ±	6.22 ±	2.19 ±
		0.0017	0.753	1	0.28	0.27
	70/30	0.087 ±	217.833 ±	341 ±	7.03 ±	3.21 ±
		0.0010	0.753	1	0.26	0.78
	90/10	0.085 ±	215.833 ±	333 ±	7.56 ±	3.25 ±
		0.0013	0.753	2	0.30	0.46
100/0	0.084 ±	220.333 ±	322 ±	7.72 ±	4.24 ±	
	0.0009	0.816	1	1.67	0.27	
XG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposites	0/100	0.091 ±	222.167 ±	316 ±	4.51 ±	1.50 ±
		0.0018	0.753	2	0.46	0.26
	10/90	0.085 ±	216.167 ±	317 ±	5.09 ±	2.16 ±
		0.0015	0.753	1	0.02	0.26
	30/70	0.082 ±	212.667 ±	316 ±	5.64 ±	2.51 ±
		0.0011	1.033	1	0.02	0.29
	50/50	0.086 ±	217.000 ±	314 ±	6.00 ±	2.91 ±
		0.0008	0.632	1	0.02	0.69
	70/30	0.084 ±	215.000 ±	312 ±	6.50 ±	2.95 ±
		0.0008	0.632	1	0.02	0.53
	90/10	0.085 ±	215.333 ±	311 ±	6.96 ±	2.95 ±
		0.0013	0.816	1	0.02	0.26
100/0	0.094 ±	224.833 ±	310 ±	7.12 ±	2.96 ±	
	0.0047	0.753	1	0.02	0.26	

Transdermal drug release kinetics

Figure 6.8 presents the drug release from thin films of XG, MC, their maghemite nanocomposites, XG/MC blends and their maghemite nanocomposites. The diffusion study showed that the drug release from methylcellulose was immediate compared to that of xanthan gum. The maghemite nanocomposite of methylcellulose and xanthan gum showed sustained release when compared with their pure polymer. The metoprolol succinate drugs release from the blends and blend – maghemite nanocomposites were also in a sustained manner.

B

Figure 6.8: Drug release kinetic data for A) XG/MC blends, and B) XG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposites

A

B

Figure 6.9: Higuchi kinetics of A) XG/MC blends, and B) XG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposites

A

Figure 6.10: Koresmeyer-Peppas kinetics of A) XG/MC blends, and B) XG/MC blend - maghemite nanocomposites

The plot of cumulative amount of drug released versus square root of time (Figure 6.9) indicated linearity and confirms diffusion type drug release. From the plot, Figure 6.10, the diffusion exponent n , and constant k , were determined and are presented in Table 6.7. In all the cases, $k > 0.5$, and $n < 0.5$ and confirms that the release of drug was Fickian kinetics [221, 223].

Table 6.7: The values of diffusion exponent and intercept from Koresmeyer-Peppas plots

Composition	Koresmeyer-Peppas model		
	Intercept (k)	Diffusion exponent (n)	
0/100	1.20336	0.30718	
50/50	1.05543	0.28773	
XG/MC blends	70/30	1.05543	0.28773
	90/10	1.12376	0.2985
	100/0	1.02785	0.28204
	0/100	1.12308	0.30138
	10/90	0.99126	0.30791
XG/MC blend	30/70	1.03469	0.30057
– maghemite	50/50	1.0515	0.30548
nanocomposites	70/30	1.08497	0.3
	90/10	1.09322	0.30562
	100/0	0.98571	0.2971

6.4.4 XG/PVA blend – maghemite nanocomposites

Physicochemical evaluations

The thickness, weight, folding endurance (FE), percentage moisture absorbance (PMA), and percentage moisture loss (PML) values of metoprolol drug infused XG, PVA, their maghemite nanocomposites, XG/PVA blends (50/50, 70/30, and 90/10), and bend – maghemite nanocomposites (90/10, 70/30, 50/50, 30/70, and 10/90) were measured and given in Table 6.8, and 6.9.

The weight and thickness of three patches each of the samples were measured. The film thickness is found in the range of 0.081 to 0.097 mm and almost uniform weight in the range of 211 to 228 mg. The folding endurance values were obtained in the range of 322 to 372 for XG/PVA blends, 310 to 342 for 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites of XG/PVAC blends, and 303 to 339 for 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites of XG/PVAC blends indicating good strength and elasticity for transdermal drug release applications.

Table 6.8: Physicochemical parameters of XG/PVA blends

Composition	Thickness		FE	PMA	PML	
	(mm)	Weight (mg)				
XG/PVA blend	0/100	0.081 ±	212.167 ±	372 ± 2	9.92 ±	5.17 ±
		0.0007	1.169		0.85	0.04
	10/90	0.081 ±	212.000 ±	367 ± 2	9.73 ±	5.04 ±
		0.0010	1.414		0.52	0.49
	30/70	0.081 ±	212.167 ±	362 ± 2	8.99 ±	5.01 ±
		0.0007	1.329		0.94	0.25
	50/50	0.082 ±	212.667 ±	353 ± 3	8.91 ±	4.87 ±
		0.0040	1.862		0.45	0.66
	70/30	0.083 ±	213.833 ±	348 ± 1	8.74 ±	4.36 ±
		0.0014	0.753		0.56	0.25
	90/10	0.086 ±	216.667 ±	346 ± 1	8.59 ±	4.32 ±
		0.0010	1.033		0.70	0.52
	100/0	0.091 ±	220.333 ±	322 ± 1	7.72 ±	4.24 ±
		0.0047	0.816		1.67	0.27

PVA showed higher folding endurance than xanthan gum. The presence of maghemite nanoparticles reduced the folding endurance. The folding endurance test values indicates that all the thin film samples would maintain the reliability with skin during administration and can be used for transdermal drug release applications.

Table 6.9: Physicochemical parameters of XG/PVA blend - maghemite nanocomposites

Composition		Thickness (mm)	Weight (mg)	FE	PMA	PML	
XG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite composites	0/100	0.081 ±	211.833 ±	342 ± 2	7.56 ±	3.62 ±	
		0.0026	0.753		0.49	0.26	
	10/90	0.082 ±	213.000 ±	341 ± 1	7.52 ±	3.90 ±	
		0.0008	1.414		0.47	0.51	
	30/70	0.087 ±	217.500 ±	338 ± 1	7.50 ±	3.22 ±	
		0.0010	1.049		0.26	0.02	
	50/50	0.086 ±	217.333 ±	330 ± 2	7.35 ±	3.38 ±	
		0.0010	1.033		0.46	0.25	
	70/30	0.085 ±	215.833 ±	321 ± 2	7.25 ±	3.25 ±	
		0.0008	0.753		0.72	0.01	
	90/10	0.083 ±	214.167 ±	311 ± 1	7.18 ±	2.80 ±	
		0.0005	1.169		0.73	0.02	
	100/0	0.094 ±	224.833 ±	310 ± 1	7.12 ±	2.96 ±	
		0.0047	0.753		0.02	0.26	
	XG/PVA blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite composites	0/100	0.085 ±	215.500 ±	339 ± 1	6.66 ±	2.78 ±
			0.0010	1.049		0.28	0.44
10/90		0.087 ±	218.000 ±	320 ± 1	6.72 ±	2.91 ±	
		0.0008	0.632		0.28	0.26	
30/70		0.088 ±	219.167 ±	314 ± 1	6.84 ±	2.74 ±	
		0.0016	0.753		0.02	0.78	
50/50		0.090 ±	221.333 ±	310 ± 1	6.78 ±	2.86 ±	
		0.0017	1.033		0.02	0.28	
70/30		0.094 ±	224.500 ±	308 ± 1	7.14 ±	2.96 ±	
		0.0010	1.049		0.46	0.25	
90/10		0.094 ±	225.000 ±	305 ± 1	7.26 ±	2.96 ±	
		0.0009	0.894		0.23	0.26	
100/0		0.097 ±	228.333 ±	303 ± 2	7.30 ±	3.07 ±	
		0.0024	1.033		0.49	0.02	

To assess the physical stability of the thin films at humid and dry conditions percentage moisture absorbance, and percentage moisture loss were measured as per the

standard procedures. It is observed that the presence of maghemite nanoparticles improved the moisture absorption and moisture loss of the thin film. The samples showed percentage moisture absorbance in the range of 7.72 to 9.92 for XG/PVA blends, 7.12 to 7.56 for XG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites, and 6.66 to 7.30 for XG/PVA blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites

The percentage moisture loss is in the range of 4.24 to 5.17 for XG/PVA blends, and 2.96 to 3.62 for XG/PVA – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites, and 2.78 to 3.07 for XG/PVA – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites

Transdermal drug release kinetics

Figure 6.11 presents the drug release from thin films of XG, PVA, their maghemite nanocomposites, XG/PVA blends and their maghemite nanocomposites.

Figure 6.11: Drug release kinetic data for A) XG/PVA blends, B) XG/PVA blend - 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites, and C) XG/PVA blend - 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites

A

B

C

Figure 6.12: Higuchi kinetics of A) XG/PVA blends, B) XG/PVA blend - 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites, and C) XG/PVA blend - 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites

A

Figure 6.13: Koresmeyer-Peppas kinetics of A) XG/PVA blends, B) XG/PVA blend - 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites, and C) XG/PVA blend - 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites

Table 6.10: The values of diffusion exponent and intercept from Koresmeyer-Peppas plots

Composition	Koresmeyer-Peppas model		
	Intercept (k)	Diffusion exponent (n)	
XG/PVA blends	0/100	1.3866	0.22011
	10/90	1.34476	0.21854
	30/70	1.27952	0.23304
	50/50	1.18141	0.25873
	70/30	1.13415	0.26235
	90/10	1.07007	0.27631
	100/0	1.02785	0.28204
XG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites	0/100	1.2991	0.25894
	10/90	1.26397	0.24905
	30/70	1.23136	0.24041
	50/50	1.17302	0.24924
	70/30	1.11026	0.26775
	90/10	1.05795	0.27652
	100/0	0.98571	0.2971
XG/PVA blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites	0/100	1.3	0.25659
	10/90	1.25575	0.25742
	30/70	1.23231	0.24927
	50/50	1.13896	0.27731
	70/30	1.05785	0.30279
	90/10	0.97262	0.3275
	100/0	0.94004	0.32888

The diffusion study showed that the drug release from PVA was immediate compared to that of xanthan gum. The maghemite nanocomposite of PVA and xanthan gum showed sustained release when compared with their pure polymer. The metoprolol succinate drugs release from the blends and blend – maghemite nanocomposites were also in a sustained manner.

The plot of cumulative amount of drug released versus square root of time (Figure 6.12) indicated linearity and confirms the diffusion type drug release from all the system was by diffusion. From the plot, Figure 6.13, the diffusion exponent n , and constant k , were determined and are presented in Table 6.10. In all the cases, $k > 0.5$, and $n < 0.5$ and confirms that the release of drug was Fickian kinetics [221, 223].

Chapter- 7

**Conclusions
&
Scope for the Future Works**

“We have matter and force. The matter, we do not know how, disappears into force and force into matter. Therefore, there is something which is neither force nor matter, as these two may not disappear into each other. This is what we call the universal mind.”

- Swami Vivekananda

Chapter 7

CONCLUSIONS

Biocompatible polymers are the most studied polymeric materials for their applications in food packaging, and biomedical applications. Many biocompatible polymers were studied for their blending for their specific applications. Blends, alloys, and composites of these polymeric materials are used in many pharmaceutical formulations. Though natural miscibility of component polymers were exploited to get polymer blends, the addition of suitable compatibilising agents improved the miscibility-windows of polymer blends. The influence of nanoparticles on improving the properties of materials has made sufficient enhancements biomedical application. Maghemite nanoparticles are found to be biocompatible and with magnetic properties. An effort has been made to check its suitability as compatibilizer to improve the miscibility of polymer blends.

In the present investigation, the author has used solution state miscibility studies like refractive index, density, and ultrasonic sound velocity measurement techniques to identify the miscibility windows for their simplicity, low basic cost, rapidity and reliability. Further, the miscibility in solution state was confirmed by well accepted viscosity measurement technique. The miscible compositions of the studied polymer blends in solution state were analyzed for miscibility behaviour in solid state by FTIR, SEM, and DSC techniques. The present thesis contains three main topics: the miscibility of polymer blends in solution and solid state, thermal degradation behaviour, and mechanical and drug release property of biocompatible polymer blends and their maghemite nanocomposites. Controlled drug delivery technology is a multidisciplinary scientific approach as one of the frontier areas of science and contributing to human health care.

The present research aims at preparation and determining the miscibility of biologically important polymeric materials based on blends of natural, semi-synthetic, and synthetic polymers like GG/MC, GG/HPMC, XG/MC, and XG/PVA their respective maghemite nanocomposites, and developing newer polymeric networks for incorporation of drugs and investigate their physical properties and release kinetics. These investigations are presented in 7 chapters including conclusion and scope for the future works.

Chapter 1 has been divided into two sections. In the first section (*Section A*) a general introduction is given to biocompatibility, biocompatible polymers, polymer blends, miscibility of polymer blends, experimental methods to determine miscibility, applications of polymer blends, magnetic nanoparticles, iron oxide nanoparticles, superparamagnetism in magnetic nanoparticles, maghemite, properties and applications of iron oxide nanoparticles and maghemite, polymer-magnetic nanocomposites, and controlled drug delivery systems. This section concludes with detailed literature in the field of water soluble biocompatible polymer blends, polymer-iron oxide nanocomposites, and the objective and scope of the present work. *Section B* gives the detailed introduction to the materials used in the preparation of biocompatible polymer blends/composites, their chemistry and properties, and different methods & methodologies adopted for the characterization of the prepared polymer blends in solution and solid states (thin films).

Chapter 2 deals with the preparation and miscibility studies of guar gum (GG)/methylcellulose (MC) blend in the solution and solid states. 0.02 wt% maghemite nanoparticles were found suitable for the preparation of polymer/blend – composites. The refractive index, ultrasonic velocity, density, and viscosity were measured for pure GG, MC, and their blends (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10). Adiabatic compressibility was calculated using ultrasonic velocity and density data. These studies confirmed the immiscibility of GG/MC blends. With the presence of maghemite nanoparticle 10/90 GG/MC blend was found to be compatibilized. The results are confirmed with SEM and FTIR studies. The thermal and mechanical properties were analyzed by DSC, TGA, and tensile strength measurements. The miscibility of GG/MC blend for 10/90 composition with maghemite nanocomposites is due to the compatibilization by the formation of hydrogen bonds between GG and MC.

Chapter 3 presents the miscibility studies of guar gum (GG)/hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) blends in solution and solid states. The refractive index, ultrasonic velocity, density, adiabatic compressibility, and viscosity were measured for pure GG, HPMC and their blends (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10). Adiabatic compressibility was calculated using ultrasonic velocity and density data. The plot of these against blend composition showed linear and non-linear regions, indicating semi-miscibility. Reduced viscosity plots against concentration showed higher slope variation for compositions with 50% or more GG in the blend. The solid state miscibility study was done for thin films of pure GG, HPMC and their blends prepared by solution casting method. A SEM study reveals that in the GG/HPMC blend HPMC granules were well

distributed in the GG matrix, confirming a good interaction between the polymers. FTIR measurement and DSC-Tg analysis confirmed the intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions in GG/HPMC blends. Thermal and mechanical properties were reported with TGA and tensile strength measurements. 0.02 wt% maghemite nanoparticles showed compatibilising effect on GG/HPMC blends in solution and solid state, studied by density, ultrasonic velocity, adiabatic compressibility, viscosity, SEM, FTIR, DSC-Tg, TGA, and tensile strength measurement methods.

Chapter 4 reports the miscibility studies of Xanthan gum (XG)/methylcellulose (MC) blends in solution and solid states. Refractive index, ultrasonic velocity, density and adiabatic compressibility studies reveals the miscible nature of XG/MC blends in solution. It is observed from the plots of refractive index, ultrasonic velocity, density and adiabatic compressibility against % composition that 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 XG/MC blend compositions showed linearity at both 30°C and 40°C. Hence it confirms that XG/MC blend is miscible in aqueous solution when XG content is more than 50% in the blend. The viscosity plots showed linearity and higher slope variation for 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 XG/MC blend compositions attributes to the increase in hydrodynamic volume. The homogeneity and hydrogen bonding interactions in solid state is confirmed by SEM, FTIR and DSC-Tg measurement methods. Temperature characteristics and mechanical properties were studied by TGA and tensile strength measurements. The influence of maghemite nanoparticles (0.02 wt% and 0.03 wt%) on the blending of XG/MC blends were studied by density, ultrasonic velocity, and viscosity measurements. It is observed that the presence of 0.02 wt% maghemite improved the miscibility nature in solution state indicated by the linearity of the plots. Whereas, maghemite nanoparticles with 0.03 wt% does not improve the miscibility characteristics. The solid state studies were performed with SEM, FTIR, DSC-Tg, TGA, and tensile strength measurements.

Chapter 5 presents miscibility studies of xanthan gum (XG)/Poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) blends in solution and solid states. The refractive index, ultrasonic velocity and density were measured for pure XG, PVA and their blends (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10). Adiabatic compressibility was calculated using ultrasonic velocity and density data. The plot of these against blend composition showed linear regions, indicating miscibility at both 30°C and 40°C. Viscosity measurements confirmed the miscibility of XG/PVA blends. The temperature did not have any significant effect on the miscibility of XG/PVA blends. The solid state miscibility study was done for thin films of XG/PVA blends prepared by solution casting method. The SEM, FTIR, and DSC-Tg measurements proved the presence of hydrogen bonding between XG and PVA in their

blends. Temperature and mechanical characteristics were reported with TGA and tensile strength measurement studies. The influence of 0.02 wt% and 0.03 wt% maghemite nanoparticles on XG/PVA blends in solution state were also studied by density, ultrasonic velocity, adiabatic compressibility, and viscosity measurements and confirmed the compatibility. Further the blend – maghemite nanocomposites were characterized by SEM, FTIR, DSC-Tg, TGA and tensile strength measurement techniques.

Chapter 6 reports the transdermal drug release applications of GG/MC, GG/HPMC, XG/MC, and XG/PVA blends and their maghemite nanocomposites. The metoprolol model drug infused thin films (patches) of all the pure polymers and their maghemite nanocomposites, and miscible blend compositions, and compatible blend – maghemite nanocomposites were evaluated for their physicochemical properties such as thickness, weight, folding endurance, percentage moisture absorption and percentage moisture loss. These parameters are important for the applications of the patches for transdermal drug release systems. The drug release kinetics studies revealed that all the patches showed diffusion of the drug and were slow, sustained release of the drug, metoprolol succinate, and follows Fickian kinetics. Hence these biomaterials can be useful for slow, sustained release formulations for transdermal systems.

Scope for the future work

The miscibility studies in solution state and solid state, the influence of maghemite nanoparticles on the miscibility, and transdermal drug release kinetics of 4 blend systems were studied in detail in this research work. The mechanical and thermal properties were also analysed.

It was observed that maghemite - a biocompatible magnetic nanoparticle is effective in compatibilising biocompatible blend systems. Miscible and or compatibilized blend systems have potential applications in drug release formulations. Many of the biocompatible immiscible blend systems may be studied with maghemite nanoparticle's compatibilization.

A sample drug metoprolol succinate was used in the present investigation to analyse the drug release pattern and its kinetics. Many other suitable drugs with applications in transdermal drug release systems can be evaluated and implicated.

During the literature survey, it was observed that the biocompatible polymers selected for the investigation has potential applications in selective adsorption of toxic metal ions, removal of hardness of water, dye degradation, and in agricultural applications. Hence the obtained miscible blend systems and maghemite compatibilized

blend systems can be evaluated for their applications in industrial water purification such as removal of toxic metal ions and dye adsorption and degradation, and for sustained release of micro nutrients to the soil.

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APPENDIX A

**LIST OF
PUBLICATIONS**

Publication Records

- 1 Bhavya, M. S., Savitha, M. B., & Prasad, P. (2017). Miscibility studies of GG/CMC blends in aqueous solution. *International Journal of Advance Research in Science and Engineering*, 06(01), 514-523.
- 2 Prasad, P., Bhavya, M. S., Abhijith, P. P., Sreelakshmi, S. K., & Savitha, M. B. (2017). Physico-chemical and thermal property studies of GG/CMC blend thin films. *International Journal of Advance Research in Science and Engineering*, 06(06), 572-578.
- 3 Prasad, P., Bhavya, M. S., Abhijith, P. P., Sreelakshmi, S. K., & Savitha, M. B. (2017). Miscibility studies of GG/PVA blends in aqueous solution. *International Journal of Advance Research in Science and Engineering*, 06(09), 1-8.
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- 5 Bhavya, M. S., Prasad, P., & Savitha, M. B. (2018). Applications of water soluble polymers. *International Journal of Advance Research in Science and Engineering*, 07(07), 27-44.
- 6 Bhavya, M. S., Sudhanva Narayana, K. S., Savitha, M. B., & Prasad, P. (2020). Guar gum (GG)/methylcellulose (MC) blends and their composites with maghemite nanoparticles. *International Journal of Management and Humanities*, 04(09), 96-102.
- 7 Bhavya, M. S., Sudhanva Narayana, K. S., Savitha, M. B., & Prasad P. (2020). Biocompatible Maghemite Nanoparticles Compatibilization of GG/CMC Blends in Aqueous Solution. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 4(1), 184-190.
- 8 Bhavya, M. S., Athira Lakshmanan, P., Sudhanva Narayana, K. S., Savitha, M. B., & Prasad, P. (2020). Investigation on γ -Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles compatibilization on guar gum/poly (vinyl alcohol) blends. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 4(1), 219-225.
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- 10 Bhavya, M. S., Sudhanva Narayana, K. S., Prasad, P., & Savitha, M. B. (2021). Maghemite Nanoparticles Compatibilization of Guar gum/Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose Blends and Their Drug Release Kinetics. *International Journal of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology*, (Communicated).

APPENDIX B

**PUBLISHED
RESEARCH PAPERS**

MISCIBILITY STUDIES OF GG/CMC BLENDS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

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ABSTRACT

Miscibility of blends of Guar Gum (GG) and Carboxymethylcellulose (CMC) in common solvent water were studied by viscometry, ultrasonic, density, and refractometric methods at 30°C and 40°C. Based on ultrasonic velocity, density and refractive index measurements, it is found that the polymer blend of Guar Gum/CMC is miscible only when the GG content is more than 60%. Below this critical GG concentration the blends were found to be immiscible. Using the viscosity data, interaction parameters were computed and it suggests that the blend is miscible when the GG content is more than 60% of the blend. Variation of temperature did not have any significant effect on the miscibility. Hence GG/CMC blend in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C is semi-miscible in nature.

Keywords: blends, CMC, Guar Gum, miscibility, viscosity interaction parameters

I. INTRODUCTION

Depletion of petroleum based products created a lot of interests in cellulose and cellulose derivatives as a renewable resource. Alkali cellulose and carboxymethylcellulose (CMC) are the most important cellulose derivatives. Cellulose is a linear and high molecular weight polymer as well as natural, renewable, and biodegradable material. Although, due to hydrogen bonds that associated with structure of molecular cellulose, it neither melts nor dissolves readily in common solvents. But its water-soluble derivatives have found various applications. Carboxymethylcellulose is a water-soluble, highly viscous, non-toxic, biocompatible synthetic polysaccharide obtained from cellulose. It is resistant to microbial fermentation. Carboxymethylcellulose is widely used in various industries such as food, pharmaceuticals and cosmetics [1–8].

Guar gum (GG) is extremely water soluble, hydrophilic polymer, the solution of which is highly viscous nature. This property has allowed these polymers and their derivatives to be commercialized in fields such as textiles, foods, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals and oil recovery and drilling [9–23]. Guar gum has strong hydrogen bonding properties. Polymer blends of guar gum and carboxymethyl cellulose may have applications in cosmetics and pharmaceutical industries.

Guar Gum or guaran is a naturally occurring polysaccharide extracted from the endosperm of *Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*. Guar bean (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*) is a commercially important crop of India and

serves as the raw material for the industrial production of the galactomannan gum. Chemically, guar gum is a straight chain galactomannan, which is 75-85% of the endosperm, with a galactose to mannose ratio of approximately 1:2. It has a chain of (1→4)-linked-β-D-mannopyranosyl units with single α-D-galactopyranosyl units connected by (1→6) linkages to, on the average, every second main chain unit [24, 25]. The schematic representation of guar gum is given in Fig.1.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of GG

Carboxymethylcellulose or cellulose gum is a cellulose derivative with carboxymethyl groups (-CH₂-COOH) bound to some of the hydroxyl groups of the glucopyranose monomers that make up the cellulose backbone. Sodium salt of carboxymethylcellulose was produced by conversion of alkali cellulose swollen in aqueous NaOH with excess of organic solvent (e.g. isopropanol or ethanol) and monochloroacetic acid or its sodium salt. Hydroxyl groups in cellulose are usually replaced by carboxymethyl groups in the order of C6 > C2 > C3[1]. Carboxymethylcellulose is a linear, long-chain, water-soluble, anionic, highly viscous, non-toxic, non-carcinogenic, biocompatible synthetic polysaccharide. CMC is widely used in various industries such as food, pharmaceuticals and cosmetics [3, 4, 7]. The schematic representation of CMC is given in Fig.2.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of CMC

In this research work miscibility of natural polymer guar gum and a synthetic polysaccharide carboxymethylcellulose at different compositions were studied by the refractive index, density, ultrasonic velocity, and viscosity measurement techniques in their dilute solution at 30°C and 40°C.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The polymers employed in the present study are Guar Gum (Merck, India) and Carboxymethylcellulose (Merck, India). Schematic representation of Guar Gum and Carboxymethylcellulose are shown in Fig.1 and 2 respectively.

Blends of the GG / CMC of different compositions of 20/80, 40/60, 50/50, 60/40 and 80/20 were prepared. Ultrasonic velocity of GG, CMC and the blend solutions of 0.5 % (w/v) were measured at 30°C and 40°C by an interferometric technique employing an ultrasonic interferometer (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi) at frequency 2MHz. The densities and refractive index of the GG/CMC blend solutions (0.5%, w/v) were measured at 30°C and 40°C using specific gravity bottle and Abbe’s refractometer, respectively.

Stock solutions of GG and CMC were prepared (0.1% w/v). The blend stock solutions of 20/80, 40/60, 50/50, 60/40 and 80/20 were prepared by stirring the mixtures at room temperature for about 45 minutes. Using the above pure and blend stock solutions, different blend solutions of 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05, 0.06, 0.07, 0.08, 0.09 and 0.1 w/v concentrations were prepared and viscosity measurements were done at 30°C and 40°C using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer. Different temperatures were maintained using a thermostat bath with a thermal stability of ± 0.05°C.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Refractive index, ultrasonic velocity, density and adiabatic compressibility measurements

The refractive index (n), ultrasonic velocity (v), density (ρ) and adiabatic compressibility (β_{ad}) offers useful techniques for investigating the miscibility of polymer blends in solution.

The adiabatic compressibility (β_{ad}) of different blend compositions was evaluated using the equation (1)

$$\beta_{ad} = \frac{1}{v^2 \rho} \quad (1)$$

Where v is ultrasonic sound velocity and ρ is the density of blend solutions.

The plots of variation of refractive index (n), ultrasonic velocity (v), density (ρ) and adiabatic compressibility (β_{ad}) over an extended range of concentrations of GG/CMC blend solutions at 30°C and 40°C were given in Fig.s3, 4, 5, and 6, respectively.

Figure 3: Variation of refractive index with composition of GG/CMC blend in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

Figure 4: Variation of ultrasonic velocity with composition of GG/CMC blend in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

Figure 5: Variation of density with composition of GG/CMC blend in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

Figure 6: Variation of adiabatic compressibility with composition of GG/CMC blend in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

These graphs show both linear and non-linear regions, indicating the semi-miscible nature of the GG/CMC blend. It was already established that the variation is linear for miscible and non-linear for immiscible blends [26–29]. In the present investigation the variation is found to be linear when the GG content is more than 60 weight percentage at 30°C and 40°C. Below this critical concentration at both 30°C and 40°C, the variation is found to be non-linear due to phase separation. The linearity in the graph may be due to the specific interaction like hydrogen bonding between polymer segments, which will be more when the GG content is more than 60 weight percent, leading to miscibility of the blend. And below this composition there may be no much interaction between the polymer segments which leads to immiscibility of the polymer blend. Hence the present study indicates the existence of the miscibility windows only when the GG content is more than 60 weight percentage at 30°C and 40°C. Hence, the GG / CMC blend is semi-miscible in aqueous solutions.

3.2 Reduced viscosity measurements

Reduced viscosities of homo-polymers GG, CMC and their blend compositions of 20/80, 40/60, 50/50, 60/40 and 80/20 were measured at 30°C and 40°C.

Huggin's plots of reduced viscosities of the pure polymers and their blend compositions against concentrations are shown in Fig.s7 and 8 respectively.

Figure 7: Huggins's plot for 0.1% (w/v) GG/CMC blend at 30°C

Figure 8: Huggins's plot for 0.1% (w/v) GG/CMC blend at 40°C

The plots were linear. A higher slope variation for 80/20 and 60/40 GG/CMC blend compositions may be attributed to the mutual attraction of macromolecules in solution which leads to the increase of hydrodynamic volume. The 50/50, 40/60 and 20/80 GG/CMC blend compositions showed lower slope may be due to the phase separation of polymers. According to the criterion of reduced viscosity-concentration, this polymer blend should be miscible for 80/20 and 60/40 compositions and immiscible for 50/50, 40/60 and 20/80 blend compositions.

In order to quantify the miscibility of polymer blends, Chee [30] proposed a general expression to calculate interaction parameter for a ternary system containing two polymers (components 1 and 2) and a solvent (component 3),

$$\eta_{sp} = [\eta]c + bc^2 \quad (2)$$

$$b = w_1^2 b_{11} + w_2^2 b_{22} + 2 w_1 w_2 b_{12} \quad (3)$$

Where w_1 and w_2 designates the normalized weight fractions of components 1 and 2 respectively. b_{11} , b_{22} and b_{12} are the slopes of the viscosity curves for the components 1 and 2 and the blend respectively.

Chee considered that the quantity b reflects the binary interactions between polymer segments and suggested a simple measure of the intermolecular interaction

$$\Delta B = \frac{b - \bar{b}}{2w_1 w_2} \quad (4)$$

$$\bar{b} = w_1 b_{11} + w_2 b_{22} \quad (5)$$

The interaction parameter ΔB is directly proportional to the difference between the observed b and the average \bar{b} , which can be determined experimentally. If $[\eta]_1$ and $[\eta]_2$ are sufficiently far apart, the factors w_1 and w_2 expressed in terms of $[\eta]$ s as

$$\mu = \frac{\Delta B}{\{[\eta]_2 - [\eta]_1\}^2} \quad (6)$$

where $[\eta]_1$ and $[\eta]_2$ are intrinsic viscosities of pure component solutions. The polymer blend is miscible if $\mu \geq 0$ and immiscible when $\mu < 0$.

For polymer mixtures, it is found that the intrinsic viscosity of the mixture and those of the components are linearly related by

$$[\eta]_m = [\eta]_1 w_1 + [\eta]_2 w_2 \quad (7)$$

With the above weighed additive rule an expression for Huggin's coefficient K_m is given as

$$K_m = \frac{K_1 [\eta]_1^2 w_1^2 + K_2 [\eta]_2^2 w_2^2 + 2 K_{12} [\eta]_1 [\eta]_2 w_1 w_2}{\{[\eta]_1 w_1 + [\eta]_2 w_2\}^2} \quad (8)$$

In the absence of strong specific interaction forces between macromolecules which would encourage aggregation and at sufficiently low concentration Sun et al. [31] proposed a new criterion for the determination of polymer-polymer miscibility as

$$\alpha = K_m - \frac{K_1 [\eta]_1^2 w_1^2 + K_2 [\eta]_2^2 w_2^2 + 2 (K_1 K_2)^{1/2} [\eta]_1 [\eta]_2 w_1 w_2}{\{[\eta]_1 w_1 + [\eta]_2 w_2\}^2} \quad (9)$$

Where K_1 and K_2 are the Huggin's constants for components 1 and 2 respectively. The long-range hydrodynamic interactions are considered while deriving the equation. The sign of parameter α can be used to predict the miscibility of polyblends, when $\alpha \geq 0$, miscible and immiscible when $\alpha < 0$.

The computed values of interaction parameters μ and α of GG/CMC blend compositions at 30°C and 40°C are given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. It is observed from the table that the interaction parameters are negative when the GG content is up to 60% in the blend and then positive for higher proportions of GG in the blend at

both 30°C and 40°C. Hence, it confirms that the GG/CMC blend is miscible in nature when GG content in the blend is above 60 weight percentage. The temperature did not have any significant effect on the miscibility of GG/CMC blends.

Table 1: Intrinsic viscosity and interaction parameter of GG/CMC blends at 30°C

Blend composition GG/CMC	$[\eta]_{\text{exp}}$ (dL/g)	μ	α
0/100	13.84	--	--
20/80	13.75	-0.261	-0.012
40/60	13.54	-0.522	-0.012
50/50	13.33	-0.238	-0.006
60/40	12.99	0.4951	0.007
80/20	12.63	0.8214	0.011
100/0	12.42	--	--

Table 2: Intrinsic viscosity and interaction parameter of GG/CMC blends at 40°C

Blend composition GG/CMC	$[\eta]_{\text{exp}}$ (dL/g)	μ	α
0/100	12.79	--	--
20/80	12.65	-0.093	-0.013
40/60	12.45	-0.087	-0.014
50/50	12.24	-0.070	-0.007
60/40	11.90	0.593	0.009
80/20	11.52	0.8956	0.019
100/0	11.31	--	--

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on viscosity, ultrasonic velocity, density and refractive index measurements, it is found that the polymer blend of Guar Gum/CMC is miscible only when the GG content is more than 60%. Below this critical GG concentration the blends were found to be immiscible. Hence GG/CMC blend in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C is semi-miscible in nature. Variation of temperature did not have any significant effect on the miscibility. The solution state studies confirmed semi-miscibility of the blends.

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PHYSICO-CHEMICAL AND THERMAL PROPERTY STUDIES OF GG/CMC BLEND THIN FILMS

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ABSTRACT

Physico-chemical, and thermal properties of blend thin films of Guar Gum (GG) and Carboxymethylcellulose (CMC) were studied by Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), and Differential Scanning Calorimetric (DSC) methods. Based on FTIR, SEM, and DSC-Tg measurements, it is found that the polymer blend of Guar Gum/CMC is miscible by forming intermolecular hydrogen bonding only when the GG content is more than 60%. Below this critical GG concentration the blends were found to be immiscible. Hence GG/CMC blend in solid state is semi-miscible in nature.

Keywords: blends, CMC, Guar Gum, FTIR, SEM, DSC

I. INTRODUCTION

Blending is one of the most effective methods of manufacturing new polymeric materials [1, 2]. Blends can be produced that have properties independent of either the original homopolymers or structurally similar copolymerized macromolecules. However, mixing of polymers to produce novel materials is typically possible only if two compounds are miscible [3]. It is important to relate the chemical structure of polymers to their physical properties, as miscibility is often a result of physical interaction between two materials. The advantage of combining polymers within a blend is twofold. First, as the blend is completely miscible, the physical properties of the material will be dependent not only on the constituent polymers but also on their interactions [4]. As such, the material's key physical properties, such as its glass transition temperature and melting/decomposition regions, can be altered, depending on the molecular organization of the two polymers in the blend [5]. Second, the mixing of two polymers adds a second functionality with which the blend can form chemical or physical interactions. A polymer blend can act in similar manner to a mixed surfactant/polymer system, which can be used to enhance the interactions of incompatible compounds or bridge immiscible environments [6].

Guar gum is a natural biocompatible polysaccharide and obtained from the endosperm of *Cyamopsis tetragonoloba* [7]. Guar gum and its derivatives are water soluble, hydrophilic polymers, and the solutions are highly viscous in nature. These polymers and their derivatives have commercial applications in

fields such as oil recovery and drilling [8, 9], textiles [10, 11], cosmetics [12], foods [13], and pharmaceuticals [14].

Carboxymethylcellulose (CMC) is a white, non-toxic, odorless, biodegradable in nature. It is a water-soluble polymer which will dissolve in hot or cold water [15]. CMC is used for a variety of applications in various industries such as pharmaceutical, personal care, paper, oilfield, and food industries. It is used as a binding, thickening, and stabilizing agent [16, 17, 18].

In our previous work we extensively investigated about the viscosity, density, ultrasonic velocity, and refractive index of guar gum/carboxymethylcellulose blends in solution state [19]. In this research miscibility of natural polymer guar gum, a synthetic polysaccharide carboxymethylcellulose, and their blend thin films at different compositions were studied by FTIR, SEM, and DSC-Tg measurement techniques.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The polymers employed in the present study are Guar Gum (Merck, India) and Carboxymethylcellulose (Merck, India).

Thin films of the polymers and their blends were prepared by solution casting method. Separate aqueous solutions of GG and CMC were prepared. A solution of CMC was added to that of GG with constant stirring. The mixture was stirred for 45 minutes at room temperature to ensure complete mixing. The total polymer concentration was kept at 0.1% (w/v). Stock solutions of GG and CMC and their different blend compositions were then casted onto teflon-coated clean glass plate and dried in a dust free atmosphere. The dried thin films were peeled off from the glass plate and were found to be transparent.

SEM photographs were recorded using a JOEL (JSM 6380LA) analyzer. FTIR spectra were recorded using NICOLET AVATAR 530 spectrophotometer. DSC thermograms were produced with a TA Q200 Differential Scanning Calorimeter, under nitrogen environment. The first temperature cycle heated the sample to 100°C, where it remained isothermal for 15 minutes to remove the remaining water in the samples. The sample was then cooled to -10°C and immediately reheated to 250°C. The heating/cooling rate was set at 10°C/min.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Fourier transform infra red spectroscopic measurements:

FTIR spectra of GG, CMC and their blend films (80/20, 60/40 and 50/50) were recorded. Fig. 1 shows the FTIR spectra of pure and blend films in the wave length range of 4000-500 cm^{-1} . Guar gum showed the presence of a very strong and broad absorption band at 3347.3 cm^{-1} is assigned to -OH bond stretching, while the sharp absorption band located at 2918.2 cm^{-1} may be attributed to -CH group stretching. The absorption band appearing at 1628.3 cm^{-1} is due to the -OH bond belonging to water molecules. -CH₂ group bending is assigned to an absorption band located at 1370.9 cm^{-1} and the bending of -CH₂-O-CH₂- appears in the 1012.7 cm^{-1} frequency region [20]. The FTIR spectra of CMC showed a hydroxyl group (-OH stretching) at 3500 cm^{-1} , a hydrocarbon group (C-H stretching of the -CH₂ groups) at 2916.7 cm^{-1} , a carbonyl group (C=O stretching) at 1593.7 cm^{-1} , a -CH₂ scissoring around 1412 cm^{-1} and ether groups (-O- stretching) at 1026 cm^{-1} [21, 22]. It is noticed that the hydroxyl stretching bands became much broader for 80/20 and 60/40 GG/CMC blends compared to CMC. The hydroxyl and carbonyl characteristic bands for 20/80, 40/60 and 50/50 blend compositions are observed at 3336.3 cm^{-1} , 3340.4 cm^{-1} , 3348.2 cm^{-1} and 1591.5 cm^{-1} , 1592.2 cm^{-1} , 1593.5 cm^{-1}

respectively. The hydroxyl characteristic bands for 60/40 and 80/20 GG/CMC blends got shifted to lower wave length compared to GG and CMC whereas for 50/50 GG/CMC blend such observations are not found. Similarly the carbonyl characteristic bands for 60/40 and 80/20 blend compositions are shifted towards lower wave numbers compared to that of CMC. These observations confirms the formation of intermolecular hydrogen bonding between the hydroxyl groups of Guar gum and carbonyl groups of carboxymethylcellulose for 60/40 and 80/20 blend compositions. Hence, the FTIR spectroscopic measurement confirms that GG/CMC blend is miscible for higher proportions of GG in the blend and GG/CMC blend is semi-miscible in nature.

Figure 1: FTIR spectroscopy for (a) CMC, (b) 80/20 GG/CMC blend, (c) 60/40 GG/CMC blend, (d) 50/50 GG/CMC blend and (e) GG

Morphological studies:

All the solution-casted films of GG, CMC and their blends (20/80, 40/60, 50/50, 60/40 and 80/20) were transparent. To check the morphology of the blends SEM was used. The results are given in Fig. 2. GG/CMC blends show aggregated particles for 20/80, 40/60 and 50/50 GG/CMC blend compositions. For 60/40 and 80/20 GG/CMC, it can be observed that the GG granule was well distributed in the CMC matrix, confirming a good interaction between GG and CMC. From the SEM images, measured at high magnification (X 5,000), it was distinctly observed that the blend with 60/40 and 80/20 GG/CMC compositions are homogeneous. The observation suggests that GG/CMC blend is miscible only when the GG content is more than 60 weight percentage. Hence GG/CMC blend is semi-miscible in solid state.

Figure 2: Scanning electron micrographs for (a) GG, (b) 20/80 GG/CMC blend, (c) 40/60 GG/CMC blend, (d) 50/50 GG/CMC blend, (e) 60/40 GG/CMC blend, (f) 80/20 GG/CMC blend and (g) CMC

Glass transition temperature measurements:

The thermal properties of GG, CMC and their blend composition 80/20 were studied by means of DSC-Tg determination and the thermograms are given in Fig. 3. The glass transition temperature was taken as the mid-point of the change of slope in the DSC curves [23, 24, 25].

It is observed in the respective thermograms that all the blends showed single composition-dependent glass transition temperature and T_g is in between GG and that of CMC, indicating intermolecular interaction between the polymers [26].

Figure 3: DSC traces of (a) GG, (b) 80/20 GG/CMC blend and (c) CMC

The T_g of miscible blend can be calculated using Fox Equation (1) [27], or Wood’s Equation (2) [28], or Pochan’s Equation (3) [29].

$$1/T_g = w_1/T_{g1} + w_2/T_{g2} \tag{1}$$

$$T_g = w_1 T_{g1} + w_2 T_{g2} \tag{2}$$

$$\ln T_g = w_1 \ln T_{g1} + w_2 \ln T_{g2} \tag{3}$$

where w₁, w₂, T_{g,1} and T_{g,2} are the weight fractions and glass transition temperatures of the corresponding polymer 1 and polymer 2 respectively.

The experimental T_g values compared with theoretical T_g values and are summarized in Table 1. Experimental T_g values for 80/20 GG/CMC blend is in good agreement with the theoretically calculated T_g values indicating an intermolecular interactions of hydrogen bonding type between the polymers [26, 30, 31, 32].

Table 1: Experimental and theoretical glass transition temperature (T_g) of GG/CMC blends

Blend comp. GG/CMC	Experimental T _g values (°C)	Theoretical T _g values (°C)		
		Fox equation	Wood equation	Pochan’s equation
0/100	57.8	--	--	--
40/60	53.13	51.63	52.48	52.06
100/0	44.5	--	--	--

VI. CONCLUSION

Guar Gum/Carboxymethylcellulose blend thin films were prepared by solution casting method using distilled water as common solvent. The studies confirm that the polymer blend of Guar Gum/CMC is miscible only when the GG content is more than 60%. Below this critical GG concentration the blends were found to be immiscible. Homogeneity of miscible compositions of GG/CMC blends and specific intermolecular interactions of hydrogen bonding type were investigated by SEM, FTIR, and DSC analysis.

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MISCIBILITY STUDIES OF GG/PVA BLENDS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

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ABSTRACT

Miscibility of blends of Guar Gum (GG) and Poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) in common solvent water were studied by viscometry, ultrasonic, density, and refractometric methods at 30°C and 40°C. Based on ultrasonic velocity, density and refractive index measurements, it is found that the polymer blend of GG/PVA is miscible only when the GG content is more than 60%. Below this critical GG concentration the blends were found to be immiscible. Using the viscosity data, interaction parameters were computed and it suggests that the blend is miscible when the GG content is more than 60% of the blend. Variation of temperature did not have any significant effect on the miscibility. Hence GG/PVA blend in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C is semi-miscible in nature.

Keywords: blends, PVA, Guar Gum, miscibility, viscosity interaction parameters.

I. INTRODUCTION

The blend materials from either synthetic or natural polymers alone are not always able to meet all the complex demands of the biomaterials [1 – 4]. The success of synthetic polymers as biomaterials relies on their wide range of mechanical properties, transformation processes that allow a variety of different shapes to be easily obtained and at low production cost. Biological polymers present good biocompatibility, but their mechanical properties are often poor [5 – 9]. The necessity of preserving biological properties complicates their processability and their production or recovery costs are very high. Therefore, biologically important polymeric materials based on the blends of synthetic and natural polymers have been prepared, such as GG/CMC [10, 11], PVP/Lignin [53], poly (ethylene oxide)/sodium alginate [58], poly (ethylene oxide)/keratin [12], PVA/starch [13], poly (ethylene oxide)/starch [14], Xanthan gum/PEO [15].

Guar gum is water soluble, hydrophilic polymer obtained from guar bean (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*), a commercially important crop of India. It's a natural biocompatible polysaccharide and has important applications in cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries [10]. Poly (vinyl alcohol) is recognized as a biodegradable polymer, and its biodegradation in various microbial environments has been reported by several researchers [16 – 22]. PVA has been widely used in biomedical industries [23 – 25].

In this research work, miscibility of natural polymer guar gum and a synthetic polymer poly (vinyl alcohol) at different compositions were studied by refractive index, density, ultrasonic velocity and viscosity measurement techniques in their dilute solution at 30°C and 40°C

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The polymers employed in the present study are guar gum (Merck, India) and PVA (Rohm, India).

Blends of GG/PVA of different compositions were prepared by mixing aqueous polymer solutions. Ultrasonic velocity of the blend solutions of 0.1 % (w/v) were measured at 30°C and 40°C by an interferometric technique employing an ultrasonic interferometer (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi) at frequency 2MHz. The densities and refractive index of the GG/PVA blend solutions (0.1%, w/v) were measured at 30°C and 40°C using specific gravity bottle and Abbe's refractometer, respectively.

Stock solutions of GG, PVA, and their blends (20/80, 40/60, 50/50, 60/40, and 80/20) were prepared (0.1% w/v) by stirring the mixtures at room temperature for about 45 minutes. Using the above pure and blend stock solutions, different blend solutions (0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05, 0.06, 0.07, 0.08, 0.09, and 0.1 w/v concentrations) were prepared and viscosity measurements were done at 30°C and 40°C using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer. Different temperatures were maintained using a thermostat bath with a thermal stability of $\pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Refractive index, ultrasonic velocity, density and adiabatic compressibility measurements

The plots of variation of refractive index (n), ultrasonic velocity (v), density (ρ) and adiabatic compressibility (β_{ad}) over an extended range of concentrations of GG/PVA blend solutions at 30°C and 40°C were given in Figs.1, 2, 3, and 4, respectively.

These graphs show both linear and non-linear regions indicating the semi-miscible nature of the GG/PVA blend. It was already established that the variation is linear for miscible and non-linear for immiscible blends [1 - 4]. In the present investigation the variation is found to be linear only when the GG content is more than 60 wt% at 30°C and 40°C. The linearity in the graph may be due to the specific interaction like hydrogen bonding between the polymer segments, which is more when the GG content is more than 60 wt%, leading to miscibility of these blends [8, 9]. Below this composition there may not be much interaction between the polymer segments which leads to immiscibility of the blend. Hence the present study indicates the existence of the miscibility window only when the GG content is more than 60 wt% at 30°C and 40°C. Hence GG/PVA blend is semi-miscible in aqueous solution.

Figure 1: Variation of refractive index with composition of GG/PVA blend in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

Figure 2: Variation of ultrasonic velocity with composition of GG/PVA blend in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

Figure 3: Variation of density with composition of GG/PVA blend in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

Figure 4: Variation of adiabatic compressibility with composition of GG/PVA blend in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

3.2 Reduced viscosity measurements

Reduced viscosities of homo-polymers GG, PVA, and their blend compositions (20/80, 40/60, 50/50, 60/40, and 80/20) were measured at 30°C and 40°C. Huggin’s plots of reduced viscosities of the pure polymers and their blend compositions against concentrations are shown in Figs.5, and 6, respectively.

Figure 5: Huggin’s plot for 0.1% (w/v) GG/PVA blend at 30°C

Figure 6: Huggin’s plot for 0.1% (w/v) GG/PVA blend at 40°C

The plots were linear. A higher slope variation for 80/20 GG/PVA blend compositions may be attributed to the mutual attraction of macromolecules in solution which leads to the increase of hydrodynamic volume [5, 6, 10]. The intercept of reduced viscosity versus concentration plots gives the intrinsic viscosity of the corresponding polymer and their blend, and the computed values of Chee’s [26] interaction parameters μ , and Sun et al.’s [27] interaction parameters α of GG/PVA blend compositions at 30°C and 40°C are which are presented in Tables 1, and 2, respectively.

It is observed from the table that the μ values are negative when the GG content is up to 50% in the blend and then positive beyond this value at 30°C and 40°C. However, a values are found to be positive for the 80/20 blend compositions of GG/PVA at both temperatures and negative for the remaining compositions. The secondary interactions are taken into account in computing α values [10]. Hence, it confirms that the GG/PVA blend is miscible only when the GG content in the blend is more than 60 wt% at 30°C and 40°C. The temperature did not have any significant effect on the miscibility of GG/PVA blends.

Table 1: Intrinsic viscosity and interaction parameter of GG/PVA blends at 30°C

Blend Composition (GG/PVA)	$[\eta]_{\text{exp}}$ (dL/g)	μ	α
0/100	2.114	-	-
20/80	3.048	- 0.4999	- 0.0904
40/60	6.409	- 0.3785	- 0.2735
50/50	7.182	- 0.1389	- 0.1238
60/40	7.778	0.2342	- 0.0162
80/20	10.33	0.7772	0.0095
100/0	12.422	-	-

Table 2: Intrinsic viscosity and interaction parameter of GG/PVA blends at 40°C

Blend Comp. GG/PVA	$[\eta]_{\text{exp}}$ (dL/g)	μ	α
0/100	1.631	-	-
20/80	3.241	- 0.5097	- 0.0491
40/60	4.465	- 0.3961	- 0.1655
50/50	5.784	- 0.2833	- 0.2229
60/40	6.579	0.1501	- 0.0335
80/20	7.456	0.9206	0.0357
100/0	11.313	-	-

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on viscosity, ultrasonic velocity, density and refractive index measurements, it is found that the polymer blend of GG/PVA is miscible when the GG content is more than 60%. Below this critical GG concentration the

blends were found to be immiscible. Hence GG/PVA blend in aqueous solution is semi-miscible in nature at 30°C and 40°C. Variation of temperature did not have any significant effect on the miscibility.

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PHYSICO-CHEMICAL AND THERMAL PROPERTY STUDIES OF GG/PVA BLEND THIN FILMS

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ABSTRACT

Physico-chemical, and thermal properties of blend thin films of Guar Gum (GG) and poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) were studied by Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), and Differential Scanning Calorimetric (DSC) methods. Based on FTIR, SEM, and DSC-Tg measurements, it is found that the polymer blend of Guar Gum/PVA is miscible by forming intermolecular hydrogen bonding only when the GG content is more than 60%. Below this critical GG concentration the blends were found to be immiscible. Hence GG/PVA blend in solid state is semi-miscible in nature.

Keywords: blends, PVA, Guar Gum, FTIR, SEM, DSC.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years polymer blends have gained considerable attention due to their cost effectiveness and the relative ease with which new tailor-made materials can be produced to meet specific applications. Blending polymers may result in reducing their basic cost, improving their processing and maximizing their important properties. The gain in properties of the blends depends on the degree of miscibility of polymers at molecular level [1-7]. The miscibility of polymer blends is directly reflected by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Fourier Transform Infra Red spectroscopic (FTIR) and Differential Scanning Calorimetric (DSC) analysis [8-11].

In our previous work we extensively investigated about the viscosity, density, ultrasonic velocity, and refractive index of guar gum/PVA blends in solution state [12]. In this research miscibility of natural polymer guar gum, a synthetic polymer poly(vinyl alcohol), and their blend thin films at different compositions were studied by FTIR, SEM, and DSC-Tg measurement techniques.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The polymers employed in the present study are guar gum (Merck, India) and PVA (Rohm and Haas, India).

Blends of GG/PVA of different compositions were prepared by mixing aqueous polymer solutions. Thin films of the polymers and their blends were prepared by solution casting method. Separate aqueous solutions of GG and PVA were prepared. A solution of PVA was added to that of GG with constant stirring. The mixture was stirred for 45 minutes at room temperature to ensure complete mixing. The total polymer concentration was kept at 0.1% (w/v). Stock solutions of GG and PVA and their different blend compositions were then casted onto Teflon-coated clean glass plate and dried in a dust free atmosphere. The dried thin films were peeled off from the glass plate and were found to be transparent. Scanning electron microscopic analysis were recorded using a JOEL (JSM 6380LA) analyzer. DSC thermograms were produced with a TA Q200 differential scanning calorimeter, under nitrogen environment. The first temperature cycle heated the sample to 100°C, where it remained isothermal for between 15 and 60 min to remove the remaining water in the samples. The sample was then cooled to -10°C before it was immediately reheated to 250°C. The heating/cooling rate was set at 10°C/min.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Fourier transform infra-red spectroscopic measurements:

FTIR spectra of GG, PVA and their blend films (50/50, 60/40 and 80/20) were recorded. Figure 1 shows the FTIR spectra of pure and blend films in the wave length range of 4000-500 cm^{-1} . The FTIR spectra of GG showed the presence of a very strong and broad absorption band at 3347.3 cm^{-1} is assigned to -OH bond stretching, while the sharp absorption band located at 2918.2 cm^{-1} may be attributed to C-H group stretching. The absorption band appearing at 1628.3 cm^{-1} is due the -OH bond belonging to water molecules. CH₂ group bending is assigned to an absorption band located at 1370.9 cm^{-1} , and the bending of CH₂-O-CH₂ appears in the 1012.7 cm^{-1} frequency region [13]. The FTIR spectra of PVA showed a broad peak at 3275.3 cm^{-1} indicating stretching of hydroxyl groups and peak at 2919.2 cm^{-1} due to C-H stretching [14].

It is noticed that the hydroxyl stretching bands became much broader with increasing PVA content. The carbonyl and hydroxyl characteristic bands shifted towards lower wave numbers compared to that of pure GG. This strongly supports the idea that a hydrogen bonding can form between the hydroxyl groups of PVA and carbonyl groups of GG.

Morphological studies:

All the solution-casted films of GG, PVA and their blends (50/50, 60/40 and 80/20) were transparent. To check the morphology of the blends SEM was used. The results are given in Figure 2. GG/PVA blends show aggregated particles for 60/40 and 50/50 GG/PVA blend compositions. For 80/20 GG/PVA, it can be observed that the PVA granule was well distributed in the GG matrix, confirming a good interaction between GG and PVA. As shown in figure, measured by high magnification (X5,000), it was observed distinctly that the blend

with 80/20 GG/PVA composition is homogeneous. The observation suggests that GG/PVA blend is miscible only when the GG content is more than 80 wt%. Hence GG/PVA blend is semi-miscible.

Glass transition temperature measurements:

The thermal properties of GG, PVA and their blend composition 80/20 were studied by means of DSC-Tg determination and the thermograms are given in Figure 3. The glass transition temperature was taken as the mid-point of the change of slope in the DSC curves. As it is observed in the respective traces all the blends showed single composition-dependent glass transition temperatures T_g between the Pure GG and that of the pure PVA, indicating intermolecular interaction between the polymers. The experimental T_g values compared with theoretical T_g values [15-17] and are summarized in Table 1. Experimental T_g values for 80/20 GG/PVA blend is in good agreement with the theoretically calculated T_g values indicating an intermolecular interactions of hydrogen bonding type between the polymers [8].

Figure 1: FTIR Spectroscopy for a) GG, b) 80/20 GG/PVA blend, c) 60/40 GG/PVA blend, d) 50/50 GG/PVA blend and e) PVA

Figure 2: Scanning electron micrographs for (a) GG, (b) PVA, (c) 50/50 GG/PVA blend, (d) 60/40 GG/PVA blend and (e) 80/20 GG/PVA blend

Figure 3: DSC traces of (a) GG, (b) 80/20 GG/PVA blend and (c) PVA

Table 1: Experimental and theoretical glass transition temperature (Tg) of GG/PVA blends

Blend comp. GG/PVA	Experimental Tg values (°C)	Theoretical Tg values (°C)		
		Fox equation	Wood equation	Pochan's equation
0/100	44.5	-	-	-
80/20	49.2	47.89	49.36	48.55
100/0	68.8	-	-	-

IV. CONCLUSION

Guar Gum/PVA blend thin films were prepared by solution casting method using distilled water as common solvent. The studies confirm that the polymer blend of Guar Gum/PVA is miscible only when the GG content is more than 60%. Below this critical GG concentration the blends were found to be immiscible. Homogeneity of miscible compositions of GG/PVA blends and specific intermolecular interactions of hydrogen bonding type were investigated by SEM, FTIR, and DSC analysis.

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APPLICATIONS OF WATER SOLUBLE POLYMER BLENDS

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ABSTRACT

Polymer science is one of the most active and promising branches of science covering a multitude of topics from natural polymers to synthetic high polymers. The tremendous development in this area was responsible for the production of synthetic films, fibres, elastomers, plastics, nano-polymers, inorganic polymers, etc. Polymers have replaced metals and wood in light weight structural materials in automotive parts, electronic goods, and building materials and breakthroughs in contemporary medicine and surgery were possible only through the availability of man-made polymers. Some polymers are obtained from natural resources and then chemically modified for various applications, while others are chemically synthesized and used. Water soluble polymers due to their blood compatibility, non-toxic, non-immunogenic, non-mutagenic and non-carcinogenic nature finds applications in pharmaceutical, cosmetic, food, agricultural, and biomedical fields. In the present paper, the applications of only water soluble polymers and their blends are described.

Keywords: *Guar Gum, Miscibility, Polymer blends, Water soluble polymers, Xanthan Gum.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Polymer science is one of the most active and promising branches of science covering a multitude of topics from natural polymers to synthetic high polymers. There is no product so widely used in every sphere of life like polymeric materials designated as resins, resinous materials, plastics and elastomers. They were found to have many physico-chemical properties different from those of common low molecular weight compounds. With the establishment of the fact that the polymers are constituted of macromolecules, the chemistry of macromolecules advanced at rapid stride and the tremendous development in this area was responsible for the production of synthetic films, fibres, elastomers, plastics, nano-polymers, inorganic polymers, etc. Polymers have replaced metals and wood in light weight structural materials in automotive parts, electronic goods, and building materials and breakthroughs in contemporary medicine and surgery were possible only through the availability of man-made polymers.

Research works in Polymer Blends, Polymer Colloids, Polyelectrolytes, Electroluminescent Polymers, Thermoplastic Elastomers, Liquid Crystalline Polymers, Biomedical Polymers, Polymer Microgels, Polymer

Composites, Inter Penetrating Networks, Conducting Polymers, etc has introduced specialty polymers which have tremendous applications in all the fields of biomedical and engineering.

A literature survey has been done in the field of miscibility of polymer blends/water soluble polymers/applications of water soluble polymers/blends from Chemical Abstracts available in the library of Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, India, in order to get a an idea about the different techniques already used and to have a comparative analysis. Till the end of the work the literature survey was continued wherever and whenever it was possible/necessary by utilizing the library facilities of Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, India, University of Mysore, Mysore, India, National Institute of Technology, Mangalore, India, and Mangalore University, Mangalore, India. The authors also used the internet facility to collect research papers in this field of study. The following are some of the references relating to the field of research the authors came across during the survey.

II. WATER SOLUBLE POLYMERS

Water soluble polymers have a wide range of industrial applications like food, pharmaceuticals, paint, textiles, paper, constructions, adhesives, coatings, water treatment, etc. In this paper, the water soluble polymers have been divided into two categories: synthetic and natural. Some of the examples for synthetic water soluble polymers includes: Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) [1], Polyacrylamides [2], Poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) [3, 4], Polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP) [5-7], Polyacrylic acid (PAA) [8, 9], Polyphosphazenes [10, 11], N-(2-Hydroxypropyl) methacrylamide (HPMA) [12], Polyphosphates [13,14], Polyoxazoline [15, 16], and Divinyl Ether-Maleic Anhydride (DIVEMA) [17, 18]. Examples for natural water soluble polymers includes: Guar Gum [19-22], Xanthan Gum [23, 24], Pectins [25, 26], Starch or Starch Based Derivatives [27-32], Cellulose Ethers (Hydroxypropylmethyl cellulose (HPMC), Hydroxypropyl cellulose (HPC), Hydroxyethyl cellulose (HEC), Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose (Na-CMC)) [33-39], Chitosan Derivatives [40-45], Dextran [46-48], Albumin [49-51], and Carrageenan [52, 53].

III. POLYMER BLENDS

Now a days, polymers are playing an increasingly significant role in all branches of industry. Recent advances in science and technology are exploiting the versatile properties offered by new polymeric materials. With the advancement of civilization, man is always looking for a new material to meet the specific needs and challenges. The new materials should provide better properties and method of preparations should be available at affordable cost. In search of new polymeric materials, either new monomers are polymerized or copolymerization technique is used to get polymers with tailor-made properties. The extensive use of polymeric materials in technology and pharmaceutical application lead to the development of polymer blends.

Polymer blends, also known as polyblends are mixtures of structurally different homo-polymers, co-polymers or ter-polymers, which interact through secondary forces such as hydrogen bond, dipole-dipole forces, etc. and with no covalent bonding. Polymer blends have received much attention since blending is simple and effective approach to develop new materials, exhibiting combinations of properties that cannot be obtained by

individual polymers. The polymer blending may result in the reduction of basic cost, enhancement of performance and improved processability [54].

Blending is one of the most effective methods of manufacturing new polymeric materials. Blends can be produced that have properties independent of either the original homopolymers or structurally similar copolymerized macromolecules. However, mixing of polymers to produce novel materials is typically possible only if two compounds are miscible. It is important to relate the chemical structure of polymers to their physical properties, as miscibility is often a result of physical interaction between two materials. The advantage of combining polymers within a blend is twofold. First, as the blend is completely miscible, the physical properties of the material will be dependent not only on the constituent polymers but also on their interactions. As such, the material's key physical properties, such as its glass transition temperature and melting/decomposition regions, can be altered, depending on the molecular organization of the two polymers in the blend [55]. Second, the mixing of two polymers adds a second functionality with which the blend can form chemical or physical interactions. A polymer blend can act in similar manner to a mixed surfactant/polymer system, which can be used to enhance the interactions of incompatible compounds or bridge immiscible environments [56].

III. CLASSIFICATION OF POLYMER BLENDS

Based on the method of preparation, polymer blends are classified in to five groups as follows [57]: (i) Mechanical polymer blends, (ii) Mechano-chemical polymer blends, (iii) Chemical polymer blends, (iv) Latex polymer blends, and (v) Solution-cast polymer blends.

IV. POLYMER ALLOYS

Polymer alloys are a class of polymer blends in which a large interpenetration of domain is secured by either chemical or physical means. Blends are a direct result of the blending action and alloys are the final blends of well-defined morphology and have a set of properties. Utracki [57] clearly mentioned the interrelations in polymer blend nomenclature. These are presented in Fig. 1. From the figure, it is clearly evident that the immiscible polymer blends which are compatibilized results in a polymer alloy.

Figure 1: Interrelation in polymer blend nomenclature

V. MISCIBILITY OF POLYMER BLENDS

Polymer blends often exhibit properties that are superior to those of any one of the component polymers. However, the manifestation of superior properties depends upon the miscibility of polymers [58]. The term 'miscibility' refers to the formation of a homogeneous system at a molecular level. Depending upon the degree of molecular mixing the blends may be categorized as miscible polymer blends, semi-miscible polymer blends and immiscible polymer blends.

The state of immiscibility of a polymer blend does not preclude its utility, multiphase polymer blends also have made respectable inroads into the polymer market. Because of their specific advantages, multiphase polymer blends have extensive utility in applications requiring improved physical and mechanical properties. The best method of enhancing the miscibility of polymer blends is to introduce specific interactions. The potentially useful specific interactions are random dipole, induced dipole, dipole-dipole, ion-dipole, hydrogen bonding, acid-base and charge transfer interactions [57, 58].

VI. THERMODYNAMIC APPROACH TO MISCIBILITY OF POLYMER BLENDS

Polymer-polymer miscibility is determined by a delicate balance of enthalpic and entropic contributions to the free energy of mixing [59]. The change in free energy (ΔG) of the mixing is given by the equation $\Delta G_{\text{mix}} = \Delta H_{\text{mix}} - T\Delta S_{\text{mix}}$ where ΔH is change in enthalpy, ΔS is change in entropy and T is the absolute temperature. The unique factor affecting the thermodynamics of polymer blends compared with other low molecular weight systems is the large molecular weights of both the components. For spontaneous mixing ΔG_{mix} must be negative so that $\Delta H_{\text{mix}} - T\Delta S_{\text{mix}} < 0$. This implies that exothermic mixtures ($\Delta H_{\text{mix}} < 0$) will mix spontaneously. Whereas, for endothermic mixtures, miscibility will occur at higher temperatures. Since usually the enthalpy of mixing (ΔH_{mix}) is positive or close to zero and very small entropy of mixing (ΔS_{mix}) associated with the polymer mixtures, free energy of mixing becomes positive. Hence, most polymer blends are immiscible in nature.

VII. FACTORS INFLUENCING MISCIBILITY OF POLYMER BLENDS

The most common interactions that are involved in blends and enhance miscibility are hydrogen bonding, charge transfer complexes, ionic and dipole interactions. All these contribute to the negative enthalpy of mixing. As a result, it may be possible to select two polymers having chemical moieties within or attached to the chain which have the proper complimentary dissimilarity to yield an exothermic heat of mixing, although it should be recognized that there will still be an endothermic contribution from the dispersive interaction or Van der Waal forces between the remaining parts of the structure that do not interact specifically [60]. There are two types of miscible polymer blends: (i) miscible polymer blends having weak or little interactions and (ii) miscible polymer blends having strong specific interactions [61]. However, in the literature [62, 63] there is confusion about the definitions of "weak interactions" and "strong interactions." Since it is well established from the thermodynamic point of view that miscible polymer blends have "negative" values of Flory-Huggins interaction parameter (χ), but some investigators treated miscible polymer blends with $|\chi| \leq 0.001$ as having "weak

interactions” and miscible polymer blends with $|\chi| \geq 0.01$ are having “strong interaction” [64]. However, such a definition is somewhat arbitrary. Further, χ may not be an appropriate parameter that can define whether a miscible polymer blend has weak or strong interactions. It is more appropriate to describe whether a miscible polymer blend has weak or strong interactions in terms of intermolecular forces. Table 1 gives a summary of bond energy and relative strength of different intermolecular forces. Miscible polymer blends with Van der Waals interaction have “weak interactions” and miscible polymer blends with other types of interactions have “strong interactions” [65].

Table 1: Bond energy and relative strength of different intermolecular forces

Type of interaction	Bond energy (kJ/mol)	Relative strength
Ionic attraction	850 – 1700	1000
Hydrogen bonding	50 – 170	100
Dipole-dipole interaction	2 – 8	10
Van der Waals interaction	≈ 1	1

The majority of the known polymeric mixtures are immiscible, however, many miscible polymer blends were prepared in the last three decades. The behaviour of polymers in the mixture does not necessarily be the same as that of the isolated polymers. Methods must be found to determine the function of each polymer in its new environment and to answer questions concerning the separation of the phase, the identification of the predominant phase, the character of dispersed phase, and the interaction between the polymers. It is also reported that materials with close solubility parameters are readily miscible with each other [66]. Most of the polymer blends are heterogeneous, but these blends appear homogeneous when suitable compatibilizers are added to them.

VIII. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS TO DETERMINE THE MISCIBILITY OF POLYMER BLENDS

There are many different experimental methods that can be used to investigate the miscibility of polymer blends [67-71], such as Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA), dielectric measurement, cloud point measurement, Small-Angle Neutron Scattering (SANS), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Fourier Transform Infra Red Spectroscopy (FTIR), Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (NMR), etc.

Singh et al. [62, 72] and Gupta et al. [73] made an ultrasonic and viscometric investigation to study the miscibility of polymers. Kulashreshtha [74] used viscometric technique for the determination of compatibility. Hani Younes and Daniel Cohn [75] have conducted DSC and IR studies on the morphology of polyethylene glycol/polylactic acid blends. Masson and Manlen [76] made a wide angle X-ray scattering (WAXS), FTIR, DSC, DMA and solid state magic-angle spinning (CP-MAS) NMR investigation on the cellulose and polyvinyl pyrrolidone blend and reported that the blend is miscible. Hourston and Schafer [77] studied the morphology, phase continuity, and mechanical properties of polyether urethane/polyethyl methacrylate. Hourstone et al. [77, 78] used modulated-DSC for the thermal characterization of multi component polymers and inter phases.

Chee [79] described a method for the study of polymer-polymer miscibility by viscometry. As per his method the polymer blend will be miscible if the interaction parameter $\mu \geq 0$ and immiscible if $\mu < 0$. Sun et al. [80] gave a new equation for the determination of interaction parameter of polymer blends in solution by viscometric method. As per their theory, the polymer blend is miscible when the interaction parameter $\alpha \geq 0$ and immiscible if $\alpha < 0$. They further stated that α gives more reliable information when compared to μ because long term interactions such as hydrodynamic attractions or repulsion terms are taken into account in the determination of the expression for μ . Corradini et al. [81] probed the miscibility of PVC/EVA hydrolyzed blends by viscometric, microscopic, and thermal analysis and reported that the blend is miscible. They further reported that all these methods gave identical results.

Mihir Sheth et al. [82] carried out DSC and DMA analysis on biodegradable polymer blends of PLA and PEG and concluded that the PLA/PEG blend ranges from miscible to partially miscible, depending on the concentration. Pingping [83] gave a new criterion of polymer –polymer miscibility detected by viscometry and further reported that the new criterion is reasonable and polymer –polymer miscibility could be determined by viscosity. Katime et al. [84] studied the behaviour of PMMA in the PVC/THF binary mixture by viscometry and laser light scattering. Their results showed that compatibility of this blend depends not only on the molar masses of the samples but also on the concentration of the PVC.

Varada Rajulu et al. [85, 86] made an ultrasonic, viscometric, refractometric, density investigation on PVC/PS, PVC/cellulose acetate and cellulose acetate/PMMA blend systems in which these blend combinations were incompatible in nature and PVC/PMMA in cyclohexanone was found to be compatible. C. K. Yeom et al. [87] characterized the sodium alginate (NaAlg) and PVA blend membranes in pervaporation separation by SEM. He et al. [88] developed methods of microscopic observation and macroscopic characterization for determining the co-phase contained in immiscible binary blends. Chen et al. [89] used viscometry method for the miscibility studies of PEO/PVAc blends. Chattopadhyay and Banerjee [90] used visible spectroscopy, polarizing microscope, and FTIR techniques to study the miscibility of polymer blends. Mohamed and Sabaa [91] studied the miscibility and the thermal degradation behaviour of PVC/Poly (vinyl butyral) blend using DSC, TGA and tensile testing methods and reported the blend to be miscible. Elberaich et al. [92] confirmed the miscible nature of PEO/PMMA blend by using optical microscopy and DSC techniques.

Homogeneous mixing at molecular level is a prerequisite for polymer miscibility. Blending of the polymers in solution ensures effective attainment of equilibrium between different polymer components in solution. This method employs dilute solution viscometry. A large number of investigations have been carried out on the miscibility of polymer blends using viscosity measurements corresponding to the ternary system (polymer1/polymer2/solvent) [67, 74, 93, 94].

Additional advantages of dilute solution viscometry is that no sophisticated equipment is necessary and the crystallinity or the morphological state of polymer blends do not affect the results, making the viscometric method more convenient and handy for characterizing polymer mixtures. Recently many simple and rapid solution techniques have been used for probing the miscibility of polymer blends in solution [85, 95-98]. These techniques include the measurement of refractive index, ultrasonic velocity and density of the polymer blends in solution.

IX. APPLICATIONS OF POLYMER BLENDS

The development of polymer blend/alloy system requires a sound scientific basis and offers opportunity for many interesting polymer mixtures for commercial exploitation. The key to blending is economic viability. As raw material cost constitute 35% to 80% of that of the finished article, the future of polymer blends lies in their attractive cost/performance ratio. An expensive polymer whose property spectrum is high, needed for a new application may be blended with an inexpensive polymer whose property spectrum is such that the resulting polymer blend has a cost to performance ratio that makes it very attractive for the given application. Thus, the standard of performance demanded by the new application is satisfied by a mixture of commercially available polymers without the need to develop a new polymer or to invest in a new plant.

The primary advantages in employing polymer blends or alloy are higher performance at a reasonable price, modification of performance as market develops, extending the performance of expensive resins, re-use of plastic scrap, generation of a unique material as far as its processability and/or performance are concerned. Now a days the release profile of a drug formulation are controlled through the use of biocompatible polymer blends [99, 100].

Generally, blending technology rests on the premise of property additivity [58], although the additivity principle is not strictly valid for most polymer blends. Wherever additivity properties are valid, one can prepare tailor-made materials by selecting the appropriate quantity of the components in the polymer blends. Multiphase polymer blends (immiscible polymer blends) have assumed greater commercial importance than miscible polymer blends [101]. Because of the success of these commercial polymer blends, attempts are being made to modify the mechanical response of normally immiscible polymer blends by adding the agents that could guarantee good stress transfer between the components of the multi component multiphase polymer blends.

X. WATER SOLUBLE POLYMERS

Importance of water soluble polymers

The work on water soluble polymers is the most fascinating and hence more advanced studies on their properties and biomedical applicability are in progress where the advantage of water as a solvent can be employed. Water soluble resins are used in almost every branch of industry [102]. However water soluble polymers are not the most glamorous of polymers. They are not in the public eye as are the more exotic polymeric products, such as nose cones for missiles, nylon for paint brushes, poly (vinyl chloride) for cosmetic jars and bottles, cables and pipes and polystyrene handles for toothbrush. Yet these water soluble polymers perform essential functions in biomedical/biological systems, latex paints, adhesives, cosmetics and foods. This lack of public awareness however does not change the fact that water soluble polymer business represents a sizeable and steadily growing segment of the industry. It has been found that the total world production of water soluble polymers is more than five million tons/year, of this, some 80 – 90% is carbohydrate based (including starch and natural gums) with an additional 3 lakhs tons/year of cellulose ethers, about 1 lakh tons/year of proteins, the remaining being synthetic

polymers, the most important of which are poly (vinyl alcohol) and polyacrylamides. Water soluble polymers are therefore of considerable economic importance, and the industries, in which they are used, including pharmaceutical, paper coating, textile sizing, detergent production, water treatment and oil-well drilling, have a significant effect on our daily life [102, 103].

Classification of water soluble polymers

The water soluble polymers are most important from both scientific and technological aspects. Water soluble polymers are classified according to their origin into three main types as follows [104]: (i) Natural products (biopolymers), (ii) Modified natural products (semi-synthetic water soluble polymers), and (iii) Synthetic water soluble polymers. Biopolymers are defined as polymers formed under natural conditions during the growth cycles of all organisms. Natural products or biopolymers are derived from animal and vegetable sources and have been marketed for many years. They are formed within cells by complex metabolic processes. They represent by far the largest volume of sales in the water soluble polymer area. For materials applications, cellulose and starch are most interesting. However, there is an increasing attention in more complex hydrocarbon polymers produced by bacteria and fungi, particularly in polysaccharides such as Xanthan gum, Guar gum, curdlan, Pullulan, etc. Modified natural products or semi-synthetic water soluble polymers are the compounds produced by altering the chemical structure of biopolymers. This class of polymers is represented by the alkyl and hydroxyalkyl ethers of cellulose and starch, ionic starches – starch sulphates, sulphonates and carboxylates – carboxymethylcellulose and the mixed ethers of starch and cellulose. Synthetic water soluble polymers are the latest members of the water soluble polymer family. Some of the examples are poly (vinyl alcohol), poly (vinyl pyrrolidone), and poly (vinyl methyl ethers), polyacrylic acids and its salts, polyacrylamides, ethylene oxide polymers and various copolymer systems.

Applications of water soluble polymers/blends

The semi-synthetic and synthetic water soluble polymer market is growing at a higher rate because they are not only displacing biopolymers in many applications, but are also creating entirely new end-use areas. Even though higher priced, they are replacing natural products because of greater efficiency (much lower dosages are needed to do a given job), increased versatility (they can be tailored to serve better in a given need) and lower biological oxygen demand (important where stream pollution is in a critical consideration) [102-106]. Water soluble polymers are used in three main areas: medical, agricultural and goods packaging. Intensive research in these fields has resulted in the development of commercial products. Because of their high specialization and greater unit values, medical applications have developed more rapidly than the others. These developed biodegradable synthetics serve as surgical implants in the blood vessels, in orthopedic surgery as implantable matrices for controlled long – term drug release in an organism, and as absorbable surgical sutures, as well as for eye treatment. Water soluble polymers can be derived from synthetic, semi-synthetic or natural sources. As with many macromolecules, the differing stereochemistry of these high molecular weight compounds results in multiple arrays of primary, secondary, and tertiary/quaternary composites within their structure. However, regardless of their inherent structural complexity, water soluble polymers are commonly biocompatible and, in

most cases, biodegradable. Their low environmental burden makes it suitable for wide range of applications within the textile, food, healthcare, paper, adhesive, waste treatment, oil recovery, thin film and wrap sizing industries.

Recently the term “biomaterial” has been defined as a non - living material used in medical device applications for interaction with a biological system. It is important that the term “biocompatibility” was also formulated; it determines how a tissue responds to foreign material. Biocompatibility is the ability of a material to coexist with some host’s reactions in a specific use. The important applications of some water soluble polymers in various fields [102-111] are given in Table 2 and some functions of water soluble polymers and their uses are given in Table 3

Table 2: Important applications of water soluble polymers

Important area of use	Some of the water soluble polymers used
Adhesives, bonding agents and glues	PVA, polyacrylic acid salts.
Agricultural and horticultural products	Polyacrylamide, PEO, PEG, gum arabic, Guar gum, alginates, agar-agar.
Asphalt emulsions and pitches	HPMC, guar-gum, alginates.
Beverages and foods	HPMC, MC, gum arabic, gum tragacanth, Guar gum, locust bean gum, starch, agar-agar, alginates, casein, gelatin.
Cements, concrete, plasters, ceramics and glazes	HEC, HPMC, MC, polyacrylamide, acrylamide copolymers, PVA, gum arabic, alginates.
Detergents, emulsifier formulations and laundry products	HEC, PEG, PEO, PVP, carboxyvinyl polymer.
Flocculation	Polyacrylamide, PEO, Guar gum, starch derivatives, alginates, gelatin.
Inks, paints and other surface coatings	HEC, PEG, PEO, PVA, PVP, gum arabic, cellulose ether, MC, polyacrylic acid salts, polyacrylamide.
Mining and mineral processing	HEC, Guar gum, agar agar.
Oil- well drilling and oil –recovery	HEC, HPMC, PEO, starch derivatives.
Paper, wall paper, wall board production	HEC, HPMC, MC, acrylamide copolymers, PVA, PVP, gum arabic, gelatin, starch, agar-agar, casein.
Pharmaceutical, dental & related products	HEC, MC, PEG, PEO, PVP, gum arabic, gum karaya, Guar gum, locust bean gum, starch derivatives.
Photographic films and related products	HEC, PEO, PVA, agar agar, alginates, gelatin.

Table 3: Some functions of water soluble polymers and their uses

Important function	Uses
Thickening and gelling	Bacteriological and microscopy media; cosmetics and toiletries;

	drilling muds for oil products, dye pastes (textile printing), foods, glazes, links, lattices, lubricants, paints, pharmaceuticals.
Stabilizing agents and suspensions	Cosmetics and toiletries, detergent formulations, drilling muds for oil production, emulsion polymerization, foods, glazes, ink, paints, pharmaceuticals.
Flocculating and clarifying suspensions	Beverages, mineral procession, water treatment.
Coatings, films and sheets	Laundry bags, mould release agents, oil-resistant films, packaging (single-dose products), photographic films, temporary protective coatings, textiles (warp-size agents).
Solid –solid bonding	Adhesives, agricultural and horticultural sprays, cements, ceramics, explosives, fertilizers, foundry cores and moulds, hair sprays, leather processing, paper production, pharmaceuticals.
Moisture retention (humectants)	Foods, lather processing, tobacco products.
Osmotic effects	Blood-plasma substitutes, cryoprotectants.
Complexing	Dye-leveling and dye-stripping (textiles), pharmaceuticals, tannin precipitation (beverages).
Crystal-growth modification	Cryoprotectants, electroplating and electro-refining, foods, pharmaceuticals.

XI. CONTROLLED DRUG RELEASE SYSTEMS

For many decades treatment of an acute disease or chronic illness has been mostly accomplished by delivery of drugs to patients using various pharmaceutical dosage forms, including tablets, capsules, pills, suppositories, creams, ointments, liquids, aerosols and injectables, as drug carriers. Even today these conventional drug delivery systems are the primary pharmaceutical products commonly seen in the prescriptions and in the market. This type of drug delivery system is known to provide a prompt release of drug. Therefore, to achieve as well as to maintain the drug concentration within the therapeutically effective range needed for treatment, it is often necessary to take this type of drug delivery system several times a day [112-114].

The restrictions of classic methods for drug administration (by injection or tablet) are widely known. As a dose is applied, the plasma levels will go up, but they will fall drastically when the drug has been metabolized and soon be below therapeutic level. The next dose will make the plasma level high again and a cyclical pattern may be established. The drug usually permeates throughout the body and is not targeted to the site where it is specifically required. Therefore, in classical drug administration, the drug concentration in plasma level swings above the maximum level or a lack of efficiency if the drug falls below the minimum level. One of the possible solutions to this problem is to use a system of controlled drug delivery in which the drug is released at a constant, preset rate, preferably near to the specific location. One of the most preferred approaches is when the drug is contained in a polymer membrane (or encapsulated in a polymer matrix), from which it

diffuses out into the tissue. Since the initiation of pharmacological therapy, maintaining steady therapeutic drug concentration level while minimizing side effects has been major challenge. The ideal drug delivery system should be inert, biocompatible, mechanically strong, capable of achieving high drug loading, safe from accidental release, simple to apply and remove, ease to fabricate and sterilize and comfortable for the patient [112-115].

XII. POLYMERS IN CONTROLLED DRUG RELEASE SYSTEMS

Controlled release drug delivery system should necessarily consist of a barrier, which is generally a polymer. Naturally occurring polymers that are used in controlled release formulation may be obtained from plant extrudates (gum acacia, gum tragacanth, gum karaya, gum ghatti), seed or root (tamarind root, locust bean gum, orka gum), sea weed extract (chitin/chitosan, algin, carrageenan) and miscellaneous like pectin, gelatin and starch. Natural polymers have some disadvantages such as inappropriate mechanical properties, low strength, inconsistent behaviour and poor cell adhesion. To overcome these disadvantages semi-synthetic or synthetic polymers are employed. Some of the semi-synthetic polymers are cellulose based (methylcellulose, carboxymethylcellulose, hydroxypropylcellulose, hydroxypropylmethylcellulose, hydroxyethylcellulose), starch based (dextrin, carboxymethylstarch, starch amylopectin, hydroxyethylstarch, hydroxypropylstarch) and miscellaneous like poly (propylene glycol), pectin, carboxy locust bean gum, carboxymethyl guar hydrogel, etc. Synthetic polymers which are generally employed in controlled formulations are vinyl polymers (PVP, PVA, carboxyvinyl copolymers), acrylic polymers (polyacrylic acid, polyacrylamide) and ethylene oxide polymers (polyox, various polaxamer) [116-129].

The miscibility nature of some biocompatible/biodegradable polymer blend systems studied by various investigators are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Miscibility nature of some biocompatible/biodegradable polymer blends

Polymer Blends	Miscibility	Reference
Chitosan/gelatin	Immiscible	Basavaraju et al. [130]
Chitosan/PEG	Semi-miscible	Jayaraju et al. [98]
PLA/PEG	Semi-miscible	Mihir Sheth et al. [82]
CAP/PVP	Immiscible	Vijayalakshmi Rao et al. [122]
PVC/Starch	Immiscible	Thakora et al. [131]
PEO/PMMA	Miscible	Elberaich et al. [132]
PVP/PVA	Miscible	Vijayalakshmi Rao et al. [133]
PC/PEO	Immiscible	Varadarajulu et al. [134]
PC/PVP	Immiscible	Varadarajulu et al. [134]
NaAlg/PVA	Semi-miscible	Raviprakash et al. [135]
PSS/PVP	Immiscible	Garcia et al. [136]
PLL/PVP	Immiscible	Garcia et al. [136]
cellulose/alginate	Immiscible	Zhang et al. [137]

PVC/PVP	Miscible	Zheng et al. [138]
HPMC/PVP	Miscible	Amarakala et al. [139]
Hexanoyl chitosan/polylactide	Immiscible	Manisara Peesan et al. [140]
XG/gelatin	Semi-miscible	Basavaraju et al. [141]
Chitosan/HPMC	Semi-miscible	Jayaraju et al. [142]
Chitosan/PVA	Semi-miscible	Jayaraju et al. [143]
Chitosan /PVP	Semi-miscible	Jayaraju et al. [144]
Dextran/PVP	Miscible	Al-Khatani et al. [145]
HPMC/PEG	Semi-miscible	Sudhir R. Illiger et al. [146]
PESu/PPSu	Semi-miscible	George Papageorgiou et al. [147]
PESu/PBSu	Semi-miscible	George Papageorgiou et al. [147]
Starch-Cl/PCL	Miscible	Dong-Keon Kweon et al. [148]
HPMC/Pullulan	Semi-miscible	Prasad P. et al. [149]
Guar Gum/Pullulan	Semi-miscible	Bhavya B. B. et al. [150]
Pullulan/Polyacrylamide	Semi-miscible	Vishwanath et al. [151, 152]
Sodium alginate/Pullulan	Miscible	Prasad P. et al. [153]
Methyl Cellulose/PVA	Semi-miscible	Guru G. S. et al. [154]
PVP/Pullulan	Semi-miscible	Guru G. S. et al. [155]
Xanthan Gum/PVP	Semi-miscible	Guru G. S. et al. [156]
Pullulan/CMC	Semi-miscible	Guru G. S. et al. [157]
Guar Gum/CMC	Semi-miscible	Bhavya M. S. et al. [158, 159]
Guar Gum/PVA	Semi-miscible	Bhavya M. S. et al. [160, 161]

XIII. CONCLUSION

Synthetic and natural polymers are used for numerous applications in the biomedical field. However the properties of pure synthetic polymers and those of pure biological polymers alone are often inadequate to produce materials with good combination of chemical, mechanical, thermal, and biological performance characteristics. Though natural polymers (biopolymers) generally offer excellent biocompatibility but their mechanical properties are often very poor. Synthetic polymers generally have good mechanical properties but their biocompatibility is not satisfactory. Now a days, especially in biomedical and biotechnological fields, materials are required with good mechanical properties and good biocompatibility. Hence a set of new polymeric materials with desired properties have been prepared by blending synthetic polymers and biological macromolecules. Water soluble polymers like hydroxypropylmethylcellulose, pullulan, sodium alginate, xanthan gum, guar gum, carboxymethylcellulose, and poly(vinyl alcohol) has been studied by several researchers due to their blood compatibility, non-toxic, non-immunogenic, non-mutagenic and non-carcinogenic nature.

XIV. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We acknowledge the support of VGST, Government of Karnataka for their support for this work through the scheme VGST-CISEE, GRD No. 538.

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Guar gum (GG) / Methylcellulose (MC) Blends and their Composites with Maghemite Nanoparticles

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Abstract: Miscibility of polymers decides the applicability of the resulting blends and immiscible polymer blends can be made compatible with suitable compatibilizer. Miscibility of blends of guar gum (GG) and methyl cellulose (MC) in common solvent water were studied by refractive index, density, ultrasonic velocity, and dilute solution viscometry methods at 30°C and 40°C. Based on these measurements, it is found that the polymer blend of GG/MC is immiscible. The effect of compatibilization with 0.02 wt% maghemite nanoparticle was studied in aqueous solution and found that 10/90 GG/MC blend is miscible in the presence of maghemite. Solution cast technique was used to prepare thin films of GG/MC blend – maghemite composite and characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) method.

Keywords: guar gum, maghemite, miscibility, methylcellulose, polymer blends.

I. INTRODUCTION

Polymer blends are tailor-made materials for specific applications. The researches on polymer blends have gained considerable interest due to the reduction in the cost of production, improved processability, and improved properties [1]. The blending of polymers is significant to obtain a variety of physical and chemical properties from the constituent polymers [2]. The blend property depends on the polymer-polymer miscibility. Based on the miscibility, polymer blends are classified as miscible, semi-miscible, and immiscible blends [3]. Extensive studies on the miscibility of polymer blends by different techniques have been reported earlier by different researchers [4-8]. The miscibility of polymer blends is studied and confirmed by using density, refractive index, ultrasonic interferometry, viscometry, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopic (FTIR) methods [9-17].

Guar gum (GG) is an extremely hydrophilic natural

polymer with high viscosity. This property has allowed GG to be commercialized in fields such as textiles, foods, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals and oil recovery and drilling [13, 15]. Methylcellulose is a semi-synthetic water-soluble polymer derived from cellulose and is used as a thickener in the food industry, and as a matrix for the controlled release of drugs in the pharmaceutical industry [18].

Polymer blends of GG and MC will be having potential applications in drug release formulations. The miscibility can be enhanced by the incorporation of suitable compatible agents [11]. Maghemite is a biocompatible magnetic nanoparticle having potential applications in the biomedical field [19-22]. In this work miscibility of guar gum and methylcellulose at different compositions were studied in solution state at 30°C and 40°C by refractive index, density, ultrasonic velocity, and viscosity measurement techniques in aqueous solution and by SEM and FTIR in solid-state. The effect of biocompatible maghemite nanoparticles (Mag NPs) on the miscibility of GG/MC blends was studied in aqueous solution by density, ultrasonic velocity, dilute solution viscometry in aqueous solution and in the solid-state by SEM, and FTIR.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The polymers employed in the present study are guar gum (GG), methylcellulose (MC), and the nanoparticle used is maghemite. All were purchased from Merck, India. Schematic representation of guar gum and methylcellulose are shown in Fig. 1, and 2, respectively.

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of guar gum

Revised Manuscript Received on May 15, 2020.

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Fig. 2: Schematic representation of methylcellulose

0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, and 0.05 wt% maghemite nanocomposites were prepared with guar gum (0.5% w/v) and with methylcellulose (0.5% w/v) separately in distilled water as solvent. The mixtures were mechanically stirred for 6 hours in a polymer mixer and were further kept for ultrasonication for 4 hours to ensure uniform mixing. The prepared samples were taken in test tubes and kept in contact with a strong magnet for 30 minutes to check the stability of the solution. All the maghemite-MC composite solutions showed stability towards the magnetic field, whereas the solutions of guar gum containing 0.05, 0.04, and 0.03 wt% of maghemite, the maghemite got settled along the sides of the test tube attracted by the strong magnet. Hence the experiments were continued with 0.02 wt% of maghemite.

Blends of GG/MC of different compositions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10) were prepared in distilled water. The refractive index, density, and ultrasonic velocity of the GG, MC, GG/MC blend solutions (0.5%, w/v) with and without maghemite nanoparticles (0.02 wt%) were measured at 30°C and 40°C using specific gravity bottle, Abbe’s refractometer, and ultrasonic interferometer (Model F-81, Mittal Enterprises, India), respectively. Different temperatures were maintained using a thermostat bath with a thermal stability of ± 0.05°C.

Stock solutions of GG, GG – maghemite composite, MC, and MC – maghemite composite were prepared (0.1% w/v of polymer). The maghemite composition was maintained at 0.02 wt%. The blend stock solutions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30 and 90/10) and blend – maghemite composite stock solutions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30 and 90/10) were prepared by stirring the mixtures at room temperature for about 45 minutes. With the above pure and blend stock solutions, different dilute blend solutions (0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05, 0.06, 0.07, 0.08, 0.09 and 0.1 w/v concentrations) were prepared. Dilute solution viscosity measurements were done at 30°C and 40°C using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer. Different temperatures were maintained using a thermostat bath with a thermal stability of ± 0.05°C.

Thin films of polymer/polymer blend - maghemite composites were prepared by solution casting technique for characterization purposes. SEM photographs were recorded using a ZEISS Sigma FESEM 300 analyzer and FTIR spectra were recorded using NICOLET AVATAR 530 spectrophotometer.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Refractive index measurements

The refractive index (RI) values of pure polymers and their blends were measured. The RI value for MC is 1.3420 and 1.3410, and for GG is 1.3402 and 1.3385 at 30°C and 40°C,

respectively. A slight linearity is observed for the 10/90 GG/MC blend compared with RI values of pure GG and MC both at 30°C and 40°C (Fig. 3). It has been well established that linearity and non-linearity of the plot indicate the miscible and immiscible nature of the blends [9, 10] respectively.

With the addition of 0.02 wt% maghemite showed an RI value of about 1.46 for pure GG, MC and their blend compositions at 30°C and of about 1.44 at 40°C. The higher RI value after the maghemite addition may be due to the brownish-red color of the maghemite nanoparticle and hence the RI measurement technique may not be considered as a suitable proof to assess the miscibility of the blend - maghemite composites with GG and MC.

Fig. 3: Variation of refractive index of GG/MC blends in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

B. Density measurements

The measured density values (ρ) of GG were $0.9972 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $0.99376 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and for MC were $0.9985 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $0.99525 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, at 30°C and 40°C, respectively. The density values of blend compositions were in between that of pure GG and MC. The ρ values were higher for MC compared to GG attributed to their molecular structure. The graph showed only non-linear regions indicating the immiscible nature of the GG/MC blend at both 30°C and 40°C (Fig. 4). The variation is linear for miscible and non-linear for immiscible blends [11, 12].

The recorded density values for maghemite composites were higher compared to that of pure polymers without maghemite. Density values for 0.02 wt% maghemite-GG composites were $1.007 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $0.9985 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and for 0.02 wt% maghemite-MC composites were $1.031 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $1.012 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, at 30°C and 40°C, respectively (Fig. 5). Only 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite composite showed linearity compared with the maghemite composites of GG and MC, other compositions got deviated from linearity. Hence it can be concluded that the addition of maghemite improved the miscibility nature of GG/MC blends.

Fig. 4: Variation of density with the composition of GG/MC blend in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

Fig. 5: Variation of density with the composition of GG/MC blend – maghemite composites in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

C. Ultrasonic velocity measurements

The measured ultrasonic velocity (v) value for methylcellulose were 1525 m/s and 1545 m/s, and for GG were 1479 m/s and 1519 m/s, at 30°C and 40°C, respectively. The v for the entire compositions were found to be in between that of pure GG and MC, but the graph showed non-linear regions (Fig. 6). This indicates that the GG/MC blend is immiscible at all compositions [12, 13].

The incorporation of maghemite nanoparticles decreased the v of GG, MC, and GG/MC blends. The measured values were 1510 m/s, and 1524 m/s for MC-maghemite composite, and 1464 m/s, and 1488 m/s for GG-maghemite composites at 30°C and 40°C, respectively (Fig. 7). The observation with ultrasonic velocity measurement studies was similar to that of density studies. The presence of maghemite might have influenced the miscibility of the GG/MC blend for the 10/90 blend composition.

Fig. 6: Variation of ultrasonic sound velocity of GG/MC blend in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

Fig. 7: Variation of ultrasonic sound velocity of GG/MC blend – maghemite composites in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

D. Reduced viscosity measurements

Reduced viscosities (η_{sp}/C) of homopolymers GG, MC and 10/90 GG/MC, 30/70 GG/MC, 50/50 GG/MC, 70/30 GG/MC, and 90/10 GG/MC were measured at 30°C and 40°C. The Huggin's plots of η_{sp}/C against concentration (C) are shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, respectively.

Fig. 8: Huggins's plot for GG/MC blend at 30°C

Fig. 10: Huggins's plot for GG/MC blend – maghemite composite at 30°C

Fig. 9: Huggins's plot for GG/MC blend at 40°C

Fig. 11: Huggins's plot for GG/MC blend – maghemite composite at 40°C

Reduced viscosities of GG-maghemite composite, MC-maghemite composite, and the blend-maghemite composite compositions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10) were measured at 30°C and 40°C. η_{sp}/C against concentration plots of maghemite composites are shown in Fig. 10, and Fig. 11, respectively.

From the Huggins plots the slope values were calculated and tabulated in Table I. The slope values of the blends are lower than that of pure GG and MC. This confirms phase separation of polymers in the blend. Higher slope variations for 10/90 GG/MC blend composition with maghemite nanoparticles may be attributed to the mutual attraction of macromolecules in solution which in turn leads to the increase of hydrodynamic volume [14]. The 90/10, 70/30, 50/50, and 30/70 GG/MC blend – maghemite composite compositions showed a lower slope, which may be due to the phase separation of polymers. According to the reduced viscosity-concentration [9-13] criteria, it may be concluded that this polymer blend is miscible for 10/90 compositions and immiscible for 90/10, 70/30, 50/50, and 30/70 GG/MC blend compositions.

Table- I: Slope values from Huggins plots

Blends Comp.	30°C		40°C	
	Without Mag NPs	With Mag NPs	Without Mag NPs	With Mag NPs
0/100	217.884	139.618	152.496	131.478
10/90	154.090	163.739	140.490	179.218
30/70	150.630	140.115	117.715	126.351
50/50	158.218	136.030	117.612	124.842
70/30	166.218	142.630	132.654	128.915
90/10	172.006	139.236	123.327	128.266
100/0	170.260	142.721	154.666	124.333

E. Morphological studies

Morphology studies were carried out to identify the interaction between maghemite and the polymers and the influence of maghemite on the miscibility of GG/MC blend. SEM images recorded for GG, MC, and maghemite incorporated GG, MC, and 10/90 GG/MC blend (Fig. 12). The SEM images confirm that guar gum form weak interaction with maghemite, whereas the maghemite is well dispersed in methylcellulose. The 10/90 GG/MC blend with maghemite does not show any phase separation.

The presence of maghemite might have stabilized the structure of guar gum to form a miscible blend with MC at 10/90 blend composition.

Fig. 12: SEM images of a) GG, b) GG-maghemite composite, c) MC, d) MC-maghemite composite, and e) 10/90 GG/MC blend-maghemite composite

F. FTIR spectroscopic measurements

FTIR spectra of GG, GG – maghemite composite, MC, MC – maghemite composite, and 10/90 GG/MC blend-maghemite composite were recorded in the wavelength range of $4000-500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Fig. 13). Guar gum showed (Fig. 13a) the broad and strong absorption band at 3347.3 cm^{-1} , the absorption band at 2918.2 cm^{-1} , 1638.3 cm^{-1} is due to the to $-\text{OH}$ bond stretching, $-\text{CH}$ group stretching, and $-\text{OH}$ bond belonging to water molecules, respectively. The absorption band at 1370.9 cm^{-1} and 1012.7 cm^{-1} is the bending of $-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-$ groups [23].

The FTIR spectra of MC (Fig. 13b) showed a $-\text{OH}$ stretching at 3350.3 cm^{-1} , and 1593.7 cm^{-1} is due the $-\text{OH}$ bond belonging to water molecules. C-H stretching of the $-\text{CH}_2$ groups is observed at 2916.7 cm^{-1} , a $-\text{CH}_2$ scissoring around 1412 cm^{-1} and $-\text{O}-$ stretching at 1026 cm^{-1} [24, 25].

Fig. 13: FTIR spectra of a) GG, b) MC, c) GG-maghemite composite, d) MC-maghemite composite, and e) 10/90 GG/MC blend-maghemite composite

FTIR images (Fig. 13c, and Fig. 13d) showed the characteristic maghemite peaks in the GG - maghemite composite, and MC - maghemite composite. FTIR spectroscopy of 10/90 GG/MC blend - maghemite composite is given in Fig. 13e. The major peaks were associated with alcohol (ν -OH) group observed at 3310 cm^{-1} . Alkyl stretching, carbonyl group stretching, and $-\text{CH}$ bending, $-\text{C}-\text{O}$ stretch were observed at 2941 cm^{-1} , 1735 cm^{-1} , 1245 cm^{-1} , 1088 cm^{-1} , respectively. The peak at 537 cm^{-1} corresponds to the vibration of Fe-O, and the other peaks of pure maghemite are 454 cm^{-1} , and 632 cm^{-1} [26-27]. The instrumental limitation did not allow these two peaks to be clearly shown. The hydroxyl characteristic bands for 10/90 GG/MC blend - maghemite composite got shifted to lower wavelength compared to GG and MC, which confirms the formation of H-bonding between guar gum and methylcellulose in the presence of maghemite. Hence, the FTIR spectroscopic measurement confirms that the incorporation of maghemite influenced the miscibility of GG/MC blend, and 10/90 GG/MC blend is miscible in the presence of 0.02 wt% maghemite.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the refractive index, density, ultrasonic velocity, adiabatic compressibility, and dilute solution viscometry studies it is confirmed that guar gum and methylcellulose form immiscible blends. The influence of biocompatible magnetic nanoparticles on the miscibility of GG/MC was studied using density, ultrasonic velocity, adiabatic compressibility, and dilute solution viscometry in aqueous solution and with solution cast thin films by scanning electron microscopy and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. The results confirms that 10/90 GG/MC blend composition is miscible with the presence of maghemite nanoparticles. The formation of intermolecular hydrogen bonding between GG and MC in the presence of maghemite nanoparticles were confirmed with SEM and FTIR studies. The maghemite compatible blend composition of GG/MC will be having applications in drug release formulations.

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Biocompatible Maghemite Nanoparticles Compatibilization of GG/CMC Blends in Aqueous Solution

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Subject Area: Nanotechnology.

Type of the Paper: Experimental Research.

Type of Review: Peer Reviewed as per [C|O|P|E](#) guidance.

Indexed In: OpenAIRE.

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3843175>.

Google Scholar Citation: [IJAEML](#).

How to Cite this Paper:

Bhavya, M. S., Sudhanva Narayana, K., Savitha, M. B. & Prasad, P. (2020). Biocompatible Maghemite Nanoparticles Compatibilization of GG/CMC Blends in Aqueous Solution. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 4(1), 184-190. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3843175>.

International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)

A Refereed International Journal of Srinivas University, India.

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Biocompatible Maghemite Nanoparticles Compatibilization of GG/CMC Blends in Aqueous Solution

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ABSTRACT

Biocompatible polymer blends with natural polymer guar gum (GG), and a modified natural polymer carboxymethylcellulose (CMC) have been studied for their compatibilization with biocompatible maghemite magnetic nanoparticles. Ultrasonic velocity, density, and dilute solution viscometry methods were used to assess the intermolecular interaction between GG and CMC in the presence of maghemite nanoparticles at 30°C and 40°C. The solution state studies confirmed that GG/CMC blends are compatible in the presence of maghemite nanoparticle only if the GG content is more than 30% in the blend. These biocompatible polymer blend-maghemite nanocomposites can be used for their applications in controlled drug release formulations.

Keywords: Maghemite, Guar gum, Carboxymethylcellulose, Biocompatibility, Polymer blend – nanocomposites.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Polymer blending is a novel method to produce a new polymer system with improved properties for applications [1]. The properties of blends depend on their miscibility at the molecular level [2, 3]. Many water-soluble biocompatible blend systems were studied to record their miscibility nature [4-10]. Guar gum (GG) [11, 12] and carboxymethylcellulose (CMC) [13, 14] are useful polymers for their applications in drug release formulations. In our previous work, the miscibility of GG with CMC was extensively studied with refractive index, ultrasonic velocity, density, and dilute solution viscometry methods in aqueous solution [15], and the blend thin films were characterized for the presence of intermolecular hydrogen bonding by SEM, FTIR, and DSC measurements [16]. It was confirmed that GG/CMC blends are miscible when GG content is more than 60% in the blend.

The immiscible polymer blends can be made compatible with the addition of suitable compatibilizers. For the applications of the blend systems for drug release formulations the compatibilizer also must be biocompatible [17-19]. Maghemite is a biocompatible magnetic nanoparticle having potential application in controlled release formulations [20-23]. In this paper extended research work on the influence of maghemite magnetic nanoparticle on the properties of GG/CMC blends is studied with dilute solution viscometry, ultrasonic interferometry, and density measurements at 30°C and 40°C in aqueous solution.

2. EXPERIMENTALPROCEDURE :

The polymers employed in the present study are guar gum and carboxymethylcellulose, and the nanoparticle used is maghemite. All the chemicals were purchased from Merck, India. Distilled water was used for the experiments. 0.02 wt% of maghemite nanoparticles were added to the prepared polymer solutions and different blend – maghemite composite compositions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 30/70, and 10/90) were prepared with the total polymer concentration as 0.5% w/v. Ultrasonic velocity and density were measured at 30°C and 40°C by an interferometric technique employing an ultrasonic interferometer (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi) at frequency 2MHz and using specific gravity bottle, respectively. Different temperatures were maintained using a thermostat bath with the thermal stability of $\pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$.

Stock solutions of GG – maghemite composite and CMC– maghemite composite were prepared (0.1% w/v) with 0.02 wt% maghemite nanoparticles. The blend – maghemite composite stock solutions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10) were prepared by stirring the mixtures at room temperature for about 45 minutes. Using the above pure and blend – composite stock solutions, different blend – nanocomposite solutions (0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05, 0.06, 0.07, 0.08, 0.09 and 0.1 w/v concentrations) were prepared and viscosity measurements were done at 30°C and 40°C using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer. Different temperatures were maintained using a thermostat bath with the thermal stability of $\pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS :

3.1 Ultrasonic velocity, density, and adiabatic compressibility measurements :

The experimental ultrasonic velocity values of GG – maghemite is higher compared to that of pure GG at both 30°C and 40°C. This may be due to the uncoiling of the GG molecule, whereas the CMC – maghemite composite showed almost similar ultrasonic velocity as that of pure CMC. The presence of maghemite increased the density value of both GG, and CMC. The variation of ultrasonic velocity, density, and adiabatic compressibility with the percentage composition of GG is given in Figures 1, 2, and 3, respectively. All these graphs show both linear and non-linear regions indicating the semi-miscible nature of the GG/CMC blend – maghemite composites. GG/CMC blends showed linearity for the blend compositions with more than 60% of GG in the blend [4-8]. With the compatibilization effect of maghemite the 30/70, 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 blend compositions show linearity, whereas 10/90 blend composition got deviated from linearity compared with GG and CMC. Hence it indicates that with the presence of 0.02 wt% maghemite the GG/CMC blends are compatible when GG content is more than 30% in the blend.

Fig. 1: Variation of ultrasonic velocity with a composition of 0.02 wt% maghemite nanoparticles composites with GG, CMC, and GG/CMC blends in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

Fig. 2: Variation of density with a composition of 0.02 wt% maghemite nanoparticle composites with GG, CMC, and GG/CMC blends in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

Fig. 3: Variation of adiabatic compressibility with the composition of 0.02 wt% maghemite nanoparticle composites with GG, CMC, and GG/CMC blends in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

3.2 Reduced viscosity measurements :

Reduced viscosities of maghemite nanocomposites with GG, CMC, and their blend compositions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10) were measured at 30°C and 40°C. Huggin's plots of reduced viscosities of the pure polymer – maghemite nanocomposites and their blend – maghemite nanocomposite compositions against concentrations are shown in Figures 4, and 5, respectively.

Fig. 4: Huggins's plot for 0.1% (w/v) GG/CMC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites at 30°C

Fig. 5: Huggins's plot for 0.1% (w/v) GG/CMC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites at 40°C

Table 1: Slope values from Huggins plots

Composition of GG/CMC blend – maghemite nanocomposites	30°C	40°C
100/0	142.721	124.557
90/10	155.212	132.400
70/30	153.163	136.157
50/50	143.703	132.957
30/70	146.690	141.284
10/90	138.000	119.678
0/100	182.430	169.709

The plots were linear. The slopes of the curves were measured and tabulated in Table 1. A higher slope variation for 90/10, 70/30, 50/50, and 30/70 compositions are attributed to the mutual attraction of macromolecules in solution which leads to the increase of hydrodynamic volume [24-27]. The 10/90 compositions showed a lower slope may be due to the phase separation of polymers. According to the criterion of reduced viscosity-concentration, this polymer blend should be compatible with 90/10, 70/30, 5/50, and 30/70 compositions and incompatible for 30/70 compositions.

4. CONCLUSION :

Based on viscosity, ultrasonic velocity, and density measurements, it is found that the incorporation of maghemite magnetic nanoparticles improved the miscibility/compatibility of a polymer blend of Guar Gum/CMC. The blend – maghemite nanocomposites are compatible when the GG content is more than 30%. Below this critical GG concentration the blend – maghemite nanocomposites were found to be immiscible. Hence GG/CMC blend – maghemite nanocomposites in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C is semi-miscible in nature. The variation of temperature did not have any significant effect on the miscibility/compatibility.

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Investigation on γ -Fe₂O₃ Nanoparticles Compatibilization on Guar Gum/poly(vinyl alcohol) Blends

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Subject Area: Nanotechnology.

Type of the Paper: Experimental Research.

Type of Review: Peer Reviewed as per [C|O|P|E|](#) guidance.

Indexed In: OpenAIRE.

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3890299>.

Google Scholar Citation: [IJAEML](#).

How to Cite this Paper:

Bhavya, M. S., Athira Lakshmanan, P., Sudhanva Narayana, K., Savitha, M. B., & Prasad, P. (2020). Investigation on γ -Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles compatibilization on guar gum/poly (vinyl alcohol) blends. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 4(1), 219-225. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3890299>.

International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)

A Refereed International Journal of Srinivas University, India.

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ABSTRACT

The semi-miscible polymer blends of natural polymer guar gum and synthetic polymer poly (vinyl alcohol) have been studied for their compatibilization with biocompatible γ -Fe₂O₃nanoparticles. Ultrasonic velocity, density, adiabatic compressibility, and dilute solution viscometry studies at 30°C and 40°C has confirmed that γ -Fe₂O₃nanocomposites of GG/PVA blends are compatible. The presence of well-dispersed nanoparticles may have allowed the uncoiling of guar gum molecules to form intermolecular hydrogen bonding with PVA. The GG/PVA blend – γ -Fe₂O₃composites are potential candidates for biomedical applications.

Keywords: γ -Fe₂O₃nanoparticles, guar gum, PVA, biocompatibility, polymer blend-nanocomposites.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Guar gum (GG) obtained from guar bean (*Cyamopsistetragonoloba*) is a hydrophilic polymer. It has got applications in cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries [1-4]. Polymer blending [5-10] introduces new miscible/semi-miscible macromolecules with newer properties or with additive properties of the two or more polymers involved in it. The blending of guar gum with other polymers has been investigated by many researchers for their applications in biomedical engineering [11, 12]. Poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA) is a synthetic biodegradable polymer and has been widely used in biodegradable packaging and biomedical industries [13, 14]. In our previous work, we have characterized the miscibility of GG/PVA blends in aqueous solution by reduced viscosity, density, adiabatic compressibility, and refractive index methods in aqueous solution [15] and the blend thin films were characterized by FTIR, SEM, and DSC methods [16]. The maghemite nanoparticles in the blend solutions may introduce potential drug release applications. Maghemite is an iron oxide nanomaterial with chemical formula γ -Fe₂O₃. These nanoparticles are used in biomedicine as they are non-toxic, and biocompatible. Even their magnetic property makes them a potential candidate for magnetic controlled drug delivery systems [17, 18]. In this paper, the compatibility of natural polymer guar gum and a synthetic polymer poly(vinyl alcohol) at different compositions were studied by density, ultrasonic velocity, and viscosity measurement techniques in their dilute solution at 30°C and 40°C.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS :

The polymers employed in the present study guar gum (GG), poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA), and maghemite (γ -Fe₂O₃) were purchased from Merck, India. Blend – maghemite nanocomposites of GG/PVA (0.5 w/v of polymer and 0.02 wt% of maghemite) of different compositions were prepared by mixing aqueous polymer – maghemite composite solutions. Ultrasonic velocity (v) was measured at 30°C and 40°C by an interferometric technique employing an ultrasonic interferometer (Mittal

Enterprises, New Delhi) at frequency 2MHz. The densities (ρ) of the GG/PVA blend – maghemite nanocomposites were measured at 30°C and 40°C using specific gravity bottle. Different temperatures were maintained using a thermostat bath with a thermal stability of $\pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$. Adiabatic compressibility (β_{ad}) were calculated as per the equation: $\beta_{ad} = 1/(v^2\rho)$.

Stock solutions of nanocomposites of GG, PVA, and their blends (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10) were prepared (0.1% w/v polymer, and 0.02 wt% maghemite) by stirring the mixtures at room temperature for about 45 minutes. Using the above pure and blend stock solutions, different blend solutions (0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05, 0.06, 0.07, 0.08, 0.09 and 0.1 w/v concentrations) were prepared and viscosity measurements were done at 30°C and 40°C using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer. Different temperatures were maintained using a thermostat bath with a thermal stability of $\pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS :

3.1 Ultrasonic velocity, density, and adiabatic compressibility measurements

Fig.1: Variation of ultrasonic velocity with the composition of GG/PVA blend – maghemite nanocomposites in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

Fig.2: Variation of density with the composition of GG/PVA blend – maghemite nanocomposites in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

Fig.3: Variation of adiabatic compressibility with composition of GG/PVA blend – maghemite nanocomposites in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

The ultrasonic velocity of PVA – maghemite nanocomposite solution is 1508 m/s, and 1540 m/s at 30°C and 40°C whereas for GG – maghemite nanocomposite solution it is 1464 m/s, and 1488 m/s, respectively. The density values were found to be $0.9989 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$ and $0.9968 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$ for PVA – maghemite nanocomposite and $1.007 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$ and $0.9985 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$ for GG – maghemite nanocomposite. The calculated adiabatic compressibility values are $4.40226 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$ and $4.2301 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$ for PVA – maghemite nanocomposite; and $4.63328 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$ and $4.5232 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Kg}^{-1}\text{ms}^2$ for GG – maghemite nanocomposites. The ultrasonic velocity, density, and adiabatic compressibility values for the entire blend – maghemite nanocomposites were found to be composition dependent and all the plots (Figures 1, 2, and 3) were linear indicating compatibility [19-21] at 30°C and 40°C.

3.2 Reduced viscosity measurements

Fig. 4: Huggins's plot for 0.1% (w/v) GG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites at 30°C

Fig.5: Huggins's plot for 0.1% (w/v) GG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites at 40°C

Table 1: Slope values from Huggin's plots

Composition of GG/PVA blend – maghemite nanocomposites	30°C	40°C
0/100	16.206	10.903
10/90	21.545	26.818
30/70	48.969	43.084
50/50	96.096	89.757
70/30	126.230	122.193
90/10	135.200	131.509
100/0	142.721	122.793

Reduced viscosities of maghemite nanocomposites of GG, PVA, and their blend compositions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10) were measured at 30°C and 40°C. Huggin's plots of reduced viscosities against concentrations are shown in Figures 4, and Figure 5, respectively.

The plots were linear. A higher slope variation for the entire blend – maghemite nanocomposites is attributed to the mutual attraction of macromolecules in solution which leads to the increase of hydrodynamic volume [22-24]. The temperature did not have any significant effect on the compatibility maghemite nanocomposites with GG/PVA blends.

4. CONCLUSION :

The plots of ultrasonic velocity, density, and adiabatic compressibility against blend – maghemite nanocomposite compositions found to be linear and composition-dependent. This indicates that the blends were compatibilized by the presence of maghemite nanoparticles. Based on dilute solution viscosity measurements it is confirmed that the entire blend – maghemite nanocomposite of guar gum and poly (vinyl alcohol) are compatible at 30°C and 40°C. The variation of temperature did not have any significant effect on the compatibility.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT :

The authors acknowledge the partial financial support by Vision Group on Science and Technology (VGST, CISEE – GRD No. 538).

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PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt / Egyptology

MISCIBILITY STUDIES OF BIOCOMPATIBLE XANTHAN GUM/METHYLCELLULOSE BLEND-MAGHEMITE NANOCOMPOSITE

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M. S. Bhavya, K. S. Sudhanva Narayana, P. Prasad, M. B. Savitha: Miscibility Studies Of Biocompatible Xanthan Gum/Methylcellulose Blend-Maghemite Nanocomposite -- Palarch's Journal Of Archaeology Of Egypt/Egyptology 17(9). ISSN 1567-214x

Keywords: Xanthan gum, MC, Maghemite, Miscibility, Polymer Blends.

ABSTRACT

Water-soluble miscible polymer blends are extensively used water purification, biomedical engineering, agriculture applications. The biopolymers used in the present study are xanthan gum (XG) which is a natural polymer and methylcellulose (MC) is a modified natural polymer. Based on refractive index, ultrasonic velocity, density, and dilute solution viscosity measurements the XG/MC blend is found to be miscible when the XG content is more than 50% in the blend. Maghemite nanoparticles were added to the blends as compatibilizers, their homogeneity and specific intermolecular hydrogen bonding was confirmed by SEM, FTIR measurements. The TGA and tensile strength measurement confirms the improved thermal properties and mechanical strength of the XG/MC blends with and without maghemite nanoparticles..

1. Introduction

Discovered in 1963 at USA's the National Center for Agricultural Utilization Research, xanthan is one of the most popular commercially produced gums. It was first derived from the bacterial action of *Xanthomonas campestris* on plants, primarily those in the cabbage family. With the advent of viscous fermentation technology in the early 1970s, this high molecular-weight polysaccharide is now produced from cornstarch. Xanthan gum (XG) is used in a variety of industrial and oil-field applications, pharmaceutical and personal care items, and processed foods. Its broad usefulness as an emulsifying, gelling, film-forming, thickening and stabilizing agent makes xanthan gum one of the most attractive products [1-5]. Methylcellulose (MC) is the simplest cellulose derivative, where methyl groups (-CH₃) substitute the hydroxyls at C-2, C-3 and/or C-6 positions of anhydro-D-glucose units. Methylcellulose is a cellulose derivative that can be prepared from the reaction of alkali-cellulose with dimethyl sulfate (DMS) or methyl chloride. It may be used as a thickener in the food industry, as a matrix for the controlled release of drugs in the pharmaceutical industry. Methylcellulose have used in food, ceramics, personal care, pharmaceuticals, biomedical, construction, adhesives, agriculture, and many other applications [6-8].

In the literature the miscibility studies of these two polymers are not available and these blends may find specific applications. The miscibility can be enhanced by the incorporation of suitable compatible agents. Maghemite is a biocompatible magnetic nanoparticle having potential applications in the biomedical field [9-13]. It is the second most common polymorph of iron oxide. The blend properties of XG and MC are intensively studied with refractive index, density, ultrasonic velocity, and dilute solution viscometry in solution state and the blend thin films were characterized by SEM, FTIR, TGA, and UTM. Further the influence of the biocompatible magnetic nanoparticle, maghemite on the blends were determined. Since xanthan gum is anionic in nature [14], we could not apply the Huggins equation to the xanthan gum in water solution, so the solution was made in 0.1 M NaCl for viscosity studies.

2. Experimental Procedure

Xanthan gum (XG) and methylcellulose (MC) were purchased from Merck, Mumbai, India, maghemite, and research-grade NaCl (Merck make) were used in this study. Blends of XG/MC of different compositions were prepared by mixing aqueous polymer solutions. Ultrasonic velocity of the blend solutions of 0.5 % (w/v) was measured at 30°C and 40°C by an interferometric technique employing an ultrasonic interferometer (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi) at frequency 2 MHz. The densities and refractive index of the XG/MC blend solutions (0.5 % w/v) were measured at 30°C and 40°C using a specific gravity bottle and Abbe's refractometer, respectively. Stock solutions of XG and MC were prepared (0.5 % w/v) in 0.1 M NaCl. The blend stock solutions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10) were prepared by stirring the mixtures at room temperature for about 45 minutes in the NaCl solution. Using the above pure

and blend stock solutions, different blend solutions (0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05, 0.06, 0.07, 0.08, 0.09 and 0.1 w/v concentrations) were prepared and viscosity measurements were done at 30°C and 40°C using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer. Different temperatures were maintained using a thermostat bath with a thermal stability of $\pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$. 0.02 wt% maghemite were used for its compatibilising effect on XG/MC blends.

Thin films of the polymers and their blends, nanocomposites, and blend nanocomposites were prepared by solution casting method. SEM photographs were recorded using a JOEL (JSM 6380LA) analyzer. FTIR spectra were recorded using NICOLET AVATAR 530 spectrophotometer. Thermogravimetric analysis of the blend films was performed over the temperature range of 20 – 500°C, using Thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA Q50 V20.2 Build 27) under nitrogen environment at a scan rate of 10°C/min. Mechanical properties were measured under tensile strain with an LLYODS UK model analyzer (LR 100K) according to ASTM standards D882.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Refractive index measurements

Figure 1: Variation of refractive index with the composition of XG/MC blend in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

Refractive index (RI) of methylcellulose is 1.3423, and 1.3413 at 30°C and 40°C, and for xanthan gum it is 1.3447, and 1.3435, respectively. The RI value of XG/MC blends is found to be in between those of xanthan gum and methylcellulose. It is found from the graph (Figure 1) that both at 30°C and 40°C the blend compositions 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 showed linearity with respect to XG and MC. Whereas for 10/90 and 30/70 XG/MC blends are not having linearity. The linearity indicates the miscibility/compatibility of the blends [15-17].

Due to the brownish-red color of the maghemite nanoparticle, the RI measurement technique may not be considered as a suitable proof to assess the miscibility of the blend - maghemite composites.

3.2 Density measurements

The density value of methylcellulose is found to be $0.9985 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $0.99525 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$ and for xanthan gum it is $0.9999 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $0.9966 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, respectively. The density values of XG/MC blends are observed to be in between that of XG and MC but the linearity is observed for 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 XG/MC blend compositions only at both 30°C and 40°C (Figure 2A).

With the addition of 0.02 wt% maghemite, the density value of methylcellulose is found to be $0.9996 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $0.9988 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and for xanthan gum, it is $1.0067 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, and $1.0032 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$, respectively at 30°C and 40°C. The increase in density indicates the interaction of the polymers with maghemite. All the blend - maghemite nanocomposite compositions with 0.02 wt% maghemite showed linearity with respect to their pure polymers composites with maghemite (Figure 2B). It indicates that the incorporation of 0.02 wt% maghemite act as a compatibilizer to the blends [18].

Figure 2: Variation of density with the composition of A) XG/MC blends, and B) XG/MC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

3.3 Ultrasonic velocity measurements

The ultrasonic velocity value of methylcellulose at 30°C and 40°C is found to be 1525 m/s, and 1545 m/s and for xanthan gum it is 1473 m/s, and 1485 m/s, respectively. The ultrasonic velocity values of XG/MC blends are observed to be in between that of XG and MC but the linearity is observed for 50/50, 70/30,

and 90/10 XG/MC blend compositions only at both 30°C and 40°C (Figure 3A).

4. With the addition of 0.02 wt% maghemite, the ultrasonic velocity value of methylcellulose at 30°C and 40°C is found to be 1510 m/s, and 1524 m/s, and for xanthan gum it is 1434 m/s, and 1462 m/s, respectively. All the blend - maghemite nanocomposite compositions with 0.02 wt% maghemite showed linearity with respect to their pure polymers composites with maghemite (Figure 3B). It indicates that the incorporation of 0.02 wt% maghemite acts as a compatibilizer to the blends [19-22].

Figure 3: Variation of ultrasonic velocity with the composition of A) XG/MC blends, and B) XG/MC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites in aqueous solution at 30°C and 40°C

3.4 Reduced viscosity measurements

Reduced viscosities of homopolymers XG, MC and their blend compositions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 30/70, and 90/10), XG – 0.02 wt % maghemite nanocomposite, MC – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite, and their blend compositions (10/90, 30/70, 50/50, 30/70, and 90/10), were measured at 30°C and 40°C. Huggin's plots of reduced viscosities against concentrations are shown in Figure 5.

At both 30°C and 40°C all the plots of XG/MC blend compositions were found to be linear. A higher slope variation is observed for 90/10, 70/30, and 50/50

XG/MC blends, whereas comparatively lower slope for 10/90, and 30/70 XG/MC blend compositions. It confirms that the XG/MC blend is miscible when XG content is 50% or more [23]. The slope values are tabulated in Table 1.

Figure 4: Huggins' plot for A) XG/MC blend at 30°C, XG/MC blend at 40°C, C) XG/MC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite at 30°C, and D) XG/MC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite at 40°C.

Table 1: Slope values from Huggins plots

Composition (XG/MC)	Blends		Blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite composites	
	30°C	40°C	30°C	40°C
0/100	153.290	151.139	175.684	161.654
10/90	146.927	150.169	282.642	261.533
30/70	151.884	148.030	411.581	301.703
50/50	201.012	256.945	472.787	344.375
70/30	290.212	298.993	508.836	379.460
90/10	420.115	386.418	566.400	380.339
100/0	500.812	414.054	568.272	351.836

The plots were linear for XG, XG - 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite, MC, MC - 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposite, blends of XG/MC, and blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites. All the plots of blends with 0.02 wt% maghemite showed higher slope variation confirming the miscibility. Whereas for blends without maghemite nanoparticles higher slope variation is observed for 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 blend composition. Without the presence of maghemite nanoparticles the XG/MC blend is miscible only when the XG content is 50% or more in the blend.

3.5 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopic measurements

FTIR spectra of XG, XG – 0.02 wt% maghemite composite, MC, MC – 0.02 wt% maghemite composite, and their blend films (50/50) were recorded. Figure 6 shows, the FTIR spectra of pure and blend films in the wavelength range of 4000-500 cm^{-1} . The FTIR spectra of MC (Figure 5b) showed a hydroxyl group (–OH stretching) at 3350.3 cm^{-1} , and 1593.7 cm^{-1} is due the –OH bond belonging to water molecules, a hydrocarbon group (C-H stretching of the –CH₂ groups) at 2916.7 cm^{-1} , a –CH₂ scissoring around 1412 cm^{-1} and O- stretching at 1026 cm^{-1} [24, 25].

On the other hand, the bands of XG (Figure 5c) appeared at 3320.0 cm^{-1} for the hydroxyl groups and at 1601.2 cm^{-1} and 1371.3 cm^{-1} for the asymmetric –COO[–] stretching vibration and symmetric –COO[–] stretching vibrations of pyruvate and glucuronate groups respectively [26].

The spectrum of the XG/MC blend film was characterized by the presence of the absorption bands typical to that of the pure components, with the intensity roughly proportional to the blending ratio. In the case of 50/50 XG/MC and 50/50 XG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite, the asymmetric –COO[–] stretching vibration and symmetric –COO[–] stretching vibrations of pyruvate and glucuronate groups shifted to 1598.2 cm^{-1} , 1405.8 cm^{-1} and 1596.4 cm^{-1} , 1405.6 cm^{-1} respectively (Figure 5e, 5f). It is noticed that the hydroxyl stretching bands became much broader with increasing MC content. The results confirm [27] the presence of hydrogen bonding between the hydroxyl groups of MC and carbonyl groups of XG.

Figure 5: FTIR spectra of a) MC, b) MC – maghemite nanocomposite, c) XG, d) XG – maghemite nanocomposite, e) 50/50 XG/MC blend, and f) XG/MC – maghemite nanocomposite

3.6 Morphological studies

All the solution-casted films of XG, XG – maghemite nanocomposite, MC, MC – maghemite nanocomposite and their blend films (50/50) were characterized by SEM to check the morphology of the blends/nanocomposites. The results are given in Figure 6.

Figure 6: SEM micrographs for a) MC, b) MC – maghemite nanocomposite, c) XG, d) XG – maghemite nanocomposite, e) 50/50 XG/MC blend, and f) 50/50 XG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite

50/50 XG/MC blend (Figure 6e) did not show any aggregated particles and it can be observed that the MC granule was well distributed in the XG matrix, confirming a good interaction between XG and MC. It was distinctly observed that the blend is homogeneous, and displayed in the form of a sandwich, which

suggests that these blends were miscible [27]. The XG – maghemite nanocomposite (Figure 6d) and 50/50 XG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite (Figure 6f) shows the uniform distribution of maghemite nanoparticles.

3.7 Thermogravimetric analysis

Figure 7: TGA curves of a) XG, b) 90/10 XG/MC, c) 70/30 XG/MC, d) 50/50 XG/MC, and e) MC

Figure 8: TGA curves of composites of 0.02 wt% maghemite with a) XG, b) 90/10 XG/MC, c) 70/30 XG/MC, d) 50/50 XG/MC, e) 30/70 XG/MC, f) 10/90 XG/MC, and g) MC

Table 2: Parameters evaluated from the thermograms of XG, MC, XG/MC blends and their maghemite composites

Composition		Temperature at different weight loss ($\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$)					
		T ₀	T ₂₀	T ₄₀	T ₅₀	T ₆₀	T _{max}
GG/HPMC blends	0/100	184	199	240	256	285	305
	50/50	187	215	261	277	297	329
	70/30	206	222	264	272	281	313
	90/10	230	247	278	284	295	318
	100/0	244	263	289	293	303	351
blend GG/HPMC maghemite composites	0/100	203	235	264	277	301	318
	10/90	199	237	276	294	313	331
	30/70	204	253	291	309	321	335
	50/50	214	261	296	310	336	355
	70/30	227	274	299	311	339	359
	90/10	247	282	315	328	348	364
	100/0	271	293	324	337	365	375

The samples of XG, XG – maghemite nanocomposite, MC, MC – maghemite nanocomposite, XG/MC blends (90/10, 70/30, and 50/50) and XG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite were characterized by thermogravimetric analyzer under nitrogen environment (Figure 7, and 8). TG curve shows that the samples have two degradation stages - the first stage is the water loss of films and the second stage which includes the depolymerisation, cellulose ethers degradation, decomposition (thermal and oxidative), steaming, and disposal of volatile compounds [28].

The temperature characteristics are calculated and shown in Table 2. The thermal characteristics of the blend compositions showed composition dependency. Addition of maghemite nanoparticle improved the thermal stability of the pure polymers and the blends. The blend – composites showed composition depended thermal properties confirming intermolecular interaction between the polymers.

3.8 Tensile strength measurements

XG/MC blends showed composition dependent tensile properties (Table 3). 90/10, 70/30 XG/MC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite composites also showed improved composition dependent tensile properties.

Table 3: Tensile strength at yield, % of elongation and tensile modulus of XG, MC, and XG/MC blends and their wt% maghemite composites

Composition		Tensile Strength at Yield (MPa)	% Elongation	Tensile Modulus (MPa)
XG/MC blends	0/100	38.21	10.74	978.6
	70/30	32.4	7.12	722.4
	90/10	29.7	6.45	689.8
	100/0	27.4	6.12	647.3
XG/MC blend/maghemite composites	0/100	36.5	9.54	945.8
	10/90	33.1	8.88	726.5
	30/70	32.5	7.56	682.6
	50/50	31.2	6.55	645.4
	70/30	29.6	6.21	602.3
	90/10	28.7	5.87	596.6
	100/0	26.8	5.48	587.8

5. Conclusion

Based on viscosity, ultrasonic velocity, density and refractive index measurements, it is found that the polymer blend of XG/MC blend is miscible when XG content is 50% and more in the blend. The variation of temperature did not have any significant effect on the miscibility. The morphology, thermal and mechanical properties were analysed using SEM, TGA, and tensile strength measurement techniques. The effect of 0.02 wt% maghemite on the properties of XG, MC, and their blends studies and showed that 0.02 wt% maghemite compatibilizes the XG/MC blends.

6. Acknowledgement

The co-author, P. Prasad acknowledges the financial support provided by VGST (CISEE - GRD No. 538), Govt. of Karnataka, India for the purchase of some of the instruments used to carry out the research work.

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